

**STUDIES ON ATANGANA-BALEANU FRACTIONAL
ORDER INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS WITH
IMPULSIVE CONDITIONS IN BANACH SPACES**

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Submitted by

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I, **Dr. M. MALLIKA ARJUNAN**, declare that this thesis, entitled “**STUDIES ON ATANGANA-BALEANU FRACTIONAL ORDER INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS WITH IMPULSIVE CONDITIONS IN BANACH SPACES**” submitted for the award of the degree of **Doctor of Science in Mathematics** of this University, has not been submitted earlier for the award of any degree or diploma of this or any other University.

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This is to certify that the thesis, entitled “**STUDIES ON ATANGANA-BALEANU FRACTIONAL ORDER INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS WITH IMPULSIVE CONDITIONS IN BANACH SPACES**” has been submitted by **Dr. M. MALLIKA ARJUNAN** for the award of the degree of **Doctor of Science in Mathematics** of Srinivas University.

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List of Abbreviations

Name	Description
A-B	Atangana-Baleanu
ABFDE	Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential equation
ABFFDI	Atangana-Baleanu fractional functional differential inclusion
ABFFDS	Atangana-Baleanu fractional functional differential system
ABFVFIDI	Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusion
ABFSIDE	Atangana-Baleanu fractional semi-linear integro-differential equation
ABFSNIDE	Atangana-Baleanu fractional semi-linear neutral integro-differential equation
FC	Fractional calculus
FDEs	Fractional differential equations
FDS	Fractional differential system
FIDS	Fractional integro-differential system
FFDE	Fractional functional differential equation
ID	Infinite delay
IIDEs	Instantaneous impulsive differential equations
K.F.T	Krasnoselskii fixed point theorem
KMNC	Kuratowski measures of non-compactness
MNC	Measures of non-compactness
NII	Non-instantaneous impulses
PDEs	Partial differential equations
R.C	Relatively compact
SDD	State-dependent delay

List of Notations and Symbols

Symbol	Meaning
\mathbb{R}	The set of real numbers
\mathbb{R}^+	The set of positive real numbers in $(0, \infty)$
\mathbb{N}	The set of natural numbers
$\ x\ $	Norm of an element x in a normed space
\mathcal{PC}	Piece-wise continuous functions
E	Banach space
${}^C D_t^\alpha$	Caputo fractional derivative of order α
$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$	Atangana-Baleanu Caputo fractional derivative of order ϑ

ABSTRACT

The research reported in this thesis deals with the problem of existence results for various types of Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential systems with impulsive conditions in Banach spaces. We first study the existence of a solution for Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential and integro-differential systems with non-instantaneous impulses in Banach spaces. Next, existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusions with non-instantaneous impulses in Banach spaces are discussed. Then, we analyze the existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional neutral integro-differential systems with infinite delay through sectorial operators in Banach spaces. Furthermore, we discuss the existence results of Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential inclusions with state-dependent delay in Banach spaces. Then, we examine the non-instantaneous impulsive Atangana-Baleanu fractional-order delay differential systems in Banach spaces. Finally, existence and controllability of Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential equation with infinite delay and impulsive effects in Banach spaces are discussed.

Our approach here is based on the fixed point techniques. Several examples are provided to illustrate the obtained results.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Fractional Differential System

Generalization have always been an interesting subject in mathematics. One example is the continuous gamma function which interpolates between the factorials. Another one is the fractional differential/integral operators which interpolates between integer order differential/integral operators. In fact analytic continuation of the gamma function for $x \leq 0$ plays an important role when we construct the theory of fractional order differential/integral operators from the corresponding integer order operators.

The field of fractional calculus is almost as old as calculus itself, but over the last decades the usefulness of this mathematical theory in applications as well as its merits in pure mathematics has become more and more evident. Recently a number of textbooks [17, 19, 28, 71, 78, 99, 106, 127, 128] have been published on this field dealing with various aspects in different ways. Possibly the easiest access to the idea of the non-integer differential and integral operators studied in the field of fractional calculus is given by Cauchy's well known representation of an n -fold integral as a convolution integral

$$\begin{aligned} J^n y(x) &= \int_0^x \int_0^{x_{n-1}} \cdots \int_0^{x_1} y(x_0) dx_0 \cdots dx_{n-2} dx_{n-1} \\ &= \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^{1-n}} y(t) dt, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}_+, \end{aligned}$$

where J^n is the n -fold integral operator with $J^0 y(x) = y(x)$. Replacing the discrete factorial $(n-1)!$ with Euler's continuous gamma function $\Gamma(n)$, which satisfies $(n-1)! =$

$\Gamma(n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, one obtains a definition of non-integer order integral, i.e.

$$J^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x \frac{1}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} y(t) dt, \quad \alpha, x \in \mathbb{R}_+.$$

Several important aspects of fractional calculus originate from non-integer order derivatives, which can simplest be defined as concatenation of integer order differentiation and fractional integration, i.e.

$$D^\alpha y(x) = D^n J^{n-\alpha} y(x) \quad \text{or} \quad D_*^\alpha y(x) = J^{n-\alpha} D^n y(x),$$

where n is the integer satisfying $\alpha \leq n < \alpha + 1$ and $D^n, n \in \mathbb{N}$, is the n -fold differential operator with $D^0 y(x) = y(x)$. The operator D^α is usually denoted as Riemann-Liouville differential operator, while the operator D_*^α is named Caputo differential operator. The fact that there is obviously more than one way to define non-integer order derivatives is one of the challenging and rewarding aspects of this mathematical field.

During the past three decades, the subject of fractional calculus (that is, calculus of integrals and derivatives of arbitrary order) has gained considerable popularity and importance, mainly due to its demonstrated applications in numerous diverse and widespread fields in science and engineering. For example, fractional calculus has been successfully applied to problems in system biology, physics, chemistry and biochemistry, hydrology, medicine and finance. In many cases these new fractional-order models are more adequate than the previously used integer-order models, because fractional derivatives and integrals enable the description of the memory and hereditary properties inherent in various materials and processes that are governed by anomalous diffusion. Hence, there is a growing need to find the solution behaviour of these fractional differential equations. For more details on this theory and on its applications, we suggest the reader to refer the books [17, 19, 28, 71, 78, 99, 106, 127, 128] and cited references therein.

Physical and geometrical interpretations of fractional calculus are discussed by Podlubny in [106]. However the theory and applications of fractional calculus in control theory is in just initial stages of development. There has been a significant development in fractional differential equations. One can see the monographs of Baleanu et al. [28], Hilfer [71], Kilbas et al. [78], Miller and Ross [99], Zhou [127, 128] and A. Atangana [17, 19]. Recently, there has been a significant development in the existence and uniqueness

of solutions of initial and boundary value problem for fractional differential equations [9, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 30, 31, 38, 39, 51–53, 64, 73, 81, 90–92, 97, 101, 103, 105, 108, 112, 113, 115, 117].

1.2 History of Fractional Calculus

The birthday of so-called “Fractional Calculus” is usually cited by most authors on this topic as a specific day. L’Hopital wrote a letter to Leibniz on September 30, 1695, inquiring about a special notation he had used in his writings for the n th-derivative of the linear function $f(x) = x, \frac{D^n x}{Dx^n}$. L’Hopital presented the issue to Leibniz, “What would happen if $n = \frac{1}{2}$ ”? L’Hopital’s posed the question to Leibniz, what would the result be if $n = \frac{1}{2}$?. “An apparent contradiction, from which one day beneficial conclusions will be deduced,” Leibniz responded. Fractional calculus was formed from these words.

Fractional calculus became largely a subject reserved for the greatest brains in mathematics following L’Hopital and Leibniz’s initial inquisition. Fourier, Euler, Laplace is among the numerous who tried to calculate fractional and mathematical consequences [102]. Many have found, using their own notation and methodology, definitions that fit the concept of a non-integer order integral or derivative. The Riemann-Liouville and Grunwald-Letnikov definitions are the most well-known of these definitions in the field of fractional calculus (but not yet in the rest of the world).

The greater part of the mathematical theory applicable to the study of fractional computation was developed before the turn of the century 20. Indeed, the most fascinating advances in engineering and scientific application have occurred in the last 100 years. The mathematics has in some cases had to change to meet the requirements of physical reality. Caputo reformulated the more ‘classic’ definition of the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative in order to use integer order initial conditions to solve his fractional order differential equations [78, 106, 128]. As recently as 1996, Kolwankar reformulated again, the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative in order to differentiate no-where differentiable fractal functions [83].

Based on research conducted over the last 300 years, Leibniz's response has shown to be at least half correct. It is obvious that many applications and physical manifestations of fractional calculus have been discovered, particularly in the twentieth century. These applications, as well as the mathematical background that surrounds fractional calculus, are not at all paradoxical. While the physical meaning is difficult (if not impossible) to understand, the definitions are no more stringent than their integer order equivalents.

1.2.1 Special Functions

(a) Gamma function

One of the basic functions of fractional calculus is Euler's Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$, which generalizes the factorial n and allows n to take non-integer and even complex values.

Definition 1.2.1. [106, p.no 1]. *The Gamma function $\Gamma(z)$ is defined by the integral*

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{z-1} dt,$$

which converges in the right half of the complex plane $\Re(z) > 0$, $z \in C$. It has the property that $\Gamma(z + 1) = z\Gamma(z)$. From this, we note that, for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Gamma(n + 1) = n!$.

(b) Beta function

It is more convenient to use the β function instead of a certain combination of values of the gamma function.

Definition 1.2.2. [106, p.no 1]. *The β function is defined by*

$$\beta(z, w) = \int_0^1 \tau^{z-1} (1 - \tau)^{w-1} d\tau, \quad \Re(z) > 0, \quad \Re(w) > 0, \quad z, w \in C.$$

The relationship between gamma function and beta function is given by

$$\beta(z, w) = \frac{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(w)}{\Gamma(z + w)}$$

from which it follows that $\beta(z, w) = \beta(w, z)$.

(c) Mittag-Leffler function

Aside from the gamma function, Euler discovered another significant function called the exponential function e^z , which is crucial in the theory of integer-order differential equations. For non-integer order differential equations, the Mittag-Leffler function is defined by substituting the factorial with a gamma function, which simplifies to an exponential function when the order is an integer.

Definition 1.2.3. [106, p.no 16]. *The function $E_\alpha(z)$ defined by*

$$E_\alpha(z) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} \quad (z \in C, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0), \quad (1.2.1)$$

was introduced by Mittag-Leffler and is, therefore, known as the Mittag-Leffler function.

The Mittag-Leffler function $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$, generalizing the one in (1.2.1), is defined by

$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)} \quad (z, \beta \in C, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0). \quad (1.2.2)$$

This function is some times called a Mittag-Leffler type function.

In particular, when $\alpha = 1$ and $\alpha = 2$, we have from (1.2.1)

$$\begin{aligned} E_1(z) &= e^z, \\ E_2(z) &= \cosh(\sqrt{z}). \end{aligned}$$

When $\beta = 1$, $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$ coincides with the Mittag-Leffler function (1.2.1), namely

$$E_{\alpha,1}(z) = E_\alpha(z) \quad (z \in C, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0).$$

The particular cases of (1.2.2) are given by

$$E_{1,2}(z) = \frac{e^{z-1}}{z}, \quad E_{2,2}(z) = \frac{\sin h(\sqrt{z})}{\sqrt{z}}.$$

In fractional calculus, Mittag-Leffler functions perform a unique role. When fractional calculus approaches are used to solve specific issues, they frequently occur. Because the basic solution of a fractional linear differential equation with constant coefficients is stated in terms of Mittag-Leffler type functions, this is the case.

1.3 Impulsive Differential Equations

Many real world processes and phenomena which are subjected during their development to short-term external influences can be modeled as impulsive differential equations. Their duration is negligible in comparison with the total duration of the original process and phenomena. The perturbations can be reasonably well-approximated as being instantaneous changes of state, or in the form of impulses. The governing equations of such phenomena may be modeled as impulsive differential equations, which allows discontinuities in the evolution of the state. Lately, there has been a growing interest in the study of impulsive differential equations as these equations provide a natural framework for mathematical modeling of many real world phenomena, such as mechanics, electrical engineering, medicine, biology, chemistry and control theory etc. Due to the great development in the theory of impulsive differential equations as well as having wide applications in various fields [84].

Impulsive differential equations are usually defined as an ordinary differential equation coupled with a difference equation, although other formulations do exist. The difference equation is usually given by

$$\Delta x(t) = I(t, x(t)) = x(t^+) - x(t^-), \quad (1.3.1)$$

where $x(t^+) = \lim_{s \rightarrow t^+} x(s)$ and $x(t^-) = \lim_{s \rightarrow t^-} x(s)$ denote the right-hand and left-hand limits, respectively. Equation (1.3.1) is to be satisfied when some spatio-temporal relation $h(t, x(t)) = 0$ is satisfied. In general then, we are led to an impulsive differential equation having the form

$$x'(t) = f(t, x(t)), \quad h(t, x(t)) \neq 0, \quad (1.3.2)$$

$$\Delta x(t) = I(t, x(t)), \quad h(t, x(t)) = 0. \quad (1.3.3)$$

Thus for as long as we have $h(t, x(t)) \neq 0$, then the evolution of the state is governed by the ordinary differential equation (1.3.2). At such time that $h(t, x(t)) = 0$, then the state undergoes an impulse and instantly changes by some amount $I(t, x(t))$ according to (1.3.3). This causes a jump discontinuity in the solution. Following this impulsive action,

and assuming $h(t, x(t))$ is nonzero for some time thereafter, then the solution will continue to evolve according to (1.3.2) until it again undergoes an impulse.

The theory of impulsive differential equations is much richer than the corresponding theory of differential equations without impulse effects. For example, initial value problems of such equations may not, in general, possess any solutions at all even when the corresponding differential equation is smooth enough; fundamental properties such as continuous dependence relative to initial data may be violated, and qualitative properties like stability may need a suitable new interpretation. Moreover, a simple impulsive differential equation may exhibit several new phenomenon such as rhythmical beating, merging of solutions, and noncontinuability of solutions. The properties of the impulsive and the classical continuous models differ greatly, so deep investigations of the impulsive models are required. Therefore it is beneficial to study the theory of impulsive differential equations as a well deserved discipline, due to the increasing applications of impulsive differential equations in various fields.

1.4 Integro-differential Equations

IDEs arise naturally in the study of stochastic processes with jumps, and more precisely in Lévy processes. A Lévy process is a stochastic process with independent and stationary increments. Informally speaking, it represents the random motion of a particle whose successive displacements are independent and statistically identical over different time intervals of the same length. These processes generalize the concept of Brownian motion, and may contain jump discontinuities.

By the Lévy-Khintchine Formula, the infinitesimal generator of any symmetric Lévy process is given by a linear integro-differential operator of the form

$$Lu(x) = - \sum_{i,j} a_{ij} \partial_{ij} u + PV \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} (u(x) - u(x+y)) d\mu(y),$$

where $A = (a_{ij})$ is a non-negative definite matrix and μ is a measure satisfying

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \min(1, |y|^2) d\mu(y) < \infty.$$

For example, let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a bounded domain, and let us consider a Lévy process $X_t, t \geq 0$, starting at $x \in \Omega$. Let $u(x)$ be the expected first passage time, i.e., the expected time $\mathbb{E}[\tau]$, where $\tau = \inf\{t > 0 : X_t \notin \Omega\}$ is the first time at which the particle exits the domain. Then, u solves the following integro-differential equation

$$\begin{cases} Lu = 1 & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \Omega, \end{cases}$$

where L is the infinitesimal generator of X_t .

Why studying integro-differential equations?

To a great extent, the study of IDEs is motivated by real world applications. Indeed, there are many situations in which a nonlocal equation gives a significantly better model than a PDEs, as explained next.

In Mathematical Finance it is particularly important to study models involving jump processes, since the prices of assets are frequently modeled following a Lévy process. Note that jump processes are very natural in this situation, since asset prices can have sudden changes. These models have become increasingly popular for modeling market fluctuations since the work of Merton [98] in 1976, both for risk management and option pricing purposes.

IDEs appear also in Ecology. Indeed, optimal search theory predicts that predators should adopt search strategies based on long jumps where prey is sparse and distributed unpredictably, Brownian motion being more efficient only for locating abundant prey. Thus, reaction-diffusion problems with nonlocal diffusion such as

$$u_t + Lu = f(u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^n$$

arise naturally when studying such population dynamics. The equation appear also in physical models of plasmas and flames; see [94], and references therein.

It is worth saying that in these problems the nonlocal diffusion (instead of a classical one) changes completely the behavior of the solutions. For example, consider the above problem with $L = (-\Delta)^s$, $f(u) = u - u^2$, and with compactly supported initial data. Then,

in both cases $s = 1$ and $s \in (0, 1)$, there is an invasion of the unstable state $u = 0$ by the stable one, $u = 1$. However, in the classical case ($s = 1$) the invasion front position is linear in time, while in case $s \in (0, 1)$ the front position will be exponential in time. For more details, please refer [37].

1.5 Neutral Functional Differential Equations

By a neutral functional differential equations or hereditary functional differential equation we mean an equation in which the rate of change of a system, $\dot{x}(t)$, at time t is determined almost everywhere by the values of x and \dot{x} over some past interval of time (we will assume the past: interval of time is finite or infinite). That is, a class of equations depend on past as well as present values but which involve derivatives with delays as well as the function itself. Such equations historically have been referred to as neutral functional differential equations. A good guide to the literature for neutral functional differential equations is the book by Hale and Lunel [61] and the references therein. Many real systems are quite sensitive to sudden changes. This fact may suggest that proper mathematical models of systems should consist of some neutral equations. Indeed we may find that effects of neutral term can be quite significant in real mathematical models. Neutral delay differential equations form a branch of delay differential equations. Neutral delay equations have been suggested as population models occasionally. But usually they do not fit well into the available theory of neutral delay equations. In general neutral delay equations have been considered to be difficult in comparison with standard delay equations.

Neutral differential equations arise in several domains of applied mathematics and so these types of equations have gained attention in recent years. Generally, neutral integro-differential equations with or without delay serve as abstract formulation of many partial neutral integro-differential equations which arise in problems connected with heat flow in materials with memory, viscoelasticity, heat conduction, wave propagation and many physical phenomena. Thus, it is significant to analyze the existence and controllability (approximate/Exact) problem of such systems in infinite dimensional spaces. For additional details on Neutral functional differential equations, we suggest the reader to

refer[62, 63, 72, 80, 83, 107, 121] and references cited therein.

A DDEs [12, 70, 109] is a differential equation where the state variable appears with delayed argument.

This can manifest itself in many ways. Simplest scenario is

- Constant delay DDEs:

$$u'(t) = f(t, u(t), u(t - \tau)), \quad u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

where $\tau > 0$ is a constant.

- DDEs with Time-Dependent Delay:

$$u'(t) = f(t, u(t), u(t - \tau(t))), \quad u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

where $\tau(t) \geq 0$ is a given function.

- DDEs with State-Dependent Delay:

$$u'(t) = f(t, u(t), u(t - \tau(t, u(t)))), \quad u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$$

where $\tau(t, u(t)) \geq 0$ is a given function.

Both state-dependent delays and impulsive fractional order integro-differential equations are important features commonly encountered in many of the same systems. If a system exhibits both of these properties, then we are led to consider impulsive fractional order integro-differential equations with state-dependent delay, which is the theme of this thesis.

1.6 Differential Inclusions

Set-valued analysis is a scientific discipline of fairly recent origin. The emergence of set-valued maps perhaps has given a new approach to study mathematical concepts. Set-valued maps allow us to get away from the restriction that a map is bijective when we want to solve an equation. Everybody meets set-valued maps very early in his mathematical education, as inverses of maps which are not one-to-one, but in elementary lectures the

set-valued aspect is usually suppressed by means of elementary tricks or restrictions which make sense for practical purposes; think of $f(x) = x^2$ which has the inverse $f^{-1}(x) = \{-\sqrt{x}, \sqrt{x}\}$, from $\mathbb{R}^+ = \{r \in \mathbb{R} : r \geq 0\}$ to $2^{\mathbb{R}}$ (the subsets of \mathbb{R}); or think of a linear operator $T : X \rightarrow Y$ with kernel $N(T) \neq 0$; in which case one uses trick to consider $T : X/N(T) \rightarrow R(T)$, defined by $\widehat{T}\widehat{x} = Tx$ for $\widehat{x} = x + N(T)$, which is one-to-one and therefore has a single-valued inverse $\widehat{T}^{-1} : R(T) \rightarrow X/N(T)$.

In many more advanced topics of analysis it is not so easy to overcome the set-valuedness and therefore one has created a theory of such maps which we simply call set-valued maps. So set-valued map is a map $F : D \subset X \rightarrow 2^Y$ which associates to each $x \in D$ a subset $F(x)$ of Y .

Conceptionally, the simplest idea in the study of set-valued maps is to look for selections, i.e., single-valued maps $f : D \rightarrow Y$ such that $f(x) \in F(x) (\forall x \in D)$, which allow to reduce a set-valued problem to a single-valued one, to some extent. Of course selections are only useful if they have some nice properties like continuity or measurability. The existence of such selections under reasonably general assumptions is an interesting problem. It is intimately connected to continuity and measurability properties of the set-valued maps, but much depends also on the properties of the sets $F(x)$ (like compactness, convexity, etc.).

Taking into account uncertainties, disturbances, modeling errors, etc., leads naturally to set-valued maps and differential inclusions. When we wish to treat a problem quantitatively, by looking for solutions common to a set of data sharing qualitative properties, uncertainties, disturbances, modeling errors, etc., occur. Therefore set-valued analysis plays an important role in the field of qualitative physics, a rapidly growing branch of Artificial Intelligence.

There is a great variety of motivations that led mathematicians to study dynamical systems having velocities not uniquely determined by the state of the system, but depending loosely upon it, i.e., to replace differential equations

$$x' = f(x)$$

by differential inclusions

$$x' \in f(x)$$

when F is the set-valued map that associates to the state x of the system the set of feasible solutions.

The motivation for the study of differential inclusions came from control theory. There we encounter dynamical systems described by an equation of the form $x'(t) = f(t, x(t), u(t))$ where $u(t)$ is the control parameter. Every solution of this equation also solves the differential inclusion $x'(t) \in F(t, x(t))$ where $F(t, x(t)) = \{f(t, x, u) : u \in U\}$ and this formulation has the advantage that the control variables do not appear explicitly. Also implicit differential equations can be viewed as differential inclusions, specifically if we have $f(t, x, x') = 0$. Then, if we define $F(t, x) = \{z : f(t, x, z) = 0\}$, the implicit differential equations take the form $x' \in F(t, x)$. For further reading refer the monographs [23, 46, 77, 127] and also see [90, 93, 113, 118].

1.7 Existence

In fact fractional differential equations are considered as an alternative model to nonlinear differential equations [34]. It draws a great application in nonlinear oscillations of earthquakes, many physical phenomena such as seepage flow in porous media and in fluid dynamic traffic models. Fractional derivative can eliminate the deficiency of continuum traffic flow. The most important advantage of using fractional differential equations in these and other applications [66] is their nonlocal property. It is well known that the integer order differential operator is a local operator but the fractional order differential operator is non-local. This means that the next state of a system depends not only upon its current state but also upon all of its historical states. This is probably the most relevant feature for making this fractional tool useful from an applied standpoint and interesting from a mathematical standpoint and in turn led to the sustained study of theory of fractional differential equations [78].

The existence of solutions for fractional integro-differential equations via resolvent operator investigated in [3] and the existence of fractional neutral functional differential

equations are discussed in [4] whereas the existence of solutions of fractional differential equations by using fixed point techniques have been discussed by several authors [9, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 30, 31, 38, 39, 51–53, 64, 73, 81, 90–92, 97, 101, 103, 105, 108, 112, 113, 115, 117].

Fractional calculus, which is as old as the traditional calculus and generalization of it. It is a brilliant medium to analyze the world around us via the fields of pure and applied mathematics [17, 19, 20]. Due to its long - term memory retaining and hereditary property fractional calculus receiving a lot of attention from diverse fields of researchers all around the world. By the continuous dedicated contribution of mathematicians such as Caputo, Riemann, Liouville, and so forth, the fractional calculus becomes the potential new field of research with lots of new ideas everyday which attracts the young researchers towards this field. In [10, 74], the authors developed the fractional differential operator for a function and several generalizations of such operators concerned with some fractional derivatives as such Caputo, Caputo-katugampola and Atangana-Baleanu. These operators are helpful in solving many problems in population growth and other models. The prime feature of fractional calculus is obtaining the solution through the examination of its available existence and uniqueness results via different techniques in fixed point methods, we refer [7, 8, 13, 14, 76, 88, 89, 111].

The Liouville - Caputo fractional derivative kernel which has memory effects based on the power law having singularity in its origin. Here, power law is not enough to model all the physical problems. Therefore, Liouville - Caputo's definition for fractional derivatives is less effective. In [38], the new notion of fractional derivative having no singular kernel is used. In [39], authors have investigated the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operator and it possesses a regular kernel which was the special feature about it. To show the significance of Caputo -Fabrizio operator the authors developed several numerical simulations using the Laplace transform algorithm; more works related with this fractional derivative are given in [17–20]. In [17–19], Atangana and Baleanu proposed a new kernel on the basis of the Mittag-Leffler function; the proposed kernel is nonlocal and nonsingular. Interesting observation is that their fractional integral is the fractional average of the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral of the given function and the function itself. The fractional derivatives proposed by Atangana and Baleanu are at the same time filters and

fractional derivatives.

The sudden change experienced by the state of existence at particular moments happens generally in modelling the real-life problems which is almost similar to the graphs which is not always a straight line having some ups and downs at particular momentum. Likewise, the mathematical modelling of such natural processes was framed by instantaneous impulsive differential equations. The processes with such features occur in almost every field such as physics, chemistry, biology, economics and dynamics. For further references, one can go through the monographs by Benchohra et al. [33], Lakshmikantham et al. [84], and the papers of Mallika Arjunan et al. [93], Li and Liu [86] for more comments and citations. In the last few decades, investigating the theory of instantaneous impulsive evolution equations in Banach space has become an important topic of research due to its wide applicability in diverse fields. For more references, we refer [33, 76, 93, 111].

The simulation process described by instantaneous impulsive ordinary and partial differential equations captures the evolution process and its small perturbations with much perfection. The perturbation occurs discretely at random moments and remains active for some finite time duration and it is negligible when compared to the duration of the total process. In brief, the problems with abrupt and instantaneous changes were framed by impulsive ordinary and partial differential equations with instantaneous impulses. However, instantaneous impulses are not sufficient to explain the evolution process in all cases. For example, pharmacotherapy. In [69], Hernandez and O' Regan considered the hemodynamic equilibrium for the simple understanding of impulse of non-instantaneous nature. The hemodynamic equilibrium is the introduction of drugs in the blood and consequently followed by the absorption of drugs by the body. In this process, the effectiveness of a drug remains in an active state for some time of finite duration. Here, it is a continuous and gradual process different from instantaneous process is known to be non-instantaneous impulsive in nature. The partial differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses have been used widely to describe realistic models with accuracy.

In [41, 43, 69, 101, 117], several authors have started showing importance towards the non-linear equations having non-instantaneous impulses. In [105], Pierre et al. investigated semi-linear abstract differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses and used the semigroup theory to obtain the existence results of mild solutions for the same system.

Colao et al. [43] obtained the existence of solutions for a second-order differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and delay on an unbounded interval by establish a compactness criterion in a certain class of functions. In [123], Yu and Wang used the semigroup theory and fixed point methods to study the solutions of periodic boundary value problems for non-linear cases with non-instantaneous impulses on Banach spaces. In [119], Wang and Li studied the non-linear ordinary differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses for periodic boundary value problems. For further reference, we refer [1, 82, 97, 114, 120].

In recent times, several authors have started showing more interest towards non-linear fractional differential equations with non-instantaneous equations, we refer [1, 41, 50, 82, 97, 114]. In [50], the authors have studied the fractional functional integro-differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses and discussed the existence, uniqueness and continuous dependence of mild solutions. In [97], Meeraj et al. investigated the fractional non-instantaneous impulsive integro-differential equations with nonlocal conditions and examined the existence of a solution using non-compact semigroup theory and fixed point theorem. In [82], Kumar et al. furnished the sufficient conditions for the existence results of mild solutions for Atangana - Baleanu non-instantaneous impulse fractional differential system. Recently, Mallika Arjunan et al. [90, 91] analyzed the existence results of various fractional differential systems through A-B derivative under suitable fixed point theorem.

Motivated by the above facts, in this thesis, we have been studied the existence and controllability results for different types of A-B fractional differential and integro-differential systems (equations/inclusions) with impulsive conditions (instantaneous/non-instantaneous) in Banach spaces under suitable fixed point theorem.

1.8 Controllability

Control theory is an interdisciplinary branch of engineering and mathematics that deals with the behavior of dynamical systems with inputs, and how their behavior is modified by feedback. The usual objective of control theory is to control a system, often called the plant, so its output follows a desired control signal, called the reference, which may be a fixed or changing value. To do this a controller is designed, which monitors the output

and compares it with the reference. The difference between actual and desired output, called the error signal, is applied as feedback to the input of the system, to bring the actual output closer to the reference. Some topics studied in control theory are stability (whether the output will converge to the reference value or oscillate about it), controllability and observability.

A systematic study of controllability was started at the beginning of sixties in the last century, when the theory of controllability based on the description in the form of state space for both time-invariant and time-varying linear control systems was worked out. The mathematical control theory exhibits a wide variety of techniques that go beyond those associated with traditional applied mathematics. Generally, controllability is one of the important concepts in which the study of steering a dynamical system from the given initial value to any other state or in the neighborhood of state under some admissible controls. The tools of control theory are drawn from many branches of mathematics such as ordinary, functional and partial differential equations (PDEs), functional analysis, algebra, geometry, probability theory, numerical analysis and computation. Control mechanisms are widespread in nature and used by living organisms in order to maintain essential variables such as body temperature and blood sugar levels at desired set points. Therefore, in recent years controllability problems for various types of linear and nonlinear dynamical systems have been studied in many publications (see [9, 27, 44, 45, 87, 111]).

1.8.1 Controllability in Infinite Dimensional Spaces

In the case of infinite dimensional systems two basic concepts of controllability can distinguished. There are exact and approximate controllability. This is strongly related to the fact that in infinite dimensional spaces there exist linear subspaces, which are not closed. Exact controllability enables to steer the system to arbitrary final state while approximate controllability means that system can be steered to arbitrary small neighborhood of the final state. Approximate controllability gives the possibility of steering the system to states which form the dense subspace in the state space. Taking this into account it is obvious that exact controllability is essentially stronger notion than approximate controllability. In other words, exact controllability always implies

approximate controllability. The converse statement is generally false. However, in the case of infinite dimensional systems exact controllability appears rather exceptionally. On the other hand, it should be stressed that in the case of finite dimensional systems, notions of exact and approximate controllability coincide.

1.9 Motivation

The objective of this thesis is to study the existence and controllability results for various types of A-B fractional differential and integro-differential system with impulsive (instantaneous/non-instantaneous) and delay (infinite delay/state-dependent) conditions in Banach spaces. We shall motivate our study by giving the occurrence of these types of equations in different fields of science and engineering.

1.9.1 Statement of Problem and Mathematical Modeling of Helical Pipe in the frame of Atangana-Baleanu derivative [2]

Assume the viscoelastic fluid at rest in helically moved circular pipe/cylinder of radius R . Initially, at time $\tau = 0^+$ the helically moved circular cylinder begins to rotate in sinusoidal form about its own axis ($\tau = 0$) with the angular velocity $\Omega \sin(\omega\tau)$ and oscillates along the same axis with $U \sin(\omega\tau)$.

Assuming above assumptions for such fluid motion, flow generates helices, this is due to fact that the streamline of helicity are helices. The governing partial differential equations for velocity distribution and shear stress profiles are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} v \frac{\partial^2 w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa^2} + \frac{v}{\kappa} \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa} - v \frac{w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\kappa^2} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}\right) \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau} \\ v \frac{\partial^2 w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa^2} + \frac{v}{\kappa} \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}\right) \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau} \\ \mu \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa} - \frac{\mu w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\kappa} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}\right) \tau_1(\kappa, \tau) \\ \mu \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}\right) \tau_2(\kappa, \tau) \end{aligned}$$

where, $v = \frac{\mu}{\rho}$ is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid.

The corresponding initial and boundary conditions are

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(\kappa, 0) = w_2(\kappa, 0) = \tau_1(\kappa, 0) = \tau_2(\kappa, 0) = \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, 0)}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, 0)}{\partial \tau} = 0 \\ w_1(R, \tau) = R\Omega \sin(\omega\tau) \text{ and } w_2(R, \tau) = U \sin(\omega\tau), \tau \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1.9.1)$$

Developing governing partial differential equations (1.9.1) of helically moved cylinder in terms of Atangana-Baleanu fractional operator, we get

$$\begin{aligned} v \frac{\partial^2 w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa^2} + \frac{v}{\kappa} \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa} - v \frac{w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\kappa^2} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial \tau^\alpha}\right) \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau}, \tau > 0 \\ v \frac{\partial^2 w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa^2} + \frac{v}{\kappa} \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial \tau^\alpha}\right) \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau} \\ \mu \frac{\partial w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \kappa} - \mu \frac{w_1(\kappa, \tau)}{\kappa} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial \tau^\alpha}\right) \tau_1(\kappa, \tau) \\ \mu \frac{\partial w_2(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau} &= \left(1 + \Lambda \frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial \tau^\alpha}\right) \tau_2(\kappa, \tau), \end{aligned}$$

where, $\frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial \tau^\alpha}$ represents Atangana-Baleanu fractional operator of order α that is defined as

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha w(\kappa, \tau)}{\partial \tau^\alpha} = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \int_0^\tau w'(\kappa, \tau) E_\alpha \left(\frac{-\alpha(z-\tau)}{1-\alpha} \right) d\tau.$$

1.9.2 RC Electrical Circuit in the frame of Atangana-Baleanu derivative [56]

Several authors replace the integer derivative by another derivative of fractional order without taking into account the dimensionality of the physical parameters. To keep the dimensionality of the fractional differential equation, a new parameter σ was introduced in [55]. For the Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative in the Liouville-Caputo or Riemann-Liouville sense, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} &\rightarrow \frac{1}{\sigma^{1-\alpha}} \cdot {}_a \mathcal{D}_t^\alpha, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \\ \frac{d^2}{dt^2} &\rightarrow \frac{1}{\sigma^{2(1-\alpha)}} \cdot {}_a \mathcal{D}_t^{2\alpha}, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1, \end{aligned} \quad (1.9.2)$$

where σ has the dimension of seconds and is associated with the temporal components in the system; when $\alpha = 1$, the aforementioned expressions are recovered in the traditional sense. Henceforth, authors apply this idea to obtain the analytical solutions of the fractional electrical circuits using the Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivatives.

Applying Kirchhoff's laws, the equation of the RC series circuit is given by

$$\mathcal{D}_t V(t) + \frac{1}{RC} V(t) = \frac{1}{RC} E(t) \quad (1.9.3)$$

where C is the capacitance, R is the resistance, and the source voltage is $E(t)$. Considering (1.9.2), the fractional equation in ABC sense 1.11.2 for the electrical circuit RC is given by

$${}_a^{ABC} \mathcal{D}_t^\alpha V(t) = \tau E(t) - \tau V(t) \quad (1.9.4)$$

where

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma^{1-\alpha}}{RC} = \tau_0 \cdot \sigma^{1-\alpha}, \quad (1.9.5)$$

τ is the fractional time constant, and $\tau_0 = \frac{1}{RC}$ is the time constant in the classical case. Now, we obtain the analytical solutions of equation (1.9.4) considering different source terms.

Unit step source, $E(t) = u(t)V$, $V(0) = V_0$, ($V_0 > 0$), equation (1.9.4) can be written as follows:

$${}_a^{ABC} D_t^\alpha V(t) = \tau u(t) - \tau V(t) \quad (1.9.6)$$

Applying the Laplace transform to (1.9.6), we have

$$\mathcal{L} \{ {}_a^{ABC} D_t^\alpha V(t) \} (s) = \tau \frac{1}{s} - \tau \tilde{V}(s), \quad (1.9.7)$$

where $\tilde{V}(s) = \mathcal{L} \{ V(t) \} (s)$. Considering

$$\mathcal{L} \{ {}_a^{ABC} D_t^\alpha V(t) \} (s) = \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \cdot \frac{s^\alpha \tilde{V}(s) - s^{\alpha-1} V(0)}{s^\alpha + \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} \quad (1.9.8)$$

substituting (1.9.8) into (1.9.7), we have

$$\frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \cdot \frac{s^\alpha \tilde{V}(s)}{s^\alpha + \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}} + \tau \tilde{V}(s) = \tau \frac{1}{s} + \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \cdot \frac{s^{\alpha-1} V_0}{s^\alpha + \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}}, \quad (1.9.9)$$

the expression for the voltage is

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{V}(s) = & \frac{\tau}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} \left[\frac{(1-\alpha)s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \frac{\tau\alpha}{B(\alpha)+\tau(1-\alpha)}} + \frac{\alpha}{s^\alpha + \frac{\tau\alpha}{B(\alpha)+\tau(1-\alpha)}} \cdot \frac{1}{s} \right] \\ & + \frac{B(\alpha)V_0}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \frac{\tau\alpha}{B(\alpha)+\tau(1-\alpha)}} \end{aligned} \quad (1.9.10)$$

Taking the inverse Laplace transform of (1.9.10), we obtain the following solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
V(t) = & \frac{\tau(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} E_{\alpha,1} \left[- \left(\frac{\tau\alpha}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} \right) t^\alpha \right] \\
& + \frac{B(\alpha)V_0}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} E_{\alpha,1} \left[- \left(\frac{\tau\alpha}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} \right) t^\alpha \right] \\
& + \frac{\tau(\alpha)}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha} \left[- \left(\frac{\tau\alpha}{B(\alpha) + \tau(1-\alpha)} \right) (t-\tau)^\alpha \right] d\tau.
\end{aligned}$$

1.9.3 A fractional SAIDR model in the frame of Atangana–Baleanu derivative [116]

The purpose of this work was to delve into a susceptible-affected-infectious-suspended-recovered (SAIDR) model, a type of fractional order model which, for the first time, was put forward in [122] employing a classical derivative aimed at SMS-based worm propagation in mobile networks, on the basis of more favourable fractional calculus theories. As long as susceptible users of mobile devices refrain from opening the links that are harmful, it is not possible for them to instantly enter into the infected state even if the malicious message is delivered to the said devices. This is the reason behind the addition of the affected state into [122] by its authors; abbreviated as state $A(t)$, it delineates the circumstance when a harmful link is delivered to a user but not yet opened. What is more, particularly if the phone is damaged, the harmful message is not invariably circulated by an infected node. Thus, another new state is also instituted, which is the suspended state, going by the abbreviation of state $D(t)$. This is of a unique quality since a harmful message cannot be circulated by an infected smart phone in spite of its existence in the given device. Lastly, the overall quantity of worm nodes are separated as follows: $N = S(t) + A(t) + I(t) + D(t) + R(t)$, i.e., $S(t)$ susceptible state, $A(t)$ affected state, $I(t)$ infected state, $D(t)$ suspended state, $R(t)$ recovered state. The integer order differential equation system which puts forth the SAIDR model in [122] can be seen below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dS(t)}{dt} &= \mu N - \gamma S - \beta SI - \mu S \\
\frac{dA(t)}{dt} &= \beta SI - \mu A - \eta A - \mu A \\
\frac{dI(t)}{dt} &= \eta A - \sigma I - \tau I - \mu I
\end{aligned} \tag{1.9.11}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dD(t)}{dt} &= \tau I - \varphi D - \mu D \\ \frac{dR(t)}{dt} &= \gamma S + \mu A + \sigma I + \varphi D - \mu R.\end{aligned}$$

The variable factors concerning the model alter at time t as follows: the susceptible node is converted into the affected state by β , the ratio of infection, when a harmful electronic message is delivered to it from another point of intersection. The worm is transmitted to the node which is in the affected state by a ratio of η in the event that it is rendered active by the affected node opening the malignant link enclosed in the message. The node shifts into the suspended state from the infected state by a transition ratio of τ . Meanwhile, certain software against malware might be set up in mobile devices in order to block or erase harmful messages. Once the said software are set up, the phone cannot permanently remain in the infected state. These safety software can also be set up in the wake of a maintenance process, provided that the phone stays in the special suspended state. Hence, the node is able to shift into the ultimate recovered state regardless of its current state. The ratios by which the node recovers from states $S(t)$, $A(t)$, $I(t)$, and $D(t)$ to state $R(t)$ are denominated as $\gamma, \mu, \sigma, \varphi$ in the order given.

In [116], authors enlarged the model (1.9.11) by substituting the time derivative by the Atangana–Baleanu derivative.

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{\kappa^{1-\theta_0}} {}^{ABC} D_t^\theta S(t) &= \mu N - \gamma S - \beta SI - \mu S \\ \frac{1}{\kappa^{1-\theta_0}} {}^{ABC} D_t^\theta A(t) &= \beta SI - \mu A - \eta A - \mu A \\ \frac{1}{\kappa^{1-\theta_0}} {}^{ABC} D_t^\theta I(t) &= \eta A - \sigma I - \tau I - \mu I \\ \frac{1}{\kappa^{1-\theta_0}} {}^{ABC} D_t^\theta D(t) &= \tau I - \varphi D - \mu D \\ \frac{1}{\kappa^{1-\theta_0}} {}^{ABC} D_t^\theta R(t) &= \gamma S + \mu A + \sigma I + \varphi D - \mu R\end{aligned}\tag{1.9.12}$$

with the initial numbers $S(0) = S_0, A(0) = A_0, I(0) = I_0, D(0) = D_0, R(0) = R_0$ where ${}_a^{ABC} D_t^\theta$ is the A-B derivative in Caputo type and $\theta \in [0, 1]$.

In this part, we prove that the system (1.9.12) has a unique solution. Implementing the fractional integral into the system (1.9.12), we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
S(t) - S(0) &= \frac{(1-\theta)\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)} [\mu N - \gamma S(t) - \beta S(t)I(t) - \mu S(t)] \\
&\quad + \frac{\theta\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)\Gamma(\theta)} \int_0^t (t-\lambda)^{\theta-1} [\mu N - \gamma S(\lambda) - \beta S(\lambda)I(\lambda) - \mu S(\lambda)] d\lambda \\
A(t) - A(0) &= \frac{(1-\theta)\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)} [\beta S(t)I(t) - \mu A(t) - \eta A(t) - \mu A(t)] \\
&\quad + \frac{\theta\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)\Gamma(\theta)} \int_0^t (t-\lambda)^{\theta-1} [\beta S(\lambda)I(\lambda) - \mu A(\lambda) - \eta A(\lambda) - \mu A(\lambda)] d\lambda \\
I(t) - I(0) &= \frac{(1-\theta)\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)} [\eta A(t) - \sigma I(t) - \tau I(t) - \mu I(t)] \\
&\quad + \frac{\theta\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)\Gamma(\theta)} \int_0^t (t-\lambda)^{\theta-1} [\eta A(\lambda) - \sigma I(\lambda) - \tau I(\lambda) - \mu I(\lambda)] d\lambda \\
D(t) - D(0) &= \frac{(1-\theta)\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)} [\tau I(t) - \varphi D(t) - \mu D(t)] \\
&\quad + \frac{\theta\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)\Gamma(\theta)} \int_0^t (t-\lambda)^{\theta-1} [\tau I(\lambda) - \varphi D(\lambda) - \mu D(\lambda)] d\lambda \\
R(t) - R(0) &= \frac{(1-\theta)\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)} [\gamma S(t) + \mu A(t) + \sigma I(t) + \varphi D(t) - \mu R(t)] \\
&\quad + \frac{\theta\kappa^{1-\vartheta}}{F(\theta)\Gamma(\theta)} \int_0^t (t-\lambda)^{\theta-1} [\gamma S(\lambda) + \mu A(\lambda) + \sigma I(\lambda) + \varphi D(\lambda) - \mu R(\lambda)] d\lambda.
\end{aligned}$$

1.10 Basic Concepts and Definitions

In order to prove the main results in this thesis, we use the following definitions and preliminary results (see for more details [53, 78, 99, 104, 106]).

1.10.1 Spaces

Definition 1.10.1. Let \mathbb{S} be a linear space over \mathbb{K} . A **norm** on \mathbb{S} is a function $\|\cdot\|$ from \mathbb{S} to \mathbb{R} such that for all $x, y \in \mathbb{S}$ and $k \in \mathbb{K}$,

(a) $\|x\| \geq 0$ and $\|x\| = 0$ if and only if $x = 0$,

(b) $\|x + y\| \leq \|x\| + \|y\|$,

(c) $\|kx\| = |k|\|x\|$.

A **normed space** is a linear space with a norm on it.

Definition 1.10.2. A normed space X over \mathbb{K} is called **Banach space** if X is complete in the metric $d(x, y) = \|x - y\|$ for every $x, y \in X$ induced by the norm $\|\cdot\|$.

Example 1.10.1. For $1 \leq p < \infty$, we define the p -norm on \mathbb{R}^n by

$$\|(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)\|_p = \left(|x_1|^p + |x_2|^p + \dots + |x_n|^p\right)^{1/p}.$$

For $p = \infty$, we define the ∞ , or maximum, norm by

$$\|(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)\|_\infty = \max\{|x_1|, |x_2|, \dots, |x_n|\}.$$

Then \mathbb{R}^n equipped with the p -norm is a finite dimensional Banach space for $1 \leq p \leq \infty$.

Definition 1.10.3. Let Y be a metric space with metric d , then the set $F = \{f_i : X \rightarrow Y, i \in I\}$ is called **uniformly bounded** if there exists an element a from Y and a positive real number M such that $d(f_i(x), a) \leq M$, for every $i \in I, x \in X$.

Definition 1.10.4. \mathcal{L}^p -spaces: Let m denote the Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R} and V be a measurable subset of \mathbb{R} . For $1 \leq p < \infty$, consider the set $\mathcal{L}^p(V)$ of all equivalence classes of p -integrable functions on V . For x in $\mathcal{L}^p(V)$, let

$$\|x\|_p = \left(\int_V |x|^p dm\right)^{1/p}.$$

1.10.2 Sets, Sequences and Functions

Definition 1.10.5. If X and Y are metric spaces with metrics d and e respectively, then a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be **continuous** at $x_0 \in X$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$, there is some μ (possibly depending on ε and x_0) such that $e(f(x), f(x_0)) < \varepsilon$ for all $x \in X$ satisfying $d(x, x_0) < \mu$. Further, f is said to be **continuous on X** if it is continuous at every point of X .

Definition 1.10.6. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in $C[a, b]$ is said to be **equicontinuous** if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there is a $\mu > 0$, depending only on ε , such that for all x_n and all $s_1, s_2 \in [a, b]$ satisfying $|s_1 - s_2| < \mu$ we have $|x_n(s_1) - x_n(s_2)| < \varepsilon$.

Definition 1.10.7. Let X and Y be linear spaces over \mathbb{K} . A **linear map** from X to Y is a function $F : X \rightarrow Y$ such that

$$F(k_1x_1 + k_2x_2) = k_1F(x_1) + k_2F(x_2)$$

for all $x_1, x_2 \in X$ and $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{K}$.

Definition 1.10.8. Let X and Y be normed spaces and $F : D(F) \rightarrow Y$ a linear operator, where $D(F) \subset X$. The operator F is said to be **bounded** if there is a real number c such that for all $x \in D(F)$, $\|F(x)\| \leq c\|x\|$. Moreover, an operator F is called a **compact linear operator** if F is linear and if for every bounded subset \mathcal{X} of X , the image $F(\mathcal{X})$ is **relatively compact**, that is, the closure of $F(\mathcal{X})$ is compact.

Definition 1.10.9. Let X, Y be normed linear spaces. A linear operator $F : X \rightarrow Y$ is called **completely continuous** if $D(F) = X$ and for every sequence $\{x_n\} \subset X$ such that $\|x_n\| \leq c$, the sequence $\{Fx_n\}$ has a subsequence which converges in Y .

1.10.3 Fixed Point Method

Let X be a Banach space and F be an operator in a way that $F : X \rightarrow X$. We say that $x \in X$ is a **fixed point** of F if $Fx = x$.

Example 1.10.2. Let us define the operator $F(x) = x^2$ for every $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$. We find the fixed points $x = 0$ and $x = 1$ for which $F(0) = 0$ and $F(1) = 1$.

When solving operator equations, fixed points occur naturally. For instance, let us consider the integral equation

$$x(t) = x_0(t) + \int_a^b f(t, s, x(s))ds, \quad t \in [a, b],$$

where x_0 is a given continuous real valued function on $[a, b]$. Let Υ denote the set of all real valued continuous functions on $[a, b]$ and

$$\mathbb{F}(x)(t) = x_0(t) + \int_a^b f(t, s, x(s))ds, \quad x \in \Upsilon, \quad t \in [a, b].$$

If for each $t \in [a, b]$, the function $f(t, s, x(s))$ is an integrable function of s on $[a, b]$ and the function $\int_a^b f(t, s, x(s))ds$ is a continuous function of t on $[a, b]$, then $\mathbb{F}(x) \in \Upsilon$. Clearly, x is a solution of this integral equation if and only if it is a fixed point of the function \mathbb{F} .

Definition 1.10.10. A mapping $F : X \rightarrow X$ is said to be **contraction** if there exists a real number k , $0 \leq k < 1$, such that $\|Fx - Fy\| \leq k\|x - y\|$ for all $x, y \in X$. Note that $\|\cdot\|$ indicates a norm in X .

Theorem 1.10.1. [35]. *Banach fixed point theorem:* If X is a Banach space and $F : X \rightarrow X$ is a contraction mapping then F has a unique fixed point.

Theorem 1.10.2. [35]. *Krasnoselskii's fixed point theorem:* Let Φ_1, Φ_2 be two operators satisfying:

(a) Φ_1 is contraction, and

(b) Φ_2 is completely continuous.

Then either

(i) the operator equation $\Phi_1 x + \Phi_2 x = x$ has a solution, or

(ii) the set $\zeta = \{u \in X : \lambda \Phi_1(\frac{u}{\lambda}) + \lambda \Phi_2 u = u\}$ is unbounded for $\lambda \in (0, 1)$.

Theorem 1.10.3. [60]. *Leray-Schauder Alternative:* Let D be a closed convex subset of a Banach space Z and assume that $0 \in D$. Let $\Gamma : D \rightarrow D$ be a completely continuous map. Then, either the set $\{z \in D : z = \lambda \Gamma(z), 0 < \lambda < 1\}$ is unbounded or the map Γ has a fixed point in D .

Theorem 1.10.4. [53]. *Schaefer's fixed point theorem:* Let P be a continuous and compact mapping on a Banach space \mathbb{X} into itself, such that the set $\{x \in \mathbb{X} : x = vPx \text{ for some } 0 \leq v \leq 1\}$ is bounded, then P has a fixed-point.

Theorem 1.10.5. [100]. *Monch fixed point theorem:* For any bounded, closed and convex subset of a Banach space E . Let $\Upsilon : B \rightarrow B$ and if the implication

$$W = \overline{\text{conv}} \Upsilon(W) \quad \text{or} \quad W = \Upsilon(W) \cup 0 \implies \beta(W) = 0$$

holds for every subset W of B , then Υ has a fixed point.

Theorem 1.10.6. [95]. *Martelli fixed point theorem:* Let X be a Banach space, and $T : X \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{b,cl,c}(X)$ be a completely continuous multi-valued map. If the set $\varepsilon = \{x \in X : \lambda x \in T(x), \lambda > 1\}$ is bounded, then T has a fixed point.

Theorem 1.10.7. [36, Chapter 2] *Arzela-Ascoli Theorem:* Let X be a compact metric space and $\{f_n\}$ a uniformly bounded, equicontinuous sequence of real valued functions on X . Then $\{f_n\}$ has a subsequence that converges uniformly on X to a continuous function f on X .

Theorem 1.10.8. Lebesgue's Dominated Convergence Theorem: Suppose $f_n : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty]$ are (Lebesgue) measurable functions such that the pointwise limit $f(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x)$ exists. Assume there is an integrable $g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ with $|f_n(x)| \leq g(x)$ for each $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Then f is integrable as is f_n for each n , and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}} f_n d\mu = \int_{\mathbb{R}} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n d\mu = \int_{\mathbb{R}} f d\mu.$$

1.10.4 Semigroup Theory

Definition 1.10.11. (Pazy [104]) Let X be a Banach space. A one parameter family $T(t)$, $0 \leq t < \infty$, of bounded linear operators from X into X is a **semigroup of bounded linear operators on X** if

- (i) $T(0) = I$, (I is the identity operator on X).
- (ii) $T(t + s) = T(t)T(s)$ for every $t, s \geq 0$ (the semigroup property).

A semigroup of bounded linear operators, $T(t)$ is **uniformly continuous** if

$$\lim_{t \downarrow 0} \|T(t) - I\| = 0.$$

Definition 1.10.12. The linear operator A defined by

$$D(A) = \left\{ x \in X : \lim_{t \downarrow 0} \frac{T(t)x - x}{t} \text{ exists} \right\}$$

and

$$Ax = \lim_{t \downarrow 0} \frac{T(t)x - x}{t} = \left. \frac{d^+ T(t)x}{dt} \right|_{t=0} \quad \text{for } x \in D(A)$$

is the **infinitesimal generator** of the semigroup $T(t)$, $D(A)$ is the domain of A .

Definition 1.10.13. Let A is a linear, not necessarily bounded operator in X , the resolvent set $\vartheta(A)$ of A is the set of all complex numbers λ for which $\lambda I - A$ is invertible, i.e., $(\lambda I - A)^{-1}$ is a bounded linear operator in X . The family $R(\lambda : A) = (\lambda I - A)^{-1}$, $\lambda \in \vartheta(A)$ of bounded linear operators is called the **resolvent** of A .

Theorem 1.10.9. (Pazy [104]) Let $T(t)$ be a uniformly continuous semigroup of bounded linear operators. Then

- (a) *There exists a constant $w \geq 0$ such that $\|T(t)\| \leq e^{wt}$.*
- (b) *There exists a unique bounded linear operator A such that $T(t) = e^{tA}$.*
- (c) *The operator A in part (b) is the infinitesimal generator of $T(t)$.*
- (d) *$t \rightarrow T(t)$ is differentiable in norm and*

$$\frac{dT(t)}{dt} = AT(t) = T(t)A.$$

Definition 1.10.14. [104] *Let X be the Banach space and A be the infinitesimal generator of a C_0 semigroup $T(t)$. Let $x_0 \in X$ and $f \in \mathcal{L}_1(0, b : X)$. The function $x \in \mathcal{C}([0, b] : X)$ given by*

$$x(t) = T(t)x_0 + \int_0^t T(t-s)f(s)ds, \quad 0 \leq t \leq b,$$

is the mild solution of the following initial value problem

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx(t)}{dt} &= Ax(t) + f(t), \quad t \in J := [0, b], \\ x(0) &= x_0. \end{aligned}$$

1.11 Methods

The theory of strongly continuous semigroups of linear operators on Banach spaces, operator semigroups for short, has become an indispensable tool in a great number of areas of modern mathematical analysis [54, 104].

The presence or absence of fixed point is an intrinsic property of a function. However many necessary and/or sufficient conditions for the existence of such points involve a mixture of algebraic order theoretic or topological properties of mapping or its domain. Fixed point theory concerns itself with a very simple and basic mathematical setting.

A point is often called fixed point when it remains invariant, irrespective of the type of transformation it undergoes. For a function f that has a set X as both domain and range, a fixed point is a point $x \in X$ for which $f(x) = x$. The fundamental theorems concerning fixed points are those of Banach, Krasnoselskii, Schaefer, Martelli and Monch. The Banach

fixed point theorem is an important source of existence and uniqueness theorem in different branch of analysis. Recently, Krasnoselskii, Schaefer, Martelli and Monch fixed point theorem are used to prove the existence of solutions of various types of Atangana-Baleanu FDS and FIDS.

1.11.1 Fractional Calculus

Definition 1.11.1. [106] For the $\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ function, $\mu \in \mathbb{R}_+$ is defined by Riemann-Liouville fractional integral order

$$I_{0+}^{\mu} \mathcal{F}(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha - s)^{\mu-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds, \quad \alpha > 0,$$

provided that the right-hand side is characterized point-wise as \mathbb{R}^+ , where Γ is a gamma function.

Definition 1.11.2. [106] Caputo fractional derivative of order $\mu \in (n - 1, n]$ is described for a continuous function $\mathcal{F} : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$,

$${}^C \mathcal{D}_{0+}^{\mu} \mathcal{F}(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \alpha)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha - s)^{n-1-\mu} \mathcal{F}^n(s) ds, \quad \alpha > 0,$$

where the integrals appearing in 1.11.1 and 1.11.2 definitions are to be taken in the manner of Bochner.

Definition 1.11.3. [18] The fractional integral of Atangnan-Baleanu (A-B) in order $\eta \in (0, 1)$ of a function $r : (d, \tau) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is specified by

$${}^{AB} I_{d+}^{\eta} r(\alpha) = \frac{1 - \eta}{B(\eta)} r(\alpha) + \frac{\eta}{B(\eta)\Gamma(\eta)} \int_d^{\alpha} (\alpha - s)^{\eta-1} r(s) ds,$$

where $B(\eta) = (1 - \eta) + \frac{\eta}{\Gamma(\eta)}$ is the normalization function which meets $B(0) = B(1) = 1$ condition.

Definition 1.11.4. [18] For $r \in H^1(d, \tau)$, $d < \tau$, the A-B fractional derivative of order $\eta \in (0, 1)$ of a function r in Caputo sense is defined by

$${}^{ABC} \mathcal{D}_{d+}^{\eta} r(\alpha) = \frac{B(\eta)}{1 - \eta} \int_d^{\alpha} r'(s) E_{\eta} \left(-\frac{\eta}{1 - \eta} (\alpha - s)^{\eta} \right) ds$$

for each $\alpha \in (d, \tau)$. Here E_{η} is the Mittag-Leffler function.

Definition 1.11.5. [18] For $r \in H^1(d, \tau)$, $d < \tau$, the A-B fractional derivative of order $\eta \in (0, 1)$ of a function r in Riemann-Liouville sense is defined by

$${}^{ABR}\mathcal{D}_{d^+}^\eta r(\alpha) = \frac{B(\eta)}{1-\eta} \frac{d}{d\alpha} \int_d^\alpha r(s) E_\eta \left(-\frac{\eta}{1-\eta} (\alpha - s)^\eta \right) ds$$

for each $\alpha \in (d, \tau)$.

1.11.2 Mild solution

In this section, we clearly derived the mild solution of the A-B fractional derivative using semigroup theory.

In particular, we consider the following systems:

$${}^{ABC}D_t^\alpha x(t) = Ax(t) + f(t, x_t), \quad t \in \cup_{i=0}^m (s_i, t_{i+1}] \subset J, \quad (1.11.1)$$

$$x(t) = I_i(t, x_t), \quad t \in \cup_{i=1}^m (t_i, s_i], \quad (1.11.2)$$

$$x_0 = \varphi \in B, \quad t \in (-\infty, 0], \quad (1.11.3)$$

and

$${}^{ABC}D_t^\alpha [x(t) - g(t, x_t)] = Ax(t) + f(t, x_t), \quad t \in \cup_{i=0}^m (s_i, t_{i+1}] \subset J, \quad (1.11.4)$$

$$x(t) = I_i(t, x_t), \quad t \in \cup_{i=1}^m (t_i, s_i], \quad (1.11.5)$$

$$x_0 = \varphi \in B, \quad t \in (-\infty, 0], \quad (1.11.6)$$

where ${}^{ABC}D_t^\alpha$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative of order $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. $A : D(A) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of α -resolvent operator $\{U_\alpha(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$, $\{V_\alpha(t)\}_{t \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $J = [0, \tau]$, $\tau > 0$ is a constant, $0 = t_0 = s_0 < t_1 < s_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_m < s_m < t_{m+1} = \tau$, are pre-fixed numbers. $f : \cup_{i=0}^m (s_i, t_{i+1}] \times B \rightarrow E$ and $g : J \times B \rightarrow E$ are given functions that satisfy assumptions to be specified later on. $I_i : (t_i, s_i] \times B \rightarrow E$ are non-instantaneous impulsive functions for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. The history function $x_t : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E$ is element of B and defined by $x_t(\theta) = x(t + \theta)$, $\theta \in (-\infty, 0]$. Here impulses are not instantaneous means these impulses start abruptly at the points t_i and their action continues on the interval $[t_i, s_i]$ and B is a phase space defined later.

Lemma 1.11.1. *To be able to determine a mild solution of the problem (1.11.1)-(1.11.3), we require to present the mild solution of the following Cauchy problem*

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{ABC}D_t^\alpha x(t) &= Ax(t) + f(t), t \in [0, \tau], 0 < \alpha < 1. \\ x(0) &= \tilde{x}_0 \in E. \end{aligned} \quad (1.11.7)$$

The mild solution of the above Cauchy problem can be described by

$$x(t) = \mathcal{G}U_\alpha(t)\tilde{x}_0 + \frac{\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s) ds + \frac{\alpha\mathcal{G}^2}{B(\alpha)} \int_0^t V_\alpha(t-s) f(s) ds, \quad (1.11.8)$$

where \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{K} are linear operators: $\mathcal{G} = \mu(\mu I - A)^{-1}$ and $\mathcal{K} = -\gamma A(\mu I - A)^{-1}$ with $\mu = \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha}$; $\gamma = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} U_\alpha(t) &= E_\alpha(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\lambda t} \lambda^{\alpha-1} (\lambda^\alpha I + \mathcal{K})^{-1} d\lambda, \\ V_\alpha(t) &= t^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\lambda t} (\lambda^\alpha I + \mathcal{K})^{-1} d\lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and Γ is a suitable path lying on $\Sigma_{(\theta,\omega)}$, and $f \in C(J, E)$.

Proof. We apply the Laplace transform on both sides of equation (1.11.7):

$$\mathcal{L}({}^{ABC}D_t^\alpha x(t))(s) = \mathcal{L}(Ax(t))(s) + \mathcal{L}(f(t))(s). \quad (1.11.9)$$

Note that we can rewrite the derivative as the product of convolution of two functions.

Thus, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}({}^{ABC}D_t^\alpha x(t))(s) &= \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \mathcal{L}\left(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha) * x'(t)\right)(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha))(s) \mathcal{L}(x'(t))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha))(s) \mathcal{L}[s\mathcal{L}(x(t))(s) - x(0)]. \end{aligned}$$

Equation (1.11.9) becomes

$$\left[\frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} s\mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha))(s) - A \right] \mathcal{L}(x(t))(s) = \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha))(s) \tilde{x}_0 + \mathcal{L}(f(t))(s). \quad (1.11.10)$$

Furthermore, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} s\mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha))(s) - A &= \frac{s^\alpha(B(\alpha) - A(1-\alpha)) - \alpha A}{(1-\alpha)(s^\alpha + \gamma)} \\ &= \frac{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}}{s^\alpha + \gamma} \frac{B(\alpha)}{\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}, \end{aligned}$$

where the operators \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{G} are given as

$$\mathcal{K} = -\gamma A(\mu I - A)^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{G} = \mu(\mu I - A)^{-1}.$$

Then (1.11.10) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(x(t))(s) &= \left[\frac{s^\alpha + \gamma}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}} \frac{1-\alpha}{B(\alpha)} \mathcal{G} \right] \frac{B(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \mathcal{L}(E_\alpha(-\gamma t^\alpha))(s) \tilde{x}_0 \\ &+ \left[\frac{s^\alpha + \gamma}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}} \frac{1-\alpha}{B(\alpha)} \mathcal{G} \right] \mathcal{L}(f(t))(s) \\ &= \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}} \mathcal{G} \tilde{x}_0 + \frac{\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} \frac{s^\alpha + \gamma}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}} \mathcal{L}(f(t))(s). \end{aligned} \quad (1.11.11)$$

Applying the inverse Laplace transform, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^{-1}\left(\frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}}\right) &= E_\alpha(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha), \\ \mathcal{L}^{-1}\left(\frac{s^\alpha}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}}\right) &= t^{-1}E_{\alpha,0}(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha) = \frac{\mathcal{K}t^{\alpha-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} - \mathcal{K}t^{\alpha-1}E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha), \\ \mathcal{L}^{-1}\left(\frac{\gamma}{s^\alpha + \mathcal{K}}\right) &= \gamma t^{\alpha-1}E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha), \end{aligned}$$

By applying the inverse Laplace transform on both sides of (1.11.11), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= \mathcal{G}E_\alpha(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha)\tilde{x}_0 \\ &+ \left[\frac{\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} t^{\alpha-1} + (\gamma - \mathcal{K}) \frac{\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)} t^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha) \right] * f(t) \\ &= \mathcal{G}E_\alpha(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha)\tilde{x}_0 + \frac{\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} t^{\alpha-1} * f(t) + \frac{\alpha\mathcal{G}^2}{B(\alpha)} t^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha) * f(t) \\ &= \mathcal{G}E_\alpha(-\mathcal{K}t^\alpha)\tilde{x}_0 + \frac{\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s) ds \\ &+ \frac{\alpha\mathcal{G}^2}{B(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(-\mathcal{K}(t-s)^\alpha) f(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

□

Using the data of Lemma (1.11.1), we provide a brief explanation of the mild solution of problem (1.11.1)-(1.11.3). The mild solution $x(t, 0, x_0)$, $t \geq 0$ of problem (1.11.1)-(1.11.3) is given by

$$x(t, 0, x_0) = \begin{cases} \varphi & \text{for } t \in (-\infty, 0], \\ X_i(t) & \text{for } t \in (s_i, t_{i+1}], i = 0, 1, \dots, m, \\ I_i(t, x_t) & \text{for } t \in (t_i, s_i], i = 1, 2, \dots, m, \end{cases}$$

where

- For $i = 0$, $t \in [0, t_1]$. Then, $X_0(t)$ is the mild solution of the Cauchy problem (1.11.7) and $\tilde{x}_0 = \varphi$, that is, $X_0(t)$ satisfies the equation (1.11.8) on $[0, t_1]$.
- For $i = 1$, $t \in [s_1, t_2]$. Then, $X_1(t)$ is the mild solution of the Cauchy problem (1.11.7) and $\tilde{x}_0 = I_1(s_1, x_{s_1})$, that is, $X_1(t)$ satisfies the equation (1.11.8) on $[s_1, t_2]$.
- For $i = 2$, $t \in [s_2, t_3]$. Then, $X_2(t)$ is the mild solution of the Cauchy problem (1.11.7) and $\tilde{x}_0 = I_2(s_2, x_{s_2})$, that is, $X_2(t)$ satisfies the equation (1.11.8) on $[s_2, t_3]$.
- ⋮
- and so on.

Depending on this explanation, we determine the definition of mild solution of the problem (1.11.1)-(1.11.3) as follows:

Definition 1.11.6. A function $x : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ such that $x \in B$ is called a mild solution of the problem (1.11.1)-(1.11.3) if $x_0 = \varphi$ and $x(t) = I_i(t, x_t)$ for $t \in (t_i, s_i]$ and each $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, satisfies the following integral equation

$$x(t) = \begin{cases} \mathcal{G}U_\alpha(t)\varphi + \frac{\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x_s) ds \\ \quad + \frac{\alpha\mathcal{G}^2}{B(\alpha)} \int_0^t V_\alpha(t-s) f(s, x_s) ds, & t \in [0, t_1], \\ \mathcal{G}U_\alpha(t-s_i)I_i(s_i, x_{\vartheta(s_i, x_{s_i})}) + \frac{\mathcal{K}\mathcal{G}(1-\alpha)}{B(\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{s_i}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x_s) ds \\ \quad + \frac{\alpha\mathcal{G}^2}{B(\alpha)} \int_{s_i}^t V_\alpha(t-s) f(s, x_s) ds, & t \in [s_i, t_{i+1}], i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 1.11.2. *To be able to determine a mild solution of the problem (1.11.4)-(1.11.6), we require to present the mild solution of the following Cauchy problem*

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{ABC}\mathcal{D}_\alpha^\vartheta[w(\alpha) - \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha))] &= \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha), \alpha \in [0, \tau], 0 < \vartheta < 1; \\ w(0) &= \tilde{w}_0 \in E. \end{aligned} \quad (1.11.12)$$

The mild solution of the above Cauchy problem can be described by

$$\begin{aligned} w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\mathcal{F}(s) + \zeta^*\mathcal{G}(s, w(s))] ds \\ &+ \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [\mathcal{F}(s) + \mathcal{Q}\mathcal{G}(s, w(s))] ds, \end{aligned} \quad (1.11.13)$$

$\mathbb{S} = \zeta^*(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ with $\zeta^* = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$; $\mathcal{Q} = -\frac{B(\vartheta)\mathbb{T}}{\vartheta\mathbb{S}}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} \sigma^{\vartheta-1} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma \quad (1.11.14)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta, \vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (1.11.15)$$

where Γ is a path lying on $\Sigma_{(\tilde{\alpha}, \omega)}$, see for instance [24] and $\mathcal{F} \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Proof. We apply the Laplace transform on both sides of equation (1.11.12):

$$\mathcal{L}({}^{ABC}D_\alpha^\vartheta[w(\alpha) - \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha))]) (s) = \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{Q}w(\alpha))(s) + \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha))(s). \quad (1.11.16)$$

Note that we can rewrite the derivative as the product of convolution of two functions.

Thus, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{L}({}^{ABC}\mathcal{D}_\alpha^\vartheta w(\alpha))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta) * w'(\alpha))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s) \mathcal{L}(w'(\alpha))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s) \mathcal{L}[s\mathcal{L}(w(\alpha))(s) - w(0)] \end{aligned} \quad (1.11.17)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{L}({}^{ABC}\mathcal{D}_\alpha^\vartheta \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha)))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta) * \mathcal{G}'(\alpha, w(\alpha))(\alpha))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s) \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G}'(\alpha, w(\alpha))(\alpha))(s) \\ &= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s) \mathcal{L}[s\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha)))(s) - \mathcal{G}(0, w(0))]. \end{aligned} \quad (1.11.18)$$

Equation (1.11.16) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[\frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} s\mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s) - \mathcal{Q} \right] \mathcal{L}(w(\alpha))(s) \\
&= \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s)[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} s\mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta)) \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha)))(s) \\
&+ \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha))(s). \tag{1.11.19}
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} s\mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s) - \mathcal{Q} &= \frac{s^\vartheta(B(\vartheta) - \mathcal{Q}(1-\vartheta)) - \vartheta\mathcal{Q}}{(1-\vartheta)(s^\vartheta + \tilde{\gamma})} \\
&= \frac{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}}{s^\vartheta + \tilde{\gamma}} \frac{B(\vartheta)}{\mathbb{S}(1-\vartheta)}, \tag{1.11.20}
\end{aligned}$$

where the operators \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{S} are given as

$$\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}, \quad \mathbb{S} = \zeta^*(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}. \tag{1.11.21}$$

Then (1.11.19) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{L}(w(\alpha))(s) \\
&= \left[\frac{s^\vartheta + \tilde{\gamma}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \frac{1-\vartheta}{B(\vartheta)} \mathbb{S} \right] \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta))(s)[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] \\
&+ \left[\frac{s^\vartheta + \tilde{\gamma}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \frac{1-\vartheta}{B(\vartheta)} \mathbb{S} \right] \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha))(s) \\
&+ \left[\frac{s^\vartheta + \tilde{\gamma}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \frac{1-\vartheta}{B(\vartheta)} \mathbb{S} \right] \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} s\mathcal{L}(E_\vartheta(-\tilde{\gamma}\alpha^\vartheta)) \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha))) \\
&= \frac{s^{\vartheta-1}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \mathbb{S}[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{S}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)} \frac{s^\vartheta + \tilde{\gamma}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha))(s) \\
&+ \left[\frac{s^\vartheta}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \mathbb{S} \right] \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha))). \tag{1.11.22}
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the inverse Laplace transform, it holds

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left(\frac{s^{\vartheta-1}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \right) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta), \tag{1.11.23}$$

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left(\frac{s^\vartheta}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \right) = \alpha^{-1} E_{\vartheta,0}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta-1}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} - \mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta), \tag{1.11.24}$$

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left(\frac{\tilde{\gamma}}{s^\vartheta + \mathbb{T}} \right) = \tilde{\gamma}\alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta), \tag{1.11.25}$$

By applying the inverse Laplace transform on both sides of (1.11.22), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}E_{\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta})[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{\mathbb{T}\mathbb{S}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)}\alpha^{\vartheta-1} + (\tilde{\gamma} - \mathbb{T})\frac{\mathbb{S}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)}\alpha^{\vartheta-1}E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta}) \right] * \mathcal{F}(\alpha) \\
&\quad + \left[\frac{\mathbb{T}\mathbb{S}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)}\alpha^{\vartheta-1} - \mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta-1}E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta}) \right] * \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha)) \\
&= \mathbb{S}E_{\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta})[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{T}\mathbb{S}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)}\alpha^{\vartheta-1} * \mathcal{F}(\alpha) \\
&\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)}\alpha^{\vartheta-1}E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta}) * \mathcal{F}(\alpha) + \frac{\mathbb{T}\mathbb{S}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)}\alpha^{\vartheta-1} * \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha)) \\
&\quad - \mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta-1}E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta}) * \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w(\alpha)) \\
&= \mathbb{S}E_{\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^{\vartheta})[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{T}\mathbb{S}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\mathcal{F}(s) + \zeta^* \mathcal{G}(s, w(s))] ds \\
&\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}(\alpha-s)^{\vartheta}) \left[\mathcal{F}(s) - \frac{B(\vartheta)\mathbb{T}}{\vartheta\mathbb{S}} \mathcal{G}(s, w(s)) \right] ds \\
&= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\mathcal{F}(s) + \zeta^* \mathcal{G}(s, w(s))] ds \\
&\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} \hat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha-s) [\mathcal{F}(s) + \mathcal{Q}\mathcal{G}(s, w(s))] ds. \tag{1.11.26}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 1.11.1. By utilizing the values of $\zeta^* = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$ and $\mathcal{Q} = -\frac{B(\vartheta)\mathbb{T}}{\vartheta\mathbb{S}}$, equation (1.11.13) is equivalent to the following equation

$$\begin{aligned}
w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \left[\mathcal{F}(s) + \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta} \mathcal{G}(s, w(s)) \right] ds \\
&\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} \hat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha-s) \left[\mathcal{F}(s) - \frac{B(\vartheta)\mathbb{T}}{\vartheta\mathbb{S}} \mathcal{G}(s, w(s)) \right] ds \\
&= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)[\tilde{w}_0 - \mathcal{G}(0, \tilde{w}_0)] + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds \\
&\quad + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{G}(s, w(s)) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha} \hat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds \\
&\quad - \mathbb{S}\mathbb{T} \int_0^{\alpha} \hat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha-s) \mathcal{G}(s, w(s)) ds. \tag{1.11.27}
\end{aligned}$$

From the above Remark 1.11.1, we realize that the equation (1.11.27) is also a mild solution of the system (1.11.12). From this point on wards, we consider the equation

(1.11.27) is the mild solution of the given system (1.11.12), since (1.11.13) and (1.11.27) are equivalent.

1.12 Author's Contribution

To the best of our knowledge, the qualitative behaviour of FDS with A-B derivative have emerged an important research topic and they are still in the developing stage with less satisfactory results. The main object of this thesis is to study the existence and controllability results for various types of Atangana-Baleanu FDS and FIDS with infinite delay in Banach spaces under suitable fixed point theorems. In the light of the above descriptions, we make an attempt to establish some significant results on the following topics:

- (1) Existence of a solution for a fractional integro-differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel.
- (2) On a new class of Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusions with non-instantaneous impulses.
- (3) Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional neutral integro-differential systems with infinite delay through sectorial operators.
- (4) A new existence results on fractional differential inclusions with state-dependent delay and Mittag-Leffler kernel in Banach space.
- (5) Non-instantaneous impulsive fractional-order delay differential systems with Mittag-Leffler kernel.
- (6) Existence and controllability of fractional integro-differential equation with infinite delay and impulsive effects.

The rest of the thesis presents the various results established by the author on the above topics.

Chapter 2

EXISTENCE OF A SOLUTION FOR A FRACTIONAL INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION WITH NON-INSTANTANEOUS IMPULSES AND MITTAG-LEFFLER KERNEL

In this chapter, we discuss the existence of a solution for a fractional integro-differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel in Banach spaces. For better readability, we divide this chapter into two sections namely

- (2.1) Existence of a solution for a fractional differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel in Banach spaces
- (2.5) Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential systems with non-instantaneous impulses in Banach spaces

2.1 Introduction

Fractional calculus, the concept of derivatives and integral of non-integer order is used rapidly to model the dynamic behaviour of natural process in the several fields of science and engineering [17, 19, 20]. Fractional differential equations have non-local relations in space and time, owing to this fact the field of fractional-calculus has started evolving much faster all around the globe. Moreover, fractional differential equations plays a brilliant tool for the explanation of memory and hereditary properties of various process. In [10, 74], authors have utilized the fractional differential operators for a function with respect to another function. These operators are used to solve problems of population growth and other models. In recent times, many researchers have discussed the existence, uniqueness

and controllability results for the solutions of various fractional initial value problems using fixed point theory [7, 8, 13, 14, 76, 88, 89, 111].

After nineteenth century, fractional calculus encounters enormous development mainly due to its applicability in diverse fields and by the growth of multiple definitions with its own peculiar properties for the fractional derivatives such as Caputo's definition, Riemann-Liouville definitions, Weyl definition and so on. In such a row the Liouville-Caputo's fractional derivative includes its kernel which is based on the power law with singularity at its origin. This definition is not much efficacy, as the power law is less effectively explaining the memory of kernel in modelling the physically problems. In [38], The definition for fractional derivative with no singular kernel was given. The Caputo-Fanrizio operator possessing regular kernel is its main contribution [39]. In [55], authors established the importance of Caputo-Fanrizio fractional operator; More research works on this fractional operator are given in [17–20]. In [18], the new kernel which is non-local and non-singular was proposed by Atangana and Baleanu on the basis of Mittag-Leffler function.

In mathematical modelling, the sudden change experienced by natural process at certain moments was stated by the class of instantaneous impulsive differential equations process with such features appears quite naturally in the areas of population, dynamics, engineering, physics and chemistry, see the monographs by Benchohra et al. [33], Lakshmikantham et al. [84], and the papers of Mallika Arjunan et al. [93], Li and Liu [86] for more references. Due to the application of the theory of instantaneous impulsive differential equations in various fields as such control, mechanics, electrical engineering, biological and medical fields, it becomes important area of research in recent times. For the past few decades, researchers have shown more interest towards investigating the theory of instantaneous impulsive evolution equation in Banach space. For further application and its theory, we refer [27, 33, 48, 76, 93, 111].

In the real world, there are many process experience the external influences abruptly. These duration is negligible when compared with the total duration of the process and these external influences are assumed to be instantaneous which are in the form of impulses. However, it is clear that models with instantaneous impulses are unable to explain some aspects of pharmacological evolution processes. When we examine the simplified scenario

of a person's hemodynamic equilibrium, the entry of medicines into the circulation and the body's subsequent absorption are slow and continuous processes, as Hernandez and O'Regan pointed out in [69]. As a result, this circumstance might be interpreted as an impulsive activity that begins quickly and continues for a finite period of time. Non-instantaneous impulses are a term we use to describe this phenomena that occurs while building mathematical models. Numerous models derived from actual models may be represented as partial differential systems with NII, according to the research.

In recent times, the authors have found some interesting results on non-linear impulsive differential equations with NII, see [41, 43, 69, 101, 105, 117, 119, 123]. Furthermore, fractional ordinary and partial differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses have also been studied in [1, 50, 82, 97, 114, 120]. In [50], author's have inquired the main results of mild solutions for fractional order functional differential equations with NII in Banach spaces. Recently, in [41], authors analyzed the existence of piecewise-continuous mild solutions for the initial value problems for a class of semilinear evolution equations under measures of non-compactness condition. In [97], Meeraj et al. studied the existence results for fractional non-instantaneous impulsive integro-differential equations with non-local conditions by using the compact semigroup theory and fixed point theory. In [82], Kumar et al. investigated the non-instantaneous impulsive fractional differential system through A-B derivative and provided the class of acceptable assumptions for the existence of its mild solutions. Mallika Arjunan et al. [90, 91] recently investigated the existence of various fractional order differential systems using the A-B derivative and an appropriate fixed point theorem.

As a result of the foregoing facts, we investigated the existence results for ABFDE with NII of the model

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (2.1.1)$$

$$w(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \quad (2.1.2)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 \in E, \quad (2.1.3)$$

where $J = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is the operational interval, $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-

Caputo derivative, $0 = \alpha_0 = s_0 < \alpha_1 \leq s_1 < \alpha_2 \leq s_2 < \dots < \alpha_m \leq s_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$; $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E \rightarrow E$ is a given function which satisfies assumptions to be specified later on. We consider the non-instantaneous impulsive functions $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times E \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and $I_\ell : E \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $w_0 \in E$.

The impulses in system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) begin rapidly at the points α_ℓ and their process continues on the interval $[\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$. To be exact, the function w takes an instantaneous impulse at α_ℓ and applies various conditions in the two sub-intervals $(\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ of the interval $(\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$. The function w is continuous at the point s_ℓ . The phrase $I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell))$ denotes that the impulses are frequently linked to the value of $w(\alpha_\ell) = w(\alpha_\ell^-)$.

We observe that if $\alpha_\ell = s_\ell$ and (2.1.2) takes the structure of $\Delta w(\alpha_\ell) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) = w(\alpha_\ell^+) - w(\alpha_\ell^-)$ with $w(\alpha_\ell^+) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} w(\alpha_\ell + \epsilon)$, $w(\alpha_\ell^-) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^-} w(\alpha_\ell + \epsilon)$ expressing the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_\ell$.

We also establish the existence and uniqueness of mild solutions for the nonlocal Cauchy problem

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (2.1.4)$$

$$w(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \quad (2.1.5)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 - g(w) \in E, \quad (2.1.6)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$, \mathcal{Q} , \mathcal{F} , I and κ are same as described in system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) and g is an appropriate given function; this frames a nonlocal Cauchy problem.

The following is a summary of the research work's main contribution:

1. The existence of a \mathcal{PC} mild solution of ABFDE with NII and impulsive condition for the systems (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) and (2.1.4)-(2.1.6) are investigated in this chapter.
2. The major findings are developed using the Banach contraction principle and the Krasnoselskii fixed point theorem. Lastly, two examples are presented to demonstrate the utility of our findings.
3. As far as we know, this work is the first attempt to address the ABFDE with NII together with impulsive condition for the systems (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) and (2.1.4)-(2.1.6).

Now we will move on to a description of the work. We give some fundamental concepts on A-B fractional derivatives, sectorial operator and mild solution of the system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) in Section 2.2. The proof of our main findings are given in Section 2.3. Examples are provided in Section 2.4 to illustrate the obtained results.

2.2 Preliminaries

This part covers the fundamental definitions and results of the sectorial operator, piecewise continuous functions, and A-B fractional derivative, which will aid us in proving our key conclusions.

Let $(E, \|\cdot\|_E)$ be a complex Banach space. $L(E)$ is the Banach space of all bounded linear operators from X into X with $\|\cdot\|_{L(E)}$ as the corresponding norm.

$\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)$ is the Banach space of all continuous functions from $[0, \tau]$ into E with the norm

$$\|w\|_{\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)} = \sup\{\|w(\alpha)\| : \alpha \in [0, \tau]\}.$$

The functions $w : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ that are integrable in the Bochner notion with regard to the Lebesgue measure, equipped with

$$\|w\|_{L^1} = \int_0^\tau \|w(x)\| dx$$

is denoted by $L^1([0, \tau], E)$.

For basic definitions of fractional and A-B fractional derivative, we suggest the reader to refer 1.11.1.

Definition 2.2.1. [104] Take $\rho(\mathcal{Q}) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C}(\lambda I - \mathcal{Q}) : D(\mathcal{Q}) \rightarrow E \text{ is invertible}\}$. Then, resolvent of the operator \mathcal{Q} is set to $R(\lambda, \mathcal{Q}) = (\lambda I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$, where $\lambda \in \rho(\mathcal{Q})$.

Definition 2.2.2. [104] Closed and linear operator \mathcal{Q} is said to be sectorial if $\widehat{\Lambda} > 0, \omega \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\tilde{\alpha} \in [\frac{\pi}{2}, \pi]$ are constants, so that conditions

$$(i) \sum_{(\tilde{\alpha}, \omega)} = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : \lambda \neq \tilde{\alpha}, |\arg(\lambda - \omega)| < \tilde{\alpha}\} \subset \rho(\mathcal{Q});$$

$$(ii) \|R(\lambda, \mathcal{Q})\| \leq \frac{\widehat{\Lambda}}{|\lambda - \omega|}, \quad \lambda \in \sum_{(\tilde{\alpha}, \omega)}.$$

are set.

When incorporating impulsive constraints, we must first construct the piece-wise continuous functions.

We discuss it in detail here.

$$\mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E) = \{w : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E : w \text{ is continuous for } \alpha \neq \alpha_\ell, \\ \text{left continuous at } \alpha = \alpha_\ell \text{ and } w(\alpha_\ell^+) \text{ exists for } \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m\}.$$

The fact that $\mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E)$ is a Banach space equipped with the \mathcal{PC} -norm

$$\|w\|_{\mathcal{PC}} = \max \left\{ \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \kappa]} \|w(\alpha^+)\|, \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \|w(\alpha^-)\| \right\}, \quad w \in \mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E),$$

where $w(\alpha^+)$ and $w(\alpha^-)$ are the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, accordingly.

We urge that the reader to read [9, 18, 35, 65, 82, 90, 106, 112] for additional detail on this topic and its uses.

In view of 1.11.2, we can now describe the mild solution for the system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3).

Definition 2.2.3. [82, 90] A function $w \in \mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E)$ is called a mild solution of the system(2.1.1)-(2.1.3) if $w(0) = w_0 \in E$ and $w(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha))$ for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, and each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, satisfies the following integral equation

$$w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)q_\ell + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (2.2.1)$$

where

$$q_\ell = \frac{1}{\mathbb{S}} \left[I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(s_\ell)) - \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))ds \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))ds \right]; \quad (2.2.2)$$

$\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - \mathcal{D})^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{D}(\zeta I - \mathcal{D})^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} \sigma^{\vartheta-1} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (2.2.3)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta, \vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (2.2.4)$$

where Γ denotes the Bromwich path [24].

2.3 Existence Results

In this section, we present and demonstrate the results of existence for the systems (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) and (2.1.4)-(2.1.6) under Banach [1.10.1] and Krasnoselskii fixed point theorem [1.10.2].

We must first establish the operator estimates described in (2.2.3) and (2.2.4) before we can present and prove the major conclusion of this section.

If $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$ and $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\beta_0, \omega_0)$, then for any $w \in E$ and $\alpha > 0$, we have $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{\Lambda}e^{\omega\alpha}$ and $\|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq Ce^{\omega\alpha}(1 + \alpha^{\vartheta-1})$, for every $\alpha > 0, \omega > \omega_0$. Hence, we get $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}$ and $\|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \alpha^{\vartheta-1}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}$. Since $\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} = \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\|$ and $\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} = \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} Ce^{\omega\alpha}(1 + \alpha^{1-\vartheta})$. For additional details, see [65, 82, 112].

The following hypotheses are specified to establish our initial existence result:

(A1) The function $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous with respect to α and we can find $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \in L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}^+)$, where $\nu \in (0, \vartheta)$ in ways that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, u) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) \|u - v\|$$

for $u, v \in E$ and every $\alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$.

(A2) For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the functions $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times E \rightarrow E$ are continuous and there exists $\mathcal{L}_\kappa \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}^+)$ such that

$$\|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, u) - \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_\kappa(\alpha) \|u - v\|$$

for $u, v \in E$ and $\alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$.

(A3) For $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $I_\ell : E \rightarrow E$ and there is a constant $\mathcal{L}_I > 0$ such that

$$\|I_\ell(u) - I_\ell(v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_I \|u - v\|$$

for all $u, v \in E$.

(A4) There exist constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$ for the bounded linear operators \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 2.3.1. *The model (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution on \mathcal{J} if assumptions (A1)-(A4) are fulfilled and*

$$\left[\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})}) + (1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}) \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \right. \\ \left. (\times) \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0,\tau])} \right] < 1.$$

Proof. Construct the operator $\Upsilon : \mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E) \rightarrow \mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E)$ as

$$\Upsilon w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha), & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \\ \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \end{cases}$$

where, Υ_1 , $\Upsilon_{2\ell}$ and $\Upsilon_{3\ell}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \\ \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha) &= I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)q_\ell + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds, \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{aligned}$$

where $q_\ell, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, defined by (2.2.2).

In view of this operator Υ , the equation (2.2.1) has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution if and only if the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon w(\alpha)$ has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution. This is possible if and only if each of $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha)$, $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha)$ and $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval $[0, \alpha_1]$, $(\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and $[s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ respectively.

In view of (A1) along with Holder's inequality, we have for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\ &\leq \left(\int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\frac{\vartheta-1}{1-\nu}} ds \right)^{1-\nu} \left(\int_0^\alpha \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(s)^{\frac{1}{\nu}} ds \right)^\nu \|u-v\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \\ &\leq \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0,\tau])} \|u-v\|_{\mathcal{PC}}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.3.1}$$

For all $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$ and $u, v \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|\Upsilon_1 u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_1 v(\alpha)\| \\
& \leq \frac{\|\mathbf{S}\|\|\mathbf{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\
& \quad + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\|\mathbf{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \alpha_1^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])} \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \\
& \leq c^* \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thinking supremum over interval $[0, \alpha_1]$, we obtain $\|\Upsilon_1 u - \Upsilon_1 v\| \leq c^* \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \rightarrow 0$ for fixed α_1 . We can find m^* such that $\Upsilon_1^{(m^*)}$ is contraction on \mathcal{PC} . The operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha)$ has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution across the interval $[0, \alpha_1]$, according to the Banach contraction theorem.

For all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and $u, v \in E$ and assuming (A2)-(A3), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\Upsilon_{2\ell} u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_{2\ell} v(\alpha)\| & \leq \|I_\ell u(\alpha_\ell) - I_\ell v(\alpha_\ell)\| + \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, u(\alpha)) - \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v(\alpha))\| \\
& \leq [\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})}] \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently $\Upsilon_{2\ell}$ is contraction, and the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha)$ has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution for the interval $(\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, according to the Banach fixed point theorem. This means for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $w(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha))$ has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution for all $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$. The uniqueness of the solution at point s_ℓ is also determined by the Lipschitz continuity of κ_ℓ .

For all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $\alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ and $u, v \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|\Upsilon_{3\ell} u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_{3\ell} v(\alpha)\| \\
& \leq \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell)\| \left[\|I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell)) - I_\ell(v(\alpha_\ell))\| + \|\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, u(s_\ell)) - \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v(s_\ell))\| \right] \\
& \quad + \frac{\|\mathbf{S}\|\|\mathbf{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \|S\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \Big] \\
& + \frac{\|S\| \|T\| (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\
& + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \|S\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\
\leq & \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \left[\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})} + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) s_\ell^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \right. \\
& \left. (\times) \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, s_\ell])} \right] \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}} \\
& + \left[\left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \alpha_{\ell+1}^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_{\ell+1}])} \right] \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}} \\
\leq & \left[\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} (\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})}) + (1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \right. \\
& \left. (\times) \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau])} \right] \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}} \\
\leq & c^* \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Considering supremum over interval $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, we get $\|\Upsilon_{3\ell} u - \Upsilon_{3\ell} v\| \leq c^* \|u - v\| \rightarrow 0$ for fixed sub-interval $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$. We can find m^* such that $\Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(m^*)}$ is contraction on $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$. The operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha)$ has a unique $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}$ -mild solution over the interval $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, according to the Banach contraction theorem.

Hence, the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon w(\alpha)$ has a unique $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}$ -mild solution on $[0, \tau]$ which is identical to the $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}$ -mild solution of the model (2.1.1)-(2.1.3). \square

The Krasnoselskii fixed point theorem (K.F.T) [1.10.2] is the basis for our second finding.

(A1)* For any $w \in E$, the function $\alpha \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w)$ is strongly measurable on $[0, \tau]$.

For a.e. $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, the function $w \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w)$ is continuous. There exists $\varphi_{\mathcal{F}} \in L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau], \mathbb{R}^+)$ with $\nu \in (0, \vartheta)$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, w)\| \leq \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(\|w\|), \quad \text{for all } w \in E \text{ and } \alpha \in [0, \tau],$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a continuous and non-decreasing function [CaNDF].

(A2)* For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the functions $I_{\ell} : E \rightarrow E$ are continuous and

$$\|I_{\ell}(w)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_I(\|w\|), \quad \text{for all } w \in E,$$

where $\mathcal{L}_I : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a CaNDF.

(A3)* For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the functions $\kappa_{\ell} : (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \times E \rightarrow E$ are continuous and there exists $\varphi_{\kappa} \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}^+)$ such that

$$\|\kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w)\| \leq \varphi_{\kappa}(\alpha) \mathcal{L}_{\kappa}(\|w\|), \quad w \in E, \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}],$$

where $\mathcal{L}_{\kappa} : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a CaNDF.

Theorem 2.3.2. *Let (A2)-(A4), (A1)*-(A3)* be satisfied. Assume that*

$$\left[\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_{\kappa}\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})}) \right] < 1 \quad (2.3.2)$$

and there exists a constant $R > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(\mathcal{L}_I(R) + \|\varphi_{\kappa}\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})} \mathcal{L}_{\kappa}(R) + \mu \|w_0\|) + (1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ & (\times) \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(R) \left(\frac{1 - \nu}{\vartheta - \nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau])} \leq R. \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.3)$$

Then the system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3) has a \mathcal{PC} -mild solution on \mathcal{J} .

Proof. To use the K.F.T, we must first define two operators. $\bar{\Upsilon}, \tilde{\Upsilon} : \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) \rightarrow \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ as

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}}(\alpha)w_0, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \\ I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) + \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \\ \mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha - s_{\ell})[I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) + \kappa_{\ell}(s_{\ell}, w(s_{\ell}))], & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases}$$

and

$$(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \text{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \\ 0, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \text{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell) \left[\frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\vartheta \text{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \right], & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

For any $w \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$, $\bar{\Upsilon}w, \tilde{\Upsilon}w \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$, hence they are well defined. Thus, $\Upsilon w = \bar{\Upsilon}w + \tilde{\Upsilon}w$.

Further, we define

$$\widetilde{M} = \{x \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E) : \|x\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}} \leq R\},$$

where R fulfills the assumption (2.3.3).

Next, we show that operators $\bar{\Upsilon}, \tilde{\Upsilon}$ fulfills the K.F.T. That is, we need to prove that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is a contraction, $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ is compact and continuous and $\bar{\Upsilon}w_1 + \tilde{\Upsilon}w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$ for all $w_1, w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$.

We have divided the proof into stages to make it easier to understand.

Step 1: $\bar{\Upsilon}w_1 + \tilde{\Upsilon}w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$ for all $w_1, w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$.

For any $w_1, w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$, we have from (2.3.1) along with (A1)*, for $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1)(\alpha) + (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)(\alpha)\| \\ & \leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, w_2(s))\| ds \\ & \leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(R) \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \alpha_1^{\vartheta-\nu} \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])}, \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1)(\alpha) + (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)(\alpha)\| & \leq \|I_\ell(w_1(\alpha_\ell))\| + \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, w_1(\alpha))\| \\ & \leq \mathcal{L}_I(R) + \mathcal{L}_\kappa(R) \|\varphi_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})}, \end{aligned}$$

and for $\alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1)(\alpha) + (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)(\alpha)\| \\
&= \left\| \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell) \left[I_\ell(w_1(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w_1(s_\ell)) - \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_2(s)) ds \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - \frac{\vartheta S^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell - s) \mathcal{F}(s, w_2(s)) ds \right] + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_2(s)) ds \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\vartheta S^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) \mathcal{F}(s, w_2(s)) ds \right\| \\
&\leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} [\mathcal{L}_I(R) + \mathcal{L}_\kappa(R) \|\varphi_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{J})}] \\
&\quad + \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{L}_\mathcal{F}(R) \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} s_\ell^{\vartheta-\nu} \|\varphi_\mathcal{F}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, s_\ell])} \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{L}_\mathcal{F}(r) \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \alpha_{\ell+1}^{\vartheta-\nu} \|\varphi_\mathcal{F}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_{\ell+1}])}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then for every $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1) + (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{E}} \\
&\leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} (\mathcal{L}_I(R) + \|\varphi_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{J})} \mathcal{L}_\kappa(R) + \mu \|w_0\|) \\
&\quad + (1 + \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}) \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{L}_\mathcal{F}(R) \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \|\varphi_\mathcal{F}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau])}.
\end{aligned}$$

In view of (2.3.3), we conclude that $\bar{\Upsilon}w_1 + \tilde{\Upsilon}w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$, for all $w_1, w_2 \in \widetilde{M}$.

Step 2: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is contraction.

Let $w_1, w_2 \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{J}, E)$. By assumptions (A2), (A3), we have for $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$,

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1)(\alpha) - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)(\alpha) = 0,$$

for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1)(\alpha) - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)(\alpha)\| \leq (\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{J})}) \|w_1 - w_2\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{E}},$$

and for $\alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}w_1)(\alpha) - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w_2)(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} (\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{J})}) \|w_1 - w_2\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{E}}.$$

In general, for every $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we have

$$\|\bar{\Upsilon}w_1 - \tilde{\Upsilon}w_2\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{E}} \leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} (\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{E}(\mathcal{J})}) \|w_1 - w_2\|_{\mathcal{P}\mathcal{E}}.$$

In view of (2.3.2), $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is contraction on $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Step 3: $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ is continuous and compact.

For our convenience, first we demonstrate that $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ is continuous. Let $w_n \rightarrow w$ in $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Without loss of generality, we may assume that $\|w_n\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \leq N$ for some $N > 0$ and $n \geq 1$. By using the condition (A1)*, we have

$$\mathcal{F}(\alpha, w_n(\alpha)) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)) \quad a.e. \quad \alpha \in \mathcal{J}, \quad (2.3.4)$$

and

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, w_n(\alpha))\| \leq \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(N), \quad \text{for } \alpha \in \mathcal{J}, n \geq 1. \quad (2.3.5)$$

For $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w_n)(\alpha) - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha)\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, w_n(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))\| ds, \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

$$\|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w_n)(\alpha) - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha)\| = 0,$$

and for $\alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w_n)(\alpha) - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha)\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, w_n(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))\| ds \\ & \quad + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, w_n(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, w(s))\| ds. \end{aligned}$$

From equations (2.3.4) and (2.3.5) along with Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem [1.10.8], we have

$$\|\tilde{\Upsilon}w_n - \tilde{\Upsilon}w\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Thus the operator $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ is continuous on $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Following that, we will see how $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ maps a bounded set into a relatively compact (R.C) set in $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Let Z be any bounded subset of $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ such that for $w \in Z$, $\|w\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \leq N$ for some $N > 0$, enough to demonstrate that the set of functions $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z) = \{\tilde{\Upsilon}w : w \in Z\}$ fulfills the assumptions of [48, Lemma 2.1].

By thinking of Step 1, the set $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)$ is uniformly bounded.

Next, we show that $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)$ is equi-continuous in $(\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1})$, $\alpha = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$.

For any $w \in Z$, if $0 \leq \alpha' < \alpha'' \leq \alpha_1$, we have

$$\|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha'') - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha')\| \leq \sum_{i=1}^4 \|C_i\|,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= \frac{\mathcal{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha'} [(\alpha'' - s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\alpha' - s)^{\vartheta-1}] \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds; \\ C_2 &= \frac{\mathcal{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha'}^{\alpha''} (\alpha'' - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds; \\ C_3 &= \frac{\vartheta \mathcal{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha'} [\hat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha'' - s) - \hat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha' - s)] \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds; \\ C_4 &= \frac{\vartheta \mathcal{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha'}^{\alpha''} \hat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha'' - s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Presently,

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_1\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} [(\alpha''^{\vartheta-\nu} - \alpha'^{\vartheta-\nu}) - (\alpha'' - \alpha')^{\vartheta-\nu}] \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu}\right)^{1-\nu} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(N) \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])}; \\ \|C_2\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} (\alpha'' - \alpha')^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu}\right)^{1-\nu} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(N) \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])}; \\ \|C_3\| &\leq \frac{\vartheta\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\hat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} [(\alpha''^{\vartheta-\nu} - \alpha'^{\vartheta-\nu}) - (\alpha'' - \alpha')^{\vartheta-\nu}] \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu}\right)^{1-\nu} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(N) \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])}; \\ \|C_4\| &\leq \frac{\vartheta\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\hat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} (\alpha'' - \alpha')^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu}\right)^{1-\nu} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(N) \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])}. \end{aligned}$$

From the above discussion, we conclude that $\|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha'') - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha')\| \rightarrow 0$ as $\alpha'' \rightarrow \alpha'$ independently of $w \in Z$.

If $\alpha < \alpha' < \alpha'' \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, the below are three cases:

Case (i): If $\alpha_\ell < \alpha' < \alpha'' \leq s_\ell$, we have

$$\|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha'') - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha')\| = 0.$$

Case (ii): If $s_\ell \leq \alpha' < \alpha'' \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha'') - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha')\| \\ & \leq \|C_1\| + \|C_2\| + \|C_3\| + \|C_4\| + \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha' - s_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha'' - s_\ell)\Pi\|, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.6)$$

where

$$\Pi = \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell - s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds.$$

From the continuity of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta$ along with the above discussion, we inferred that the right side of (2.3.6) tends to zero as $\alpha'' \rightarrow \alpha'$.

Case (iii): If $\alpha_\ell < \alpha' < s_\ell < \alpha'' \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, we have $\|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha'') - (\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha')\| \rightarrow 0$ independently of $w \in Z$, as $\alpha'' \rightarrow \alpha'$ (we have $\alpha'' \rightarrow s_\ell$). Hence, $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)$ is equi-continuous in $(\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1})$, $\ell = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Finally, let $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)(\alpha)$ denote the set $\{(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha) : w \in Z\}$, $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, we shall demonstrate that $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)(\alpha)$ is R.C in E . Clearly, $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)(0) = \{0\}$ is compact.

Case I: Consider $0 < \alpha \leq \alpha_1$.

For each $h \in (0, \alpha)$, we describe a set

$$\tilde{\Upsilon}^h(Z)(\alpha) = \{(V_h w)(\alpha) : w \in Z\}$$

with

$$V_h w(\alpha) = \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha-h} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha-h} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds.$$

Since $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)$ is a compact operator, the set $\tilde{\Upsilon}^h(Z)(\alpha)$ is relatively compact in E .

Furthermore, for every $w \in Z$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\tilde{\Upsilon}w)(\alpha) - (V_h w)(\alpha)\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{\alpha-h}^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, w(s))\| ds \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(N) \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} h^{\vartheta-\nu} \|\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau])}. \end{aligned}$$

Case II: If $\alpha < \alpha \leq s_\ell$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ we have $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)(\alpha) = \{0\}$ is compact.

Case III: If $s_\ell < \alpha < \alpha_{\ell+1}$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)(\alpha) = & \left\{ \frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \right. \\ & + \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ & - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell) \left[\frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \right] : w \in Z \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

In view of Case I and compactness of the operator, we realize that $\tilde{\Upsilon}(Z)(\alpha)$ is relatively compact. From [48, Lemma 2.1] that $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ is continuous and compact.

As a consequence of Steps 1-3, the operators $\bar{\Upsilon}$ and $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ fulfill all conditions of the K.F.T [35, Lemma 2.3].

As a result, Υ has a fixed point in $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ which is a \mathcal{PC} -mild solution of system (2.1.1)-(2.1.3). The proof has now been finished. \square

Lastly, we present and prove the existence and uniqueness results for the system (2.1.4)-(2.1.6) under Banach fixed point theorem [1.10.1].

In addition to the assumptions (A1)-(A4), we need to list another one assumption in order to discuss the nonlocal system.

(A5) There exists a constant $\mathcal{L}_g > 0$ such that $\|g(u) - g(v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_g \|u - v\|$ for each $u, v \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Theorem 2.3.3. *If assumptions (A1)-(A5) are satisfied and*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})} + \mu \mathcal{L}_g) \right. \\ & \left. + (1 + \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \|\mathcal{L}_\mathcal{F}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau])} \right] < 1, \end{aligned}$$

then the nonlocal system (2.1.4)-(2.1.6) has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution on \mathcal{J} .

Proof. Define an operator $\widehat{\Upsilon} : \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) \rightarrow \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ as

$$\widehat{\Upsilon}w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \widehat{\Upsilon}_1 w(\alpha), & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \\ \widehat{\Upsilon}_{2\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \widehat{\Upsilon}_{3\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \end{cases}$$

where, $\widehat{\Upsilon}_1$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\Upsilon}_1 w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)[w_0 - g(w)] + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s)) ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.7)$$

and the operators $\widehat{\Upsilon}_{2\ell}$ and $\widehat{\Upsilon}_{3\ell}$ are same as $\Upsilon_{2\ell}$ and $\Upsilon_{3\ell}$ are defined in Theorem 2.3.1.

By thinking of Theorem 2.3.1 and for all $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$ and $u, v \in \mathcal{PC}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\|\widehat{\Upsilon}_1 u(\alpha) - \widehat{\Upsilon}_1 v(\alpha)\| \\ &\leq \|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \|g(u) - g(v)\| \\ &\quad + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{T}\| (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta \|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\ &\leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\mathcal{L}_g \|u - v\| + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s))\| ds \\ &\leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\mathcal{L}_g + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \alpha_1^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{\vartheta-\nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \alpha_1])} \right] \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \\ &\leq C^* \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thinking supremum over interval $[0, \alpha_1]$, we have $\|\widehat{\Upsilon}_1 u - \widehat{\Upsilon}_1 v\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \leq C^* \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{PC}} \rightarrow 0$ for fixed α_1 . We can find M^* such that $\widehat{\Upsilon}_1^{(M^*)}$ is contraction on $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$. The operator equation $w(\alpha) = \widehat{\Upsilon}_1 w(\alpha)$ has a unique \mathcal{PC} -mild solution over the interval $[0, \alpha_1]$, according to the Banach contraction theorem.

In view of Theorem 2.3.1, we realize that the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \widehat{\Upsilon}w(\alpha)$ has unique solution on $[0, \tau]$ which is identical to \mathcal{PC} -mild solution of the nonlocal system (2.1.4)-(2.1.6).

□

2.4 Example

Consider the following fractional differential equation with non-instantaneous impulsive condition of the form

$$\begin{cases} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\frac{3}{4}} z(\alpha, x) = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} z(\alpha, x) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, z(\alpha, x)), & \alpha \in [0, \frac{1}{2}] \cup (\frac{2}{3}, 1], x \in [0, \pi] \\ z(\alpha, x) = I \left(z \left(\alpha_{\frac{1}{2}}, x \right) \right) + \kappa(\alpha, z(\alpha, x)), & \alpha \in (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{3}], x \in [0, \pi] \\ z(\alpha, x) = z_0(x), & x \in [0, \pi] \\ z(\alpha, 0) = z(\alpha, \pi) = 0, & \alpha \in [0, 1] \end{cases} \quad (2.4.1)$$

Here $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\frac{3}{4}}$ is the A-B-C derivative is considered for α with the lower limit zero.

Let $E = L^2([0, \pi], \mathbb{R})$ and $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ be an operator by $\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \Theta''$, $\Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q})$ with domain $D(\mathcal{Q}) = \{\Theta \in E; \Theta \text{ and } \Theta' \text{ are absolutely continuous, } \Theta'' \in E, \Theta(0) = \Theta(\pi) = 0\}$. Then

$$\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q}),$$

where $\Theta_n(s) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin(ns)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the orthonormal set of eigenvectors of \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{Q} generates a C_0 semigroup $\{\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ in E which is given by

$$\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\alpha} \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in E, \alpha > 0$$

which is uniformly bounded and also a compact semigroup and hence the operator $R(\lambda, \mathcal{Q}) = (\lambda I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ is compact for each $\lambda \in \rho(\mathcal{Q})$, i.e., $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\beta_0, \Theta_0)$. We also get $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_\vartheta$ for each $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$ by using the idea of subordination of the solution operator. Refer to [82, 104] for further information.

Assumption I:

Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\alpha, z(\alpha, x)) &= \frac{\cos \alpha}{(\alpha + 6)^2} (z(\alpha, x) + \arctan z(\alpha, x)) \\ I(z(\alpha, x)) &= \frac{|z(\alpha, x)|}{4 + |z(\alpha, x)|}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\kappa(\alpha, z(\alpha, x)) = \frac{1}{3} \sin z(\alpha, x) + e^\alpha$$

Define $w(\alpha)(x) = z(\alpha, x)$, $(\alpha, x) \in [0, 1] \times [0, \pi]$. Then \mathcal{F} , I , and κ can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)) &= \frac{\cos \alpha}{(\alpha + 6)^2} (w(\alpha) + \arctan w(\alpha)) \\ I(w(\alpha)) &= \frac{|x(\alpha)|}{4 + |w(\alpha)|}, \\ \kappa(\alpha, w(\alpha)) &= \frac{1}{3} \sin w(\alpha) + e^\alpha.\end{aligned}$$

We can easily verify that the assumptions (A1)-(A4) hold by taking $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) = \frac{2 \cos \alpha}{(\alpha + 6)^2}$, $\mathcal{L}_I = \frac{1}{4}$ and $\mathcal{L}_\kappa(\alpha) = \frac{1}{3}$. Moreover, since $\vartheta = \frac{3}{4}$, let $\nu = \frac{1}{2}$; $\mu = \bar{\mu} = 1$ and $\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} = \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} = 1$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}& \left[\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{F})}) + (1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^{\vartheta-\nu} \left(\frac{1 - \nu}{\vartheta - \nu} \right)^{1-\nu} \right. \\ & \quad \left. (\times) \|\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}\|_{L^{\frac{1}{\nu}}([0, \tau])} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{3} + 2 \left(\frac{(1 - \frac{3}{4})}{(0.8620)(1.2254)} + \frac{\frac{3}{4}}{0.8620} \right) \times 1.4142 \times \frac{1}{18} = 0.7538 < 1,\end{aligned}$$

where $B(\vartheta) = (1 - \vartheta) + \frac{\vartheta}{\Gamma(\vartheta)}$ and $B\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right) + \frac{\frac{3}{4}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)} = 0.8620$, since $\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) = 1.225417$.

Therefore by Theorem 2.3.1, the system (2.4.1) has a unique $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}$ -mild solution over $[0, 1]$. Hence the system has a unique $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}$ -mild solution over the interval $[0, 1]$.

Assumption II:

Let

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}(\alpha, z(\alpha, x)) &= e^{-|z(\alpha, x)|} + 6\alpha^2 + \sin \alpha + \frac{z(\alpha, x)}{1 + z^2(\alpha, x)} \\ I(z(\alpha, x)) &= \frac{|z(\alpha, x)|}{4 + |z(\alpha, x)|} + 5\alpha, \quad \kappa(\alpha, z(\alpha, x)) = \frac{1}{3} \arctan z(\alpha, x) + 3\end{aligned}$$

Likewise, \mathcal{F} , I , and κ are being rephrased as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha)) &= e^{-|w(\alpha)|} + 6\alpha^2 + \sin \alpha + \frac{w(\alpha)}{1 + w^2(\alpha)} \\ I(w(\alpha)) &= \frac{|w(\alpha)|}{4 + |w(\alpha)|} + 5\alpha, \quad \kappa(\alpha, w(\alpha)) = \frac{1}{3} \arctan w(\alpha) + 3.\end{aligned}$$

Put $\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) \equiv 1$, $\varphi_{\kappa}(\alpha) \equiv 1$, $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}(\|w\|) \equiv 9\sqrt{\pi}$, $\mathcal{L}_{\kappa}(\|w\|) \equiv \left(\frac{\pi}{6} + 3\right) \sqrt{\pi}$, $\mathcal{L}_I(\|w\|) \equiv \frac{1}{4}\sqrt{\pi}$, $\mathcal{L}_I = \frac{1}{4}$, and $\mathcal{L}_{\kappa}(\alpha) \equiv \frac{1}{3}$. From these assumed values, easily we can verify that the

assumptions (A1)*, (A2), (A3), (A2)*, and (A3)*.

Moreover

$$\bar{\Lambda}(\mathcal{L}_I + \|\mathcal{L}_\kappa\|_{\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J})}) = 1 \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{3} \right) = \frac{7}{12} < 1.$$

In this case, we can clearly select a constant $R > 0$ that meets the (2.3.3) conditions.

As a result of Theorem 2.3.2, it implies that system (2.4.1) has a \mathcal{PC} -mild solution.

2.5 Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential systems with non-instantaneous impulses in Banach spaces

In this chapter, further, we examine the existence and uniqueness of mild solutions of Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential equations of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w(\alpha), \int_0^\alpha k(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \right), \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (2.5.1)$$

$$w(\alpha) = \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha_\ell^-)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \quad (2.5.2)$$

$$w(0) = w_0 \in E, \quad (2.5.3)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative of order ϑ , where $0 < \vartheta < 1$. $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of ϑ -resolvent operator $\{\hat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}, \{\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is a constant, $0 = \alpha_0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$, $s_0 = 0; w(\alpha_\ell^+) = \kappa_\ell(\alpha_\ell, w(\alpha_\ell^-))$, where the symbols $w(\alpha_\ell^+) := \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} w(\alpha_\ell + \epsilon)$ and $w(\alpha_\ell^-) := \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^-} w(\alpha_\ell + \epsilon)$ represent the right and the left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_\ell$ respectively and $s_\ell \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1})$ for each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m; \mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E \times E \rightarrow E; k : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$, where $\Delta = \{(w, s) : 0 \leq s \leq w \leq \tau\}$ are given function which satisfies assumptions to be specified later on. $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times E \rightarrow E$ are non-instantaneous impulsive functions for each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $w_0 \in E$. For our convenience, we denote $E_1 w(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha k(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds$.

In the next section, we will recall some basic definitions, notations and preliminary lemmas. In Section 2.7, we will prove existence and uniqueness of mild solutions for the problem (2.5.1)-(2.5.3) with initial and nonlocal condition and also we will give an example to illustrate the feasibility of our abstract result.

2.6 Preliminaries

Basic definitions and theorems of fractional calculus and functional analysis are discussed in this section, which will help us to prove our main results.

Let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ be the Banach space of continuous functions from \mathcal{J} into E with norm

$$\|w\|_\infty = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha)\|_E.$$

Let $B(E)$ stand for the Banach space of bounded linear operators from E into E .

A measurable function $w : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E$ is Bochner integrable if and only if $\|w\|_E$ is Lebesgue integrable.

Let $L^1(\mathcal{J}, E)$ stand for the Banach space of measurable functions $W : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E$ which are Bochner integrable normed by

$$\|w\|_{L^1} = \int_0^\tau \|w(\alpha)\| d\alpha.$$

Next, we need to define the piece-wise continuous functions when implementing impulsive conditions.

In particular, we describe

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) = \{w : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E : w \text{ is continuous for } \alpha \neq \alpha_\ell, \\ \text{left continuous at } \alpha = \alpha_\ell \text{ and } w(\alpha_\ell^+) \text{ exists for } \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m\}. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see that $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ is a Banach space endowed with the \mathcal{PC} -norm

$$\|w\|_{\mathcal{PC}} = \max \left\{ \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha^+)\|, \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha^-)\| \right\}, \quad w \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E),$$

where $w(\alpha^+)$ and $w(\alpha^-)$ constitute respectively the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$.

In view of 1.11.2, we are now in a position to define the system's mild solution (2.5.1)-(2.5.3).

Definition 2.6.1. [9, 18] A function $w \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ is a mild solution of (2.5.1)-(2.5.3) if $w(0) = w_0 \in E$ and $w(\alpha) = \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha_\ell^-))$ for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, and each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, satisfies the following integral equation

$$w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1w(s))ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1w(s))ds, & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(\alpha_\ell^-)) + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1w(s))ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1w(s))ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (2.6.1)$$

\mathbb{S} , \mathbb{T} , \mathcal{B}_ϑ and $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta$ are same as defined in (2.2.3) and (2.2.4) respectively.

2.7 Existence and Uniqueness Results

In this section, we present and demonstrate the results of existence for the system (2.5.1)-(2.5.3) under the Banach fixed point theorem [1.10.1].

Before presenting and proving the main result of this section, first we need to find the operator estimates defined in (2.2.3) and (2.2.4).

If $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$ and $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\beta_0, \omega_0)$, then for any $w \in E$ and $\alpha > 0$, we have $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{\Lambda}e^{\omega\alpha}$ and $\|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq Ce^{\omega\alpha}(1 + \alpha^{\vartheta-1})$, for every $\alpha > 0, \omega > \omega_0$. Hence, we get $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}$ and $\|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \alpha^{\vartheta-1}\widehat{M}_\widehat{\mathcal{B}}$. Since $\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} = \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\|$ and $\widehat{M}_\widehat{\mathcal{B}} = \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} Ce^{\omega\alpha}(1 + \alpha^{1-\vartheta})$. For additional details, see [65, 82, 112].

Next, we list the subsequent hypotheses for the use of the Banach fixed point theorem [1.10.1]:

(A1) The function $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous with respect to α and there exist positive constants $\mathcal{L}_\mathcal{F}$ and $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_\mathcal{F}$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, u_1, v_1) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, u_2, v_2)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_\mathcal{F} \|u_1 - u_2\| + \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_\mathcal{F} \|v_1 - v_2\|$$

for $u_1, v_1, u_2, v_2 \in B_{r_0} = \{w \in E; \|w\| \leq r_0\}$ for some r_0 .

(A2) The function $k : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous and there exists a constant \mathcal{L}_k such that

$$\left\| \int_0^\alpha [k(\alpha, s, u) - k(\alpha, s, v)] ds \right\| \leq \mathcal{L}_k \|u - v\|$$

for $u, v \in B_{r_0}$.

(A3) For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ the functions $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times E \rightarrow E$ are continuous and there exists a positive constant $0 < \mathcal{L}_{\kappa_\ell} < 1$ such that

$$\|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, u) - \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_{\kappa_\ell} \|u - v\|$$

for $u, v \in B_{r_0}$ and $\alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$.

(A4) \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} are bounded linear operators and we can find constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$.

Theorem 2.7.1. *If assumptions (A1)-(A4) are satisfied, then the semilinear fractional integro-differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses (2.5.1)-(2.5.3) has a unique mild solution on \mathcal{J} .*

Proof. Define an operator Υ on E by

$$\Upsilon w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1] \\ \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \end{cases}$$

where, $\Upsilon_1, \Upsilon_{2\ell}$ and $\Upsilon_{3\ell}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1 w(s)) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1 w(s)) ds, \quad \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1] \end{aligned}$$

$$\Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha) = \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha_\ell^-)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(\alpha_\ell^-)) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1 w(s)) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1 w(s)) ds, \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \end{aligned}$$

for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

In view of this operator Υ , the equation (2.6.1) has a unique solution if and only if the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon w(\alpha)$ has unique solution. This is possible if and only if each

of $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha)$, $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha)$ and $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval $(0, \alpha_1]$, $(\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ respectively.

For all $\alpha \in (0, \alpha_1]$ and $u, v \in B_{r_0}$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \Upsilon_1^{(n)} u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_1^{(n)} v(\alpha) \right\| \\ & \leq \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{T}\| (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \int_0^{\tau_1} \dots \int_0^{\tau_{n-1}} (\alpha - \tau_1)^{\vartheta-1} (\tau_1 - \tau_2)^{\vartheta-1} \dots (\tau_{n-1} - s)^{\vartheta-1} \\ & \quad (\times) \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s), E_1 u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s), E_1 v(s))\| ds d\tau_{n-1} \dots d\tau_1 \\ & \quad + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \int_0^{\tau_1} \dots \int_0^{\tau_{n-1}} (\alpha - \tau_1)^{\vartheta-1} (\tau_1 - \tau_2)^{\vartheta-1} \dots (\tau_{n-1} - s)^{\vartheta-1} \\ & \quad (\times) \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s), E_1 u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s), E_1 v(s))\| ds d\tau_{n-1} \dots d\tau_1 \end{aligned}$$

By applying assumption (A1)-(A2) and (A4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \Upsilon_1^{(n)} u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_1^{(n)} v(\alpha) \right\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^{\alpha_1} \int_0^{\alpha_1} \dots \int_0^{\alpha_1} \alpha_1^{n(\vartheta-1)} [\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \|u - v\| \\ & \quad + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}} \|u - v\|] ds d\tau_{n-1} \dots d\tau_1 \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\alpha_1^{n(\vartheta-1)} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{(n-1)!} \int_0^{\alpha_1} (\alpha_1 - s)^{n-1} ds \|u - v\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\alpha_1^{n\vartheta} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{n!} \|u - v\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\tau^{n\vartheta} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{n!} \|u - v\| \\ & \leq c^* \|u - v\|. \end{aligned}$$

Considering supremum over interval $(0, \alpha_1]$, we get $\|\Upsilon_1^{(n)} u - \Upsilon_1^{(n)} v\| \leq c^* \|u - v\| \rightarrow 0$ for fixed α_1 . Therefore there exist m^* such that $\Upsilon_1^{(m^*)}$ is contraction on B_{r_0} . Thus by general Banach contraction theorem the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval $(0, \alpha_1]$.

For all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and $u, v \in E$ and assuming (A3), we have

$$\|\Upsilon_{2\ell} u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_{2\ell} v(\alpha)\| = \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, u(\alpha_\ell^-)) - \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v(\alpha_\ell^-))\| \leq \mathcal{L}_{\kappa_\ell} \|u - v\|.$$

Then $\Upsilon_{2\ell}$ is contraction and by Banach fixed point theorem the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{2\ell}w(\alpha)$ has a unique solution for the interval $(\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$. This means for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $w(\alpha) = \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha_\ell^-))$ has a unique solution for all $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$. Lipschitz continuity of κ_ℓ leads to uniqueness of the solution at point s_ℓ also.

For all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, $\alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ and $u, v \in B_{r_0}$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| \Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(n)}u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(n)}v(\alpha) \right\| \\
& \leq \|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell)\| \|\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, u(\alpha_\ell^-)) - \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v(\alpha_\ell^-))\| \\
& \quad + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{T}\| (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \int_{s_\ell}^{\tau_1} \cdots \int_{s_\ell}^{\tau_{n-1}} (\alpha - \tau_1)^{\vartheta-1} (\tau_1 - \tau_2)^{\vartheta-1} \cdots (\tau_{n-1} - s)^{\vartheta-1} \\
& \quad (\times) \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s), E_1u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s), E_1v(s))\| ds d\tau_{n-1} \cdots d\tau_1 \\
& \quad + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \int_{s_\ell}^{\tau_1} \cdots \int_{s_\ell}^{\tau_{n-1}} (\alpha - \tau_1)^{\vartheta-1} (\tau_1 - \tau_2)^{\vartheta-1} \cdots (\tau_{n-1} - s)^{\vartheta-1} \\
& \quad (\times) \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s), E_1u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s), E_1v(s))\| ds d\tau_{n-1} \cdots d\tau_1
\end{aligned}$$

Appalling assumption (A1), (A2) and (A4), we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| \Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(n)}u(\alpha) - \Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(n)}v(\alpha) \right\| \\
& \leq [\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_{\kappa_\ell} \|u - v\| \\
& \quad + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{s_\ell}^{\alpha_{\ell+1}} \int_{s_\ell}^{\alpha_{\ell+1}} \cdots \int_{s_\ell}^{\alpha_{\ell+1}} (\alpha_{\ell+1} - s)^{n(\vartheta-1)} \\
& \quad (\times) [\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \|u - v\| + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}} \|u - v\|] ds d\tau_{n-1} \cdots d\tau_1 \\
& \leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_{\kappa_\ell} + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{(\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^{n(\vartheta-1)} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{(n-1)!} \right. \\
& \quad \left. (\times) \int_{s_\ell}^{\alpha_{\ell+1}} (\alpha_{\ell+1} - s)^{n-1} ds \right] \|u - v\| \\
& \leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_{\kappa_\ell} + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{(\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^{n\vartheta} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{n!} \right] \|u - v\| \\
& \leq c^* \|u - v\|.
\end{aligned}$$

Considering supremum over interval $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, we get $\|\Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(n)}u - \Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(n)}v\| \leq c^* \|u - v\| \rightarrow 0$ for fixed sub-interval $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Therefore there exist m^* such that $\Upsilon_{3\ell}^{(m^*)}$ is contraction on B_{r_0} . Thus by general Banach contraction theorem the

operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon_{3\ell}w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ for all $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

Hence, the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \Upsilon w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval \mathcal{J} which is nothing but mild solution of the equation (2.5.1)-(2.5.3). □

2.7.1 System with Nonlocal Conditions

In this subsection, we present and prove the existence and uniqueness results for the problem (2.5.1)-(2.5.2) with nonlocal conditions of the form $w(0) = w_0 - g(w)$, where $g : \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) \rightarrow E$ is a given system.

In addition to the assumptions (A1)-(A4), we need to list another one assumptions in order to discuss the nonlocal system.

(A5) There exists a constant $\mathcal{L}_g > 0$ such that $\|g(u) - g(v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_g\|u - v\|$ for each $u, v \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Theorem 2.7.2. *If assumptions (A1)-(A5) are satisfied, then the semilinear fractional integro-differential equation of the system (2.5.1)-(2.5.2) with nonlocal condition $w(0) = w_0 - g(w)$ has a unique mild solution on \mathcal{J} .*

Proof. Define an operator $\bar{\Upsilon}$ on E by

$$\bar{\Upsilon}w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \bar{\Upsilon}_1w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1] \\ \bar{\Upsilon}_{2\ell}w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \bar{\Upsilon}_{3\ell}w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \end{cases}$$

where, $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Upsilon}_1w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)[w_0 - g(w)] + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1w(s))ds \\ &+ \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \hat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s)\mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1w(s))ds, \quad \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1] \end{aligned} \quad (2.7.1)$$

and the operators $\bar{\Upsilon}_{2\ell}$ and $\bar{\Upsilon}_{3\ell}$ are same as $\Upsilon_{2\ell}$ and $\Upsilon_{3\ell}$ are defined in Theorem 2.7.1.

By thinking of Theorem 2.7.1 along with the equation (2.7.1) and for all $\alpha \in (0, \alpha_1]$ and $u, v \in B_{r_0}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| \bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(n)} u(\alpha) - \bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(n)} v(\alpha) \right\| \\
& \leq \|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \left\| \|g(u) - g(v)\| \right\| \\
& \quad + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{T}\| (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \int_0^{\tau_1} \cdots \int_0^{\tau_{n-1}} (\alpha - \tau_1)^{\vartheta-1} (\tau_1 - \tau_2)^{\vartheta-1} \cdots (\tau_{n-1} - s)^{\vartheta-1} \\
& \quad (\times) \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s), E_1 u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s), E_1 v(s))\| ds d\tau_{n-1} \cdots d\tau_1 \\
& \quad + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \int_0^{\tau_1} \cdots \int_0^{\tau_{n-1}} (\alpha - \tau_1)^{\vartheta-1} (\tau_1 - \tau_2)^{\vartheta-1} \cdots (\tau_{n-1} - s)^{\vartheta-1} \\
& \quad (\times) \|\mathcal{F}(s, u(s), E_1 u(s)) - \mathcal{F}(s, v(s), E_1 v(s))\| ds d\tau_{n-1} \cdots d\tau_1
\end{aligned}$$

By applying assumption (A1)-(A2) and (A4)-(A5), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| \bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(n)} u(\alpha) - \bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(n)} v(\alpha) \right\| \\
& \leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_g \|u - v\| \\
& \quad + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^{\alpha_1} \int_0^{\alpha_1} \cdots \int_0^{\alpha_1} \alpha_1^{n(\vartheta-1)} [\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \|u - v\| \\
& \quad + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}} \|u - v\|] ds d\tau_{n-1} \cdots d\tau_1 \\
& \leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_g + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\alpha_1^{n(\vartheta-1)} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{(n-1)!} \right. \\
& \quad \left. (\times) \int_0^{\alpha_1} (\alpha_1 - s)^{n-1} ds \right] \|u - v\| \\
& \leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_g + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\alpha_1^{n\vartheta} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{n!} \right] \|u - v\| \\
& \leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mathcal{L}_g + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{(\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})^{n\vartheta} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\tau^{n\vartheta} (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \mathcal{L}_k \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}})}{n!} \right] \|u - v\| \\
& \leq C^* \|u - v\|.
\end{aligned}$$

Considering supremum over interval $(0, \alpha_1]$, we get $\|\bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(n)} u - \bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(n)} v\| \leq C^* \|u - v\| \rightarrow 0$ for fixed α_1 . Therefore there exist M^* such that $\bar{\Upsilon}_1^{(M^*)}$ is contraction on B_{r_0} . Thus by general Banach contraction theorem the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \bar{\Upsilon}_1 w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval $(0, \alpha_1]$.

In view of Theorem 2.7.1, we realize that the operator equation $w(\alpha) = \bar{\Upsilon}w(\alpha)$ has unique solution over the interval \mathcal{J} which is nothing but mild solution of the nonlocal system.

□

Example 2.7.1.

Consider the following fractional integro-differential equation with non-instantaneous impulsive condition of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta z(\alpha, w) &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial w^2} z(\alpha, w) + a_1(\alpha) \sin z(\alpha, w) \\ &\quad + \int_0^\alpha a_2(\alpha - s) e^{-z(s, w)} ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, 1/3) \cup [2/3, 1] \end{aligned} \quad (2.7.2)$$

$$z(\alpha, 0) = z(\alpha, 1) = 0, \quad \alpha \in [0, 1], \quad (2.7.3)$$

$$z(0, w) = z_0(w), \quad w \in [0, \pi], \quad (2.7.4)$$

$$z(\alpha, w) = \frac{z(\alpha, w)}{2(1 + z(\alpha, w))}, \quad \alpha \in [1/3, 2/3] \quad (2.7.5)$$

over the interval $[0, 1]$.

Let $E = L^2([0, \pi], \mathbb{R})$ and $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ be an operator by $\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \Theta''$, $\Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q}) = \{\Theta \in E : \Theta \text{ and } \Theta' \text{ are absolutely continuous and } \Theta(0) = \Theta(\pi) = 0\}$. Then

$$\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q}),$$

where $\tau_n(s) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin ns$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the orthonormal set of eigenvectors of \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{Q} generates a C_0 semigroup $\{\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ in E which is given by

$$\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\alpha} \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in E$$

which is uniformly bounded by 1 and also a compact semigroup and hence the operator $R(\lambda, \mathcal{Q}) = (\lambda I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ is compact for each $\lambda \in \rho(\mathcal{Q})$, i.e., $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\beta_0, \Theta_0)$. We also obtain through the concept of subordination of the solution operator $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}$ for each $\alpha \in [0, 1]$.

The system (2.7.2)-(2.7.5) can be reformulated as fractional order abstract form (2.5.1)-(2.5.3) in $E = L^2([0, 1], \mathbb{R})$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta x(\alpha) &= \mathcal{Q}x(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, x(\alpha), E_1x(\alpha)), \quad t \in [0, 1/3) \cup [2/3, 1] \\ x(\alpha) &= \kappa(\alpha, x(\alpha)), \quad t \in [1/3, 2/3] \end{aligned}$$

over the interval $[0,1]$ by defining $x(\alpha) = z(\alpha, \cdot)$.

The functions \mathcal{F} , E_1 and κ over respected domains are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}(\alpha, x(\alpha), E_1x(\alpha)) &= a_1(\alpha) \sin x(\alpha) + E_1x(\alpha) \\ E_1x(\alpha) &= k(\alpha, s, w(s)) = a_2(\alpha - s)e^{-x(\alpha)} \\ \kappa(\alpha, x(\alpha)) &= \frac{x(\alpha)}{2(1 + x(\alpha))}\end{aligned}$$

respectively.

Furthermore

- (i) The function $\mathcal{F} : [0, 1] \times E \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous with respect to α and is differential with respect to argument x and E_1x . Therefore there exist positive constants $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}}$ and $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, x_1, E_1x_1) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, x_2, E_1x_2)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \|x_1 - x_2\| + \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}} \|E_1x_1 - E_1x_2\|,$$

$x_1, x_2 \in B_{r_0}$ for some r_0 .

- (ii) The function $k : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous with respect to α and differentiable with respect to x for all x and hence k is Lipschitz continuous with respect to x . This means there exist positive constant \mathcal{L}_k such that $\|k(\alpha, s, x_1) - k(\alpha, s, x_2)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_k \|x_1 - x_2\|$, $x_1, x_2 \in B_{r_0}$.

- (iii) The non-instantaneous impulse κ is continuous with respect to α and Lipschitz continuous with respect to x with Lipschitz constant $\mathcal{L}_{\kappa} = 1/2 < 1$.

Therefore by Theorem 2.7.1, the system (2.7.2)-(2.7.5) has a unique solution over $[0, 1]$. Hence the equation has a unique solution over the interval $[0, 1]$.

Chapter 3

ON A NEW CLASS OF ATANGANA-BALEANU FRACTIONAL VOLTERRA-FREDHOLM INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL INCLUSIONS WITH NON-INSTANTANEOUS IMPULSES

3.1 Introduction

Fractional order differential equations have attracted multiple researchers due to hereditary attributes and long term memory specifications. Numerous science and engineering models like seepage flow in porous media, anomalous diffusion, the nonlinear oscillations of an earthquake, fluid dynamics, traffic model, electromagnetism, and population dynamics are now revisiting in terms of fractional differential equations. More details and applications are found in monographs in [17, 19] and in articles of [10, 18, 20, 38, 39, 55, 74]. Due to a broad range of applications in various fields, fractional-order differential equations enhanced a rich applied mathematics branch. The study of the existence of mild solutions of fractional differential, integro-differential, and evolution equations using different fixed point theorem were found in [7, 8, 13, 14, 76, 88, 89, 111].

Fractional differential equations (FDEs) with singular kernels have complexities in treating certain physical processes. As a consequence, fractional derivatives with a non-singular kernel have been established. Caputo and Fabrizio [38] published a new description of fractional derivative with exponential kernel in 2015. In [85], authors found the properties of this new concept. Atangana and Baleanu [18] suggested a simplified fractional derivative with the kernel property of Mittag-Leffler. One such new concept is called the A-B fractional derivative, which is more effective in complex model with

memory effects.

There are several problems that have some abrupt shifts in their states, and those abrupt changes are regarded as impulsive impacts on problems. In the present theory, there are two types of impulsive mechanisms, one could be the instantaneous impulsive model, the other is identified as the non-instantaneous impulsive model. In the instantaneous impulsive framework, the duration of these abrupt changes is minimal in relationship with the range of an entire progression measure. These instantaneous impulsive forces occur in heart throbs, shocks and cataclysmic events [33, 84, 86, 93], while in the non-instantaneous impulses, the duration of these unexpected changes continues throughout a restricted time stretch. That is, when constructing a mathematical model for the evolution process, the short time perturbations occur discretely, and its duration is insignificant compared with the total duration of the process. The instantaneous impulsive ordinary and partial differential equations are considered for quick and rapid impulses. On the other hand, we can observe that the models with instantaneous impulsive effects cannot understand pharmacology dynamics' evolution. Recently, Hernandez and O'Regan discussed in [69], the hemodynamic equilibrium of a person, which is the gradual and continuous admission of drugs in the bloodstream, followed by the body's absorption of drugs. Thus, one should state this process as an example of the impulsive action, which begins quickly and remains operative on a particular time interval. It is known as a non-instantaneous impulse, and it can be utilized for constructing mathematical models for such natural processes. Insignificant cases, the partial differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses is used widely to explain the physical model with more accuracy.

The non-instantaneous impulses in non-linear differential equations have been discussed by several authors, see for instance [41, 43, 69, 101, 105, 117]. In particular, Pierri et al. [105] used the analytic semigroup theory to obtain a mild solution for the considered class of abstract semi-linear differential equations with NII. Colao et al. [43] studied the existence of a second-order differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and delayed on an unbounded interval. Yu and Wang used the semigroup theory and fixed point theory on a Banach space to show solutions to periodic boundary value problems with non-instantaneous impulses [123]. In [119], Wang and Li studied the solutions for the periodic boundary value problem with NII. Further, the ordinary

and partial differential equations of fractional order with NII have been discussed in the following papers [1, 48, 82, 97, 114, 120].

Differential systems with non-instantaneous equations have been analyzed by many researchers and got a few novel outcomes, see [1, 35, 41, 50, 82, 97, 114, 119]. The existence, uniqueness, and continuous dependency results of mild solutions for fractional functional integro-differential equations with non-instant impulses were investigated in [50] by employing the method of the α -resolvent family of analytic and fixed-point theorems. In [41], authors have examined the initial value problem for the class of semi-linear evolution equations and provided piecewise-continuous mild solutions for the same under the measure of non-compactness condition. Meeraj et al. [97] analyzed the existence of fractional non-instantaneous impulsive integro-differential equations with non-local conditions and a fixed-point theorem. Lately, Kumar et al. [82] derived the set of sufficient conditions for the existence of mild solutions of A-B fractional system with NII under the notion of measures of non-compactness in Banach space.

Inspired by the aforementioned works, in this chapter, we have been studied the existence of mild solutions of ABFVFIDI with NII of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) &\in \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w(\alpha), \int_0^{\alpha} \chi(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds, \int_0^{\tau} \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \right), \\ \alpha &\in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \\ w(\alpha) &= I_{\ell}(w(\alpha_{\ell})) + \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \\ w(0) &= w_0 \in E, \end{aligned} \tag{3.1.1}$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative of order $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$ with the lower limit zero. $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of ϑ -resolvent operator $\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}, \{\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is a constant, $0 = \alpha_0 = s_0 < \alpha_1 \leq s_1 < \alpha_2 \leq s_2 < \dots < \alpha_m \leq s_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$, are pre-fixed numbers. $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(E)$ is a set valued map, $\chi, \tilde{\chi} : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$, where $\Delta = \{(\alpha, s) : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$ are given functions which fulfills certain conditions to be defined later on. For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m, \kappa_{\ell} : (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \times E \rightarrow E$ are non-instantaneous impulsive functions; $I_{\ell} : E \rightarrow E$ for $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $w_0 \in E$. For our convenience, we denote

$$E_1 w(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha \chi(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \text{ and } E_2 w(\alpha) = \int_0^\tau \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds.$$

The impulses in system (3.1.1) begin rapidly at the points α_ℓ and their process continues on the interval $[\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$. To be exact, the function w takes an instantaneous impulse at α_ℓ and applies various conditions in the two sub-intervals $(\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and $(s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$ of the interval $(\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$. At the point s_ℓ , the function w is continuous. The term $I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell))$ implies that the impulses are often connected to the value of $w(\alpha_\ell) = w(\alpha_\ell^-)$.

We notice that if $\alpha_\ell = s_\ell$ and the second equation of (3.1.1) comes as a form of $\Delta w(\alpha_\ell) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) = w(\alpha_\ell^+) - w(\alpha_\ell^-)$ with $w(\alpha_\ell^+) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+} w(\alpha_\ell + \epsilon)$, $w(\alpha_\ell^-) = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0^-} w(\alpha_\ell + \epsilon)$ describing the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_\ell$.

The merits of this work are listed in brief as follows:

- (i) This research investigates the existence of piecewise-continuous mild solution of ABFVFIDI with NII in Banach space.
- (ii) With the aid of Martelli's fixed point theorem and ϑ -resolvent operators, we develop the main results.
- (iii) To the best of our information, no work exists in ABFVFIDI with NII [with lower limit zero] in literature, and this is the primary inspiration behind this chapter.

As follows, the remaining part of the chapter is structured. In the next section, we will recall some basic notations and definitions. In Section 3.3, we will prove the existence of mild solutions for the system (3.1.1) under Martelli's fixed point theorem [1.10.6]. An example is given to illustrate the theoretical results in Section 3.4.

3.2 Preliminaries

Essential definitions of functional analysis and fractional calculus are recalled in this section, which will help us to prove our main results.

Let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ be the Banach space of continuous functions from \mathcal{J} into E with norm

$$\|w\|_\infty = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha)\|_E.$$

Let $B(E)$ stand for the Banach space of bounded linear operators from E into E .

A measurable function $w : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E$ is Bochner integrable if and only if $\|w\|_E$ is Lebesgue integrable.

Let $L^1(\mathcal{J}, E)$ stand for the Banach space of measurable functions $W : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E$ which are Bochner integrable normed by

$$\|w\|_{L^1} = \int_0^\tau \|w(\alpha)\| d\alpha.$$

For basic definitions of fractional and A-B fractional derivative, we suggest the reader to refer 1.11.1. Next, we need to define the piecewise continuous functions when implementing impulsive conditions.

In particular, we describe

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) = \{w : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E : w \text{ is continuous for } \alpha \neq \alpha_\ell, \\ \text{left continuous at } \alpha = \alpha_\ell \text{ and } w(\alpha_\ell^+) \text{ exists for } \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m\}. \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to see that $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ is a Banach space endowed with the \mathcal{PC} -norm

$$\|w\|_{\mathcal{PC}} = \max \left\{ \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha^+)\|, \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha^-)\| \right\}, \quad w \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E),$$

where $w(\alpha^+)$ and $w(\alpha^-)$ constitute respectively the right and left limits of $w(\alpha)$ at $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$.

Let the metric space be (E, d) . The expressions we have used are $\mathcal{P}(E) = \{Z \in \mathcal{P}(E) : Z \neq \emptyset\}$, $\mathcal{P}_c(E) = \{Z \in \mathcal{P}(E) : Z \text{ closed}\}$, $\mathcal{P}_b(E) = \{Z \in \mathcal{P}(E) : Z \text{ bounded}\}$, $\mathcal{P}_{cp}(E) = \{Z \in \mathcal{P}(E) : Z \text{ compact}\}$ and $\mathcal{P}_c(E) = \{Z \in \mathcal{P}(E) : Z \text{ convex}\}$.

A set-valued map $\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_c(E)$ is said to be measurable, if for every $w \in E$, the function $\alpha \mapsto d(w, \mathcal{G}(\alpha)) = \inf\{|w - z| : z \in \mathcal{G}(\alpha)\}$ is measurable where d is the metric convinced by the Banach space E .

Definition 3.2.1. A set-valued map $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{J} \times E^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_c(E)$ is said to be L^1 -Carathodory if

- (i) $\alpha \mapsto \mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v, z)$ is measurable for each $u, v, z \in E$;
- (ii) $(u, v, z) \mapsto \mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v, z)$ is upper semi-continuous for almost all $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$;
- (iii) For each $r > 0$, we can find $\nu_r \in L^1(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}_+)$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v, z)\| = \sup\{\|\mathcal{F}\| : \mathcal{F} \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v, z)\} \leq \nu_r(\alpha)$$

for almost everywhere $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$.

Remark 3.2.1. (i) For a function w described on \mathcal{J} , we characterize the set

$$S_{\mathcal{F},w} = \{ \mathcal{F} \in L^1(\mathcal{J}, E) : \mathcal{F}(\alpha) \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha), E_1 w(\alpha), E_2 w(\alpha)), \text{ for a.e. } \alpha \in \mathcal{J} \}$$

which is known as the set of selection functions.

(ii) If $\dim(E)$ and $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{J} \times E^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(E)$ is L^1 -Carathéodory, then $S_{\mathcal{F},w} \neq \emptyset$ for each $w \in E$.

For the basic concepts of convex (closed), bounded, upper semi-continuous and closed graph, we refer [24, 46, 57, 93].

In view of 1.11.2, we are now in a position to define the system's mild solution (3.1.1).

Definition 3.2.2. [9, 18, 48] A function $w \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ is a mild solution of (3.1.1) if $w(0) = w_0 \in E$ and $w(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha))$ for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, and each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and if there exists a function $\mathcal{F} \in L^1(\mathcal{J}, E)$ such that $\mathcal{F}(\alpha) \in \mathcal{F}(s, w(s), E_1 w(s), E_2 w(s))$ satisfies the following integral equation

$$w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s)ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s)ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)q_\ell + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s)ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s)ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (3.2.1)$$

where

$$q_\ell = \frac{1}{\Lambda_1} \left[I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(s_\ell)) - \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s)ds - \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell-s) \mathcal{F}(s)ds \right]; \quad (3.2.2)$$

$\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}(\zeta I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} \sigma^{\vartheta-1} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (3.2.3)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (3.2.4)$$

where Γ is a path lying on $\sum_{(\tilde{\alpha}, \omega)}$, see for instance [24].

3.3 Existence Results

In this section, we present and demonstrate the existence results for the system (3.1.1) through the Martelli's fixed point theorem [1.10.6].

(A1) The function $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_{b,c,d}(E)$ is measurable with respect to α for every $(u, v, z) \in E \times E \times E$, and u.s.c with respect to (u, v, z) for each $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$ and the set

$$S_{\mathcal{F},w} = \{ \mathcal{F} \in L^1(\mathcal{J}, E) : \mathcal{F}(\alpha) \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha), E_1 w(\alpha), E_2 w(\alpha)) \text{ for a.e. } \alpha \in \mathcal{J} \}$$

is nonempty.

(A2) For each $(\alpha, s) \in \Delta$, the functions $\chi(\alpha, s, \cdot), \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, \cdot) : E \rightarrow E$ are continuous and for each $w \in E$ the functions $\chi(\alpha, s, \cdot), \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, \cdot) : \Delta \rightarrow E$ are strongly measurable.

(A3) (i) The functions $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times E \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ are continuous and there are positive constants d_ℓ^j , $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2$, such that

$$\|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, w)\| \leq d_\ell^1 \|w\| + d_\ell^2, \quad \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], w \in E.$$

(ii) The functions $I_\ell : E \times E$ are continuous and there are the positive constants c_ℓ^j , $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2$ such that

$$\|I_\ell(w)\| \leq c_\ell^1 \|w\| + c_\ell^2, \quad w \in E.$$

(A4) There exist $\varphi_\chi, \varphi_{\tilde{\chi}} \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}_+)$, such that

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \int_0^\alpha \chi(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \right\| &\leq \varphi_\chi(\alpha) \|w\|, \quad \text{for each } \alpha \in \mathcal{J}, w \in E; \quad \text{and} \\ \left\| \int_0^\alpha \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \right\| &\leq \varphi_{\tilde{\chi}}(\alpha) \|w\|, \quad \text{for each } \alpha \in \mathcal{J}, w \in E. \end{aligned}$$

(A5) \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} are bounded linear operators and we can find constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$.

(A6) There exists $\varphi_{\mathcal{F}} \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}_+)$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v, z)\| = \sup\{\|\mathcal{F}\| : \mathcal{F} \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v, z)\} \leq \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) \Phi(\|u\| + \|v\| + \|z\|)$$

for a.e. $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$ and $u, v, z \in E$, where $\Phi : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is a continuous and non-decreasing function satisfying $\Phi(\gamma(\alpha)(x)) \leq \gamma(\alpha)\Phi(x)$, where $\gamma \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, \mathbb{R}_+)$.

(A7) For every bounded set $U \subset \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$, the sets $\{\alpha \rightarrow \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha)) : w(\alpha) \in U\}$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ are equi-continuous in $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Remark 3.3.1. Since $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times E^3 \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(E)$ is a set-valued map with closed and convex valued. In Example 3.4, we have verified this condition in detail.

Theorem 3.3.1. Let (A1)-(A7) be satisfied. If $\mu = 1 - \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(c_\ell^1 + d_\ell^1) > 0$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and

$$\widetilde{K}_1 \int_0^\tau (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(s) ds < \int_{\widetilde{K}_0}^\infty \frac{du}{\Phi(u)},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{K}_0 &= \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq m} \left\{ \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{1 - \mu} [c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^2] \right\}, \\ \widetilde{K}_1 &= \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq m} \left\{ \frac{(1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}})}{1 - \mu} \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \right\}, \alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \\ K_0 &= \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\|, K_1 = \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right), \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \end{aligned}$$

and $\widetilde{M}(\alpha) = \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha)(1 + \varphi_\chi(\alpha) + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(\alpha))$, $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$,

then there exists a mild solution of the system (3.1.1).

Proof. Define an operator $\Upsilon : \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E))$ as

$$\Upsilon(w) = \left\{ v \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) : v(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha), & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \\ \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \\ \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha), & \alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \end{cases} \right.$$

where, Υ_1 , $\Upsilon_{2\ell}$ and $\Upsilon_{3\ell}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha) &= \left\{ v(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1] \right. \\ \Upsilon_{2\ell} w(\alpha) &= \left\{ v(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \right. \\ \Upsilon_{3\ell} w(\alpha) &= \left\{ v(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell)q_\ell + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds, \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \right. \end{aligned}$$

where $q_\ell, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, defined by (3.2.2) and $\mathcal{F} \in S_{\mathcal{F}, w}$, defined in Remark 3.2.1.

Next, we show that the operator Υ satisfies all the conditions of Martelli's fixed point theorem [1.10.6].

We split the proof into several steps for easier reading.

Step 1: $\Upsilon(w)$ is convex for each $w \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Certainly, if $v_i \in \Upsilon(w), i = 1, 2$, then we can find $\mathcal{F}_i \in S_{\mathcal{F}, w}, i = 1, 2$ in ways that, for each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} v_i(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}_i(s) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}_i(s) ds, \quad i = 1, 2. \end{aligned}$$

Let $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$. Then for each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &[\lambda v_1 + (1-\lambda)v_2](\alpha) \\ &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda \mathcal{F}_1(s) + (1-\lambda)\mathcal{F}_2(s)] ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [\lambda \mathcal{F}_1(s) + (1-\lambda)\mathcal{F}_2(s)] ds. \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, for each $\alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &[\lambda v_1 + (1-\lambda)v_2](\alpha) \\ &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)q_\ell + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda \mathcal{F}_1(s) + (1-\lambda)\mathcal{F}_2(s)] ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [\lambda \mathcal{F}_1(s) + (1-\lambda)\mathcal{F}_2(s)] ds, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} q_\ell &= \frac{1}{\Lambda_1} \left[I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(s_\ell)) \right. \\ &\quad - \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda \mathcal{F}_1(s) + (1-\lambda)\mathcal{F}_2(s)] ds \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell-s) [\lambda \mathcal{F}_1(s) + (1-\lambda)\mathcal{F}_2(s)] ds \right]; \end{aligned}$$

Since $S_{\mathcal{F}, w}$ is convex (\mathcal{F} has convex values), thus

$$[\lambda v_1 + (1-\lambda)v_2] \in \Upsilon(w).$$

Step 2: Υ is bounded on bounded sets of $\mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Indeed, it is sufficient to prove that we can find a positive constant $\tilde{\ell}$ in ways that, for each $v \in \Upsilon(w)$, $w \in B_r = \{w \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E) : \|w\| \leq r\}$, one has $\|v\| \leq \tilde{\ell}$. Suppose $v \in \Upsilon(w)$, then there exists $\mathcal{F} \in S_{\mathcal{F}, w}$ such that for each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$v(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s)ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s)ds$$

By assumptions (A3)-(A5) and Definition 3.2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|v(\alpha)\| &= \|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\|\|w_0\| + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathbb{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s)\|ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbb{S}^2\|}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\|\|\mathcal{F}(s)\|ds \\ &\leq \mu\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \nu_r(s)ds \\ &\leq \mu\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \|\nu_r\|_{L^1\alpha_1}^\vartheta = \tilde{\ell}. \end{aligned}$$

In the similar manner, for each $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we have from (A3),

$$\begin{aligned} \|v(\alpha)\| &\leq \|I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell))\| + \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha))\| \\ &\leq c_\ell^1(r) + c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^1(r) + d_\ell^2 = \tilde{\ell}, \end{aligned}$$

and for $[s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\|v(\alpha)\| \\ &\leq \|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)\|\|q_\ell\| + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathbb{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s)\|ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbb{S}^2\|}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\|\|\mathcal{F}(s)\|ds \\ &\leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} \left[c_\ell^1(r) + c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^1(r) + d_\ell^2 + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell-s)^{\vartheta-1} \nu_r(s)ds \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \nu_r(s)ds \\ &\leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} \left[c_\ell^1(r) + c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^1(r) + d_\ell^2 + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \|\nu_r\|_{L^1s_\ell}^\vartheta \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta+1)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \|\nu_r\|_{L^1\alpha_{\ell+1}}^\vartheta, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\|q_\ell\| \leq \frac{1}{\|\Lambda_1\|} \left[\|I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell))\| + \|\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(s_\ell))\| + \frac{\|S\|\|\mathbf{T}(1-\vartheta)\|}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s)\| ds \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\vartheta\|S^2\|}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell - s) \|\mathcal{F}(s)\| ds \right].$$

Then, we get

$$\|v(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(c_\ell^1(r) + c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^1(r) + d_\ell^2) + (1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}) \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} \tau^\vartheta = \tilde{\ell}.$$

Step 3: Υ maps bounded sets into equi-continuous sets of $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Let B_r be the same as defined in Step 2. Let $0 \leq \nu_1 < \nu_2 \leq \alpha_1$ for each $\nu \in B_r$, we obtain

$$\|(\Upsilon v)(\nu_2) - (\Upsilon v)(\nu_1)\|_E \leq \sum_{i=0}^4 \|C_i\|,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_0 &= Sw_0[\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1)]; \\ C_1 &= \frac{S\mathbf{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1 - s)^{\vartheta-1}] \mathcal{F}(s) ds; \\ C_2 &= \frac{S\mathbf{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds; \\ C_3 &= \frac{\vartheta S^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s)] \mathcal{F}(s) ds; \\ C_4 &= \frac{\vartheta S^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Presently

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_0\| &\leq \mu \|w_0\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1)\| \\ \|C_1\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\ \|C_2\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \end{aligned}$$

$$\|C_3\| \leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta]$$

$$\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.$$

$$\|C_4\| \leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta]$$

$$\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.$$

By applying the continuity of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta$, we deduce that $\|(\Upsilon v)(\nu_2) - (\Upsilon v)(\nu_1)\|_E \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$.

For any $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$ and from (A7), we get

$$\|(\Upsilon v)(\nu_2) - (\Upsilon v)(\nu_1)\|_E = \|\kappa_\ell(\nu_2, w(\nu_2)) - \kappa_\ell(\nu_1, w(\nu_1))\|_E$$

$$\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.$$

In the similar manner, for any $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $s_\ell \leq \nu_1 < \nu_2 \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, we obtain

$$\|(\Upsilon v)(\nu_2) - (\Upsilon v)(\nu_1)\|_E \leq \sum_{i=5}^9 \|C_i\|,$$

where

$$C_5 = \mathbb{S}[\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s_\ell)]q_\ell$$

$$C_6 = \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1 - s)^{\vartheta-1}] \mathcal{F}(s) ds;$$

$$C_7 = \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds;$$

$$C_8 = \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s)] \mathcal{F}(s) ds;$$

$$C_9 = \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds.$$

Now

$$\|C_5\| \leq \mu \|[\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s_\ell)]q_\ell\|_E$$

$$\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.$$

$$\|C_6\| \leq \frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2 - s_\ell)^\vartheta - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta - (\nu_1 - s_\ell)^\vartheta]$$

$$\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\|C_7\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|C_8\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2 - s_\ell)^\vartheta - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta - (\nu_1 - s_\ell)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|C_9\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \|\nu_r\|_{L^1} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

From the above discussion, we conclude that $\|(\Upsilon v)(\nu_2) - (\Upsilon v)(\nu_1)\|_E \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$. Thus the operator Υ is equi-continuous on $\mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$.

Step 4: The set $\mathcal{V}(\alpha) = \{v(\alpha) : v(\alpha) \in \Upsilon(B_r)\}$ is pre-compact in E .

Let $0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau$ be fixed and σ a real number satisfying $0 < \sigma < \alpha$. For $w \in B_r$ and $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we describe

$$\begin{aligned}
v_\sigma(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha-\sigma} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds \\
&\quad + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\alpha-\sigma} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds,
\end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{F} \in S_{\mathcal{F},w}$. Since $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)$ is a compact operator, the set $\mathcal{V}_\sigma(\alpha) = \{v_\sigma(\alpha) : v_\sigma \in \Upsilon(B_r)\}$ is pre-compact in E for each $\sigma, 0 < \sigma < \alpha$. Furthermore, for every $v \in \Upsilon(w)$, we have

$$|v(\alpha) - \mathcal{B}_\sigma(\alpha)| \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{\alpha-\sigma}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \nu_r(s) ds.$$

Therefore, pre-compact sets exist that are arbitrarily near to $\mathcal{V}(\alpha) = \{v(\alpha) : v \in \Upsilon(B_r)\}$, and $\mathcal{V}(\alpha)$ in E are pre-compact.

As outcome of the above steps with Arzela-Ascoli theorem [1.10.7], the completely continuous of Υ is achieved.

Step 5: Υ has a closed graph.

Let $\{w_n\} \subset \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ be a sequence such that $w_n \rightarrow w_*$ and let $\{v_n\}$ be a sequence described by $v_n \in \Upsilon(w_n)$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $v_n \rightarrow v_*$. We shall show that $v_* \in \Upsilon(w_*)$. Since $v_n \in \Upsilon(w_n)$, there exists a $\mathcal{F}_n \in S_{\mathcal{F},w_n}$ in way that for each

$\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$v_n(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}_n(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}_n(s) ds.$$

We must prove that there exists $\mathcal{F}_* \in S_{\mathcal{F}, w_*}$ in ways that

$$v_*(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}_*(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}_*(s) ds.$$

Consider the linear continuous operator

$$\bar{\Upsilon} : L^1([0, \alpha_1], E) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}([0, \alpha_1], E)$$

$$\mathcal{F} \mapsto \bar{\Upsilon}(\mathcal{F})(\alpha) = \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds$$

In view of Lemma 2.2 [93], we note that the operator $\bar{\Upsilon} \cdot S_{\mathcal{F}}$ is closed graph operator.

Furthermore, we have

$$v_n(\alpha) - \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 \in \bar{\Upsilon}(S_{\mathcal{F}(w_n)}).$$

Since $w_n \rightarrow w_*$, it follows that from Lemma 2.2 [93], that

$$v_*(\alpha) - \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 = \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}_*(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}_*(s) ds,$$

for some $\mathcal{F}_* \in S_{\mathcal{F}(w_*)}$.

Hence the multivalued operator Υ is an upper semi-continuous operator on $\mathcal{PC}([0, \alpha_1], E)$.

Now, if $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, from the continuity of I_ℓ, κ_ℓ , $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we have $v_n(t) \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{} v(\alpha)$. As a outcome, we deduce that $v \in \Upsilon$, then from above discussion, we obtain the operator Υ is upper semi-continuous.

Step 6: Finally we demonstrate that the set

$$\mathcal{M} = \{w \in \mathcal{PC}(\mathcal{J}, E) : \lambda w \in \Upsilon(w), \quad \text{for some } \lambda > 1\}$$

is bounded.

Let $w \in \mathcal{M}$. Then $\lambda w \in \Upsilon(w)$ for some $\lambda > 1$. Thus, there exists $\mathcal{F} \in S_{\mathcal{F}, w}$ in ways that for each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} w(\alpha) &= \lambda^{-1} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)w_0 + \lambda^{-1} \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s) ds \\ &\quad + \lambda^{-1} \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s) ds \end{aligned}$$

By assumptions (A3)-(A6), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|w(\alpha)\| \\
& \leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
& \quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(s) \Phi(\|w(s)\| + \varphi_{\chi}(s)\|w(s)\| + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s)\|w(s)\|) ds \\
& \leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
& \quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(s) (1 + \varphi_{\chi}(s) + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s)) \Phi(\|w(s)\|) ds \\
& \leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\| + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(s) \Phi(\|w(s)\|) ds \\
& \leq K_0 + K_1 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(s) \Phi(\|w(s)\|) ds,
\end{aligned}$$

where $K_0 = \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|w_0\|$, $K_1 = \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right)$ and $\widetilde{M}(\alpha) = \vartheta_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha)(1 + \varphi_{\chi}(\alpha) + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(\alpha))$.

Let us take the right hand side of the above inequality as $\beta(\alpha)$. Then, we obtain

$$\beta(0) = K_0, \quad \|w(\alpha)\| \leq \beta(\alpha), \quad \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1],$$

and

$$\beta'(\alpha) = K_1 (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(\alpha) \Phi(\|w(\alpha)\|).$$

Using the non-decreasing character of Φ , we get

$$\beta'(\alpha) \leq K_1 (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(\alpha) \Phi(\beta(\alpha)).$$

The above inequality implies, for each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$ that

$$\int_{\beta(0)}^{\beta(\alpha)} \frac{du}{\Phi(u)} \leq K_1 \int_0^{\alpha_1} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(s) ds < \int_{K_0}^{\infty} \frac{du}{\Phi(u)}.$$

Accordingly, we can find a constant \bar{K}_1 such that $\beta(\alpha) \leq \bar{K}_1$, $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, and as a deduction $\|w\| \leq \bar{K}_1$. From this, we notice that the set \mathcal{M} is bounded. By thinking of Theorem [1.10.6], we deduct that Υ has a fixed point, which is a mild solution of the system (3.1.1) on $[0, \alpha_1]$.

For $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and from (A3), we have

$$\|w(\alpha)\| \leq \|I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell))\| + \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha))\| \leq c_\ell^1(r) + c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^1(r) + d_\ell^2,$$

and for each $\alpha \in [s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} w(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell)q_\ell + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s)ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s)\mathcal{F}(s)ds, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} q_\ell &= \frac{1}{\Lambda_1} \left[I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w(s_\ell)) - \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s)ds \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{s_\ell} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(s_\ell - s)\mathcal{F}(s)ds \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\|w(\alpha)\| \\ &\leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}[c_\ell^1\|w(\alpha)\| + c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^1\|w(\alpha)\| + d_\ell^2] + \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_\mathcal{F}(s)\Phi(\|w(s)\| + \varphi_\chi(s)\|w(s)\| + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s)\|w(s)\|)ds \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_\mathcal{F}(s)\Phi(\|w(s)\| + \varphi_\chi(s)\|w(s)\| + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s)\|w(s)\|)ds \\ &\leq \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}}{1 - \mu}[c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^2] + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}}{1 - \mu} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_0^{s_\ell} (s_\ell - s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_\mathcal{F}(s)(1 + \varphi_\chi(s) + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s))\Phi(\|w(s)\|)ds \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{1 - \mu} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_\mathcal{F}(s)(1 + \varphi_\chi(s) + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s))\Phi(\|w(s)\|)ds. \end{aligned}$$

In general, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|w(\alpha)\| &\leq \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}}{1 - \mu}[c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^2] + \frac{(1 + \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B})}{1 - \mu} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \varphi_\mathcal{F}(s)(1 + \varphi_\chi(s) + \varphi_{\bar{\chi}}(s))\Phi(\|w(s)\|)ds \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \widetilde{K}_0 + \widetilde{K}_1 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(s) \Phi(\|w(s)\|) ds,$$

where

$$\widetilde{K}_0 = \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq m} \left\{ \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}}{1 - \mu} [c_\ell^2 + d_\ell^2] \right\}, \quad \widetilde{K}_1 = \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq m} \left\{ \frac{(1 + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}})}{1 - \mu} \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \right\}$$

and $\widetilde{M}(\alpha) = \vartheta_{\mathcal{D}}(\alpha)(1 + \varphi_{\mathcal{X}}(\alpha) + \varphi_{\widetilde{\mathcal{X}}}(\alpha))$.

Let's consider $\bar{\beta}(\alpha)$ as the right hand side of the above inequality. So, then we get

$$\bar{\beta}(0) = \widetilde{K}_0, \quad \|w(\alpha)\| \leq \bar{\beta}(\alpha), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau],$$

and

$$\bar{\beta}'(\alpha) = \widetilde{K}_1 (s - \alpha)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(\alpha) \Phi(\|w(\alpha)\|).$$

Using the non-decreasing character of Φ , we get

$$\bar{\beta}'(\alpha) \leq \widetilde{K}_1 (s - \alpha)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(\alpha) \Phi(\bar{\beta}(\alpha)).$$

The above inequality implies, for each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$ that

$$\int_{\bar{\beta}(0)}^{\bar{\beta}(\alpha)} \frac{du}{\Phi(u)} \leq \widetilde{K}_1 \int_0^{\alpha_1} (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{M}(s) ds < \int_{\widetilde{K}_0}^{\infty} \frac{du}{\Phi(u)}.$$

Consequently, we can find a constant \bar{K}_2 such that $\bar{\beta}(\alpha) \leq \bar{K}_2$, $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, and as a deduction $\|w\| \leq \bar{K}_2$. From this, we realize that the set \mathcal{M} is bounded. In view of of Theorem [1.10.6], we deduct that Υ has a fixed point, which is a mild solution of the system (3.1.1) on $[0, \tau]$. \square

3.4 Example

In this section, we give an example to illustrate the above theoretical result.

Let $E = L^2([0, \pi], \mathbb{R})$ and $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ be an operator by $\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \Theta''$, $\Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q})$ with domain $D(\mathcal{Q}) = \{\Theta \in E; \Theta \text{ and } \Theta' \text{ are absolutely continuous, } \Theta'' \in E, \Theta(0) = \Theta(\pi) = 0\}$. Then

$$\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q}),$$

where $\Theta_n(s) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin(ns)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the orthonormal set of eigenvectors of \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{Q} generates a C_0 semigroup $\{\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ in E which is given by

$$\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\alpha} \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in E, \alpha > 0$$

which is uniformly bounded and also a compact semigroup and hence the operator $R(\lambda, \mathcal{Q}) = (\lambda I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ is compact for each $\lambda \in \rho(\mathcal{Q})$, i.e., $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\beta_0, \Theta_0)$. We also obtain through the concept of subordination of the solution operator $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}$ for each $\alpha \in [0, \pi]$. For more details, refer [82].

We consider the following system:

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\frac{3}{4}} u(\alpha, x) \in \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} u(\alpha, x) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, x(\alpha), E_1 x(\alpha), E_2 x(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in \left(0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\right] \cup \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}, 1\right], \quad (3.4.1)$$

$$u(\alpha, x) = \frac{1}{24} \sin u \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, x \right) + \frac{1}{12} \cos \pi \alpha u \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, x \right), \quad \alpha \in \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \right], \quad x \in [0, \pi], \quad (3.4.2)$$

$$u(\alpha, 0) = u(\alpha, \pi) = 0, \quad \alpha \in [0, 1], \quad (3.4.3)$$

$$u(0, x) = u_0, \quad x \in [0, \pi], \quad (3.4.4)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\frac{3}{4}}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative is taken for the time variable α with the lower limit zero.

Further for $\alpha \in \left(0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}\right] \cup \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}, 1\right]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\alpha, x(\alpha), E_1 x(\alpha), E_2 x(\alpha)) = & \left\{ 0, \frac{\|u(\alpha, x)\|}{12(\sqrt{\alpha} + 1)(1 + \|u(\alpha, x)\|)} \right. \\ & + \frac{e^{-\alpha}}{(\sqrt{\alpha} + 1)(\alpha + 1)} \int_0^\alpha \frac{\sqrt{\alpha} u(s, x)}{8(1 + s^2 + \alpha)(1 + u^2(s, x))} ds \\ & \left. + \frac{e^{-\alpha}}{(\sqrt{\alpha} + 1)(\alpha + 1)} \int_0^\alpha \frac{\sqrt{\alpha} u(s, x)}{16(1 + s^2 + \alpha)(1 + u^2(s, x))} ds \right\}. \quad (3.4.5) \end{aligned}$$

Take $\tau = \alpha_2 = 1, \alpha_0 = s_0 = 0, \alpha_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, s_1 = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}$. The system (3.4.1)-(3.4.5) can be written in the abstract form (3.1.1):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta w(\alpha) \in \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w(\alpha), \int_0^\alpha \chi(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds, \int_0^\tau \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w(s)) ds \right), \\ \alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \quad \ell = 1, 2; \end{aligned}$$

$$w(\alpha) = I_\ell(w(\alpha_\ell)) + \kappa_\ell(\alpha, w(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], \ell = 1,$$

$$w(0) = w_0 \in E,$$

where $w(\alpha) = u(\alpha, \cdot)$, that is $w(\alpha)(x) = u(\alpha, x)$, $x \in [0, \pi]$.

Next, we verify that the assumptions (A1)-(A7) for the above system (3.4.1)-(3.4.5) one by one.

Verification of (A1):

Set

$$\mathcal{F}(\alpha, w(\alpha), E_1w(\alpha), E_2w(\alpha))$$

$$= \{\mathcal{F} \in E : f_1(\alpha, w(\alpha), E_1w(\alpha), E_2w(\alpha)) \leq \mathcal{F} \leq f_2(\alpha, w(\alpha), E_1w(\alpha), E_2x(\alpha))\},$$
(3.4.6)

where $f_1, f_2 : [0, 1] \times E^3 \rightarrow E$. We assume that for each $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, f_1 is lower semi-continuous (i.e., the set $\{w \in E : f_1(\alpha, w, E_1w, E_2w) > \tilde{\mu}\}$ is open for each $\tilde{\mu} \in E$), and assume that for each $t \in [0, 1]$, f_2 is upper semi-continuous (i.e., the set $\{w \in E : f_2(\alpha, w, E_1w, E_2w) < \tilde{\mu}\}$ is open for each $\tilde{\mu} \in E$). Assume that there exists $\varphi_{\mathcal{F}} \in \mathcal{C}([0, 1], \mathbb{R})$ and $\Phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is a non-decreasing function such that

$$\max\{\|f_1(\alpha, x(\alpha), E_1x(\alpha), E_2x(\alpha))\|, \|f_2(\alpha, x(\alpha), E_1x(\alpha), E_2x(\alpha))\|\}$$

$$\leq \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha)\Phi(\|w(\alpha)\| + \|E_1w(\alpha)\| + \|E_2w(\alpha)\|), \quad \alpha \in [0, 1], w \in E.$$
(3.4.7)

From the equations (3.4.5), (3.4.6) and (3.4.7) along with the above discussion, we observe that \mathcal{F} is non-empty and further clear that \mathcal{F} is compact and convex valued, and is upper semi-continuous. Therefore \mathcal{F} satisfies the condition (A1).

Verification of (A2) and (A4):

The function $\chi : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$ is given by

$$\chi(\alpha, s, w)(x) = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}w(\alpha)(x)}{8(1 + s^2 + \alpha)(1 + w^2(\alpha)(x))}$$
(3.4.8)

and the function $\tilde{\chi} : \Delta \times E \rightarrow E$ is given by

$$\tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w)(x) = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}w(\alpha)(x)}{16(1 + s^2 + \alpha)(1 + w^2(\alpha)(x))}.$$
(3.4.9)

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \int_0^\alpha \chi(\alpha, s, w)(x) ds \right\| &\leq \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{8 + 8\alpha} \|w(\alpha)(x)\| \\ &\leq \varphi_\chi(\alpha) \|w(\alpha)(x)\|, \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.10)$$

where $\varphi_\chi(\alpha) = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{8 + 8\alpha}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \int_0^\alpha \tilde{\chi}(\alpha, s, w)(x) ds \right\| &\leq \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{16 + 16\alpha} \|w(\alpha)(x)\| \\ &\leq \varphi_{\tilde{\chi}}(\alpha) \|w(\alpha)(x)\|, \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.11)$$

where $\varphi_{\tilde{\chi}}(\alpha) = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha}}{16 + 16\alpha}$.

From the equations (3.4.8)-(3.4.11), we notice that the assumptions (A2) and (A4) are verified.

Verification of (A3) and (A7):

From (3.4.2), we consider the function

$$\kappa_1(\alpha, w(\alpha))(x) = \frac{1}{12} \cos \pi \alpha w \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) (x) \quad (3.4.12)$$

and

$$\|\kappa_1(\alpha, w(\alpha))(x)\| \leq \frac{1}{12} \|w(\alpha)(x)\| \quad (3.4.13)$$

$$\leq d_1^1 \|w(\alpha)(x)\| + d_2^2, \quad (3.4.14)$$

where $d_1^1 = \frac{1}{12}$ and $d_2^2 = 0$.

From (3.4.12), we notice that the function represent the non-instantaneous impulses during interval $\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}, \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$.

Further, consider the function

$$I_1(w(\alpha))(x) = \frac{1}{24} \sin w \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) (x) \quad (3.4.15)$$

and

$$\|I_1(w(\alpha))(x)\| \leq \frac{1}{24} \|w(\alpha)(x)\| \quad (3.4.16)$$

$$\leq c_1^1 \|w(\alpha)(x)\| + c_2^2, \quad (3.4.17)$$

where $c_1^1 = \frac{1}{24}$ and $c_2^2 = 0$.

For any $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1$, we have from (3.4.12),

$$\begin{aligned} & \|\kappa_1(\nu_2, w(\nu_2))(x) - \kappa_1(\nu_1, w(\nu_1))(x)\| \\ &= \left\| \frac{1}{12} \cos \pi \nu_2 w \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) (x) - \frac{1}{12} \cos \pi \nu_1 w \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right) (x) \right\| \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.18)$$

From equations (3.4.14), (3.4.17) and (3.4.18), we realize that the assumptions (A3) and (A7) verified.

Verification of (A5):

In view of Definition 3.2.2, we have

$\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}(\zeta I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$, $B(\vartheta) = 1 - \vartheta + \frac{\vartheta}{\Gamma(\vartheta)}$. From (3.4.1), we know that $\vartheta = \frac{3}{4}$.

Therefore

$$B\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{3}{4}\right) + \frac{\frac{3}{4}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)} = 0.86, \quad \text{since } \Gamma(0.75) = 1.2254.$$

From the above normalization function value, we have

$$\zeta = 3.44 \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\gamma} = 3.$$

From the above discussion, Λ_1 and Λ_2 are bounded linear operators and there are positive constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\Lambda_1\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\Lambda_2\| \leq \bar{\mu}$.

Verification of (A6):

The function $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{J} \times E^3 \rightarrow E$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{F}(\alpha, v, y, z)(x) \\ &= \frac{\|v(\alpha)(x)\|}{12(\sqrt{\alpha} + 1)(1 + \|v(\alpha)(x)\|)} + \frac{e^{-\alpha}}{(\sqrt{\alpha} + 1)(\alpha + 1)} y(\alpha)(x) + \frac{e^{-\alpha}}{(\sqrt{\alpha} + 1)(\alpha + 1)} z(\alpha)(x). \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, v, y, z)(x)\| &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{\alpha}} \Phi(\|v(\alpha)(x)\| + \|y(\alpha)(x)\| + \|z(\alpha)(x)\|) \\ &\leq \varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) \Phi(\|v(\alpha)(x)\| + \|y(\alpha)(x)\| + \|z(\alpha)(x)\|), \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.19)$$

where $\varphi_{\mathcal{F}}(\alpha) = \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{\alpha}}$ and $\widehat{\Phi}(\alpha) = \alpha$. From this, we observe that the assumption (A5) is verified.

Furthermore, from Theorem 3.3.1, we realize that

$$\mu = 1 - \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}(c_1^1 + d_1^1) > 0.$$

That is, we need to prove that $\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}(c_1^1 + d_1^1) < 1$. To do this, from (3.4.14) and (3.4.17), we have

$$1 \left(\frac{1}{24} + \frac{1}{12} \right) = 0.1246 < 1.$$

Clearly, all the assumptions of Theorem 3.3.1 are satisfied. Hence by the conclusion of Theorem 3.3.1, it follows that system (3.4.1)-(3.4.5) has a solution.

Chapter 4

EXISTENCE RESULTS FOR ATANGANA-BALEANU FRACTIONAL NEUTRAL INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS WITH INFINITE DELAY THROUGH SECTORIAL OPERATORS

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, firstly, we examine the existence of mild solutions of ABFSIDE with ID of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} w(\alpha) = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w_{\alpha}, \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w_s) ds \right), \quad \alpha \in \mathcal{J} = [0, \tau] \quad (4.1.1)$$

$$w(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (4.1.2)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo (ABC) derivative of order ϑ , where $0 < \vartheta < 1$. $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of ϑ -resolvent operator $\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}, \{\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is the solution operator on a complex Banach space $(E, \|\cdot\|)$, $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is a constant; $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \times E \rightarrow E; k : \Delta \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$, where $\Delta = \{(\alpha, s) : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$ are given functions which ensures assertions to be defined subsequently. For our convenience, we label $E_1 w_s = \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w_s) ds$.

For any function w defined on $(-\infty, +\infty)$ and any $\alpha \geq 0$, we denote w_{α} the element of \mathcal{B} defined by $w_{\alpha}(\theta) = w(\alpha + \theta)$, $\theta \in (-\infty, 0]$ up to the present time α . We assume that the histories w_{α} belong to some abstract phase space \mathcal{B} , to be specified in next section.

In section 4.5, we also discuss the existence results for ABFSNIDE of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} [w(\alpha) - \mathcal{G}(\alpha, w_{\alpha})] = \mathcal{Q}w(\alpha) + \mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, w_{\alpha}, \int_0^{\alpha} k(\alpha, s, w_s) ds \right), \quad (4.1.3)$$

$$w(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (4.1.4)$$

where $\alpha \in \mathcal{J} = [0, \tau]$ and $\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is a continuous function and other functions are same as defined in system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2).

Fractional calculus is a branch of mathematics that generalizes the conventional concepts of integral and derivative operators to integrals and derivatives of the fractional order. Due to its applications in diverse fields of applied science, the solutions of fractional differential equations in analytical and numerical senses have been of considerable interest, see for instance [6, 49, 73]. For the fundamentals of fractional theory, see Kilbas et al. [78], Miller and Ross [99] and Podlubny [106]. However, there are several fractional neutral models that are yet to be explored and extended to real-world implementations in various fields of science and engineering.

Recently, Caputo and Fabrizio [38] suggested a derivative on which the exponential decay law is used to move ahead within the domain of fractional calculus. Certain advantages over current ones of this derivative are that, the derivative should be used when following the exponential law of nature; since the kernel is focused on the exponential function, this derivative is free of singularity. A lot of work on this latest discovery has recently been achieved with considerable results [15, 16, 58]. This derivative has been used in mechanical engineering, groundwater studies, thermal physics, diffusion models and other fields of study [15, 16]. In [21], Atangana and Koca pointed out another important problem where they said the solution of the equation ${}_0^{CF} \mathcal{D}_\alpha^\vartheta w(\alpha) = w(\alpha)$ was not a special function but an exponential function. Atangana and Baleanu [18] proposed an even better overview of a derivative without a single kernel to fix this issue, which satisfies the problems figured out against that of Caputo-Fabrizio [38]. Their derivative is concentrated on the generalized Mittag-Leffler equation that is well-known. In 2018, Atangana and Alqahtani [17] explored the existence and uniqueness results for the Keller–Segel model with Atangana-Baleanu derivative via numerical technique. Ucar et al. [115] discussed the contribution of Atangana-Baleanu derivative on the smoking model. For further information on the Atangana-Baleanu derivative and its applications in various branches of science, we suggest the reader to refer [9, 19, 20, 73, 108].

There has been a growing interest in the development of functional differential equations integrating memory or aftereffect in many fields of research, i.e. there is the effect of infinite delay on state equations, see for instance [79, 80, 121] and references therein for a wealth of reference materials on the topic. As a result, there seems to be a strong need to address functional differential systems with infinite delay. And the development of the theory of functional differential system with infinite delays depends on a choice of a phase space. In reality, multiple phase spaces have been discussed and a separate development of the theory has been needed for each particular phase space. (Hino et al. [72]). The usual space is the phase space \mathcal{B} indicated by Hale and Kato [63], which is commonly used in functional differential equations with infinite delay, one can see [68, 107] and references therein for additional details.

Some interesting findings on Atangana-Baleanu fractional order differential equations in Banach spaces have recently been identified by the authors, see for instance [9, 18, 73, 82, 108, 115]. In [73], authors discussed the existence and uniqueness criteria for ordinary differential equation containing Atangana–Baleanu fractional derivative and further they discussed the Ulam stability also in detail. Aimene et al. [9] established the controllability of semi-linear differential equation of Atangana-Baleanu fractional order with impulses and finite delay through Darbo fixed point theorem. Atangana and Seda Igrret Araz [22] introduced a new partial integro-differential equation with mixed fractional operators. The differential operator can be taken as Caputo while the integral is consider to be Caputo–Fabrizio or the Atangana–Baleanu integral. Recently, Seda Igrret Araz [110] presented a new integro-differential equation by utilizing from the concept of fractal-fractional derivative and Atangana integral under Banach contraction principle. Further, in [96], authors discussed the Predictor–corrector for non-linear differential and integral equation with fractal–fractional operators. Recently, Kumar and Pandey [82] analyzed the existence of mild solution of Atangana–Baleanu fractional differential system with non-instantaneous impulses in Banach spaces. Very recently, Baleanu and Agarwal [26] discussed the main ideas of fractional calculus had in science and engineering and briefly present just a point of view for some of the crucial problems of this interdisciplinary field. To the authors’ knowledge, no work exists in Atangana-Baleanu fractional neutral integro-differential system with infinite delay in literature, and this is the key inspiration of this

chapter.

Sparked by the above reason and discussions, our main aim is to analyze the existence and uniqueness results of ABFSIDE and ABFSNIDE in Banach spaces. The main contribution of this chapter is indexed in brief as pursues:

- (i) Atangana-Baleanu fractional derivative is incorporate into the fractional semi-linear integro-differential equations and fractional semi-linear neutral integro-differential equations with infinite delay for the first time.
- (ii) By utilizing the A-B derivative along with the semigroup property and Laplace transform, we have introduced the mild solution of the given system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) for the first time in literature.
- (iii) Depends on the principle of Banach contraction mapping and ϑ -resolvent operators, we analyzed the existence and uniqueness for the addressed system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) and (4.1.3)-(4.1.4).
- (iv) Based on famous generalized Gronwall's inequality techniques, we have established the solution of (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) and (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) are bounded.
- (v) Based on the nonlinear alternative of the Leray-Schauder, Krasnoselskii-Schaefer fixed point theorem and properties of ϑ -resolvent operators, we analyzed the existence results for the addressed system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) and (4.1.3)-(4.1.4).
- (vi) Moreover, the obtained results in this chapter are generalized and improved the existing works in the literature [9, 82].

The scheme of this chapter is as planned out as follows. In the next section, we recall some basic definitions and notations which are required in the discussion. Section 4.3 is devoted to the existence and uniqueness of mild solution for the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) through Banach contraction principle [1.10.1] under some assumptions. Further, we also investigate the existence of mild solution for the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) through nonlinear alternative of Leray-Schauder type [1.10.3] under suitable conditions in the same section. An example is given in Section 4.4 to illustrate the theoretical results. Section 4.5 is

dedicated to the existence and uniqueness of mild solution for the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) through Banach contraction principle [1.10.1] under some assumptions. Further, we also examine the existence of mild solution for the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) through Krasnoselskii-Schaefer fixed point theorem [1.10.2] under some suitable conditions in the same section.

4.2 Preliminaries

Basic definitions and notations of fractional calculus and functional analysis are recalled in this section, which will help us to prove our main results.

Let $\mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ be the Banach space of continuous functions from \mathcal{J} into E with norm

$$\|w\|_{\infty} = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(\alpha)\|_E.$$

$B(E)$ denotes the Banach space of bounded linear operators from E into E .

A measurable function $w : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E$ is Bochner integrable if and only if $\|w\|_E$ is Lebesgue integrable.

Let $L^1(\mathcal{J}, E)$ be the Banach space of measurable functions $W : \mathcal{J} \rightarrow E$ which are Bochner integrable normed by

$$\|w\|_{L^1} = \int_0^{\tau} \|w(\alpha)\|_E d\alpha.$$

For basic definitions of fractional and A-B fractional derivative, we suggest the reader to refer 1.11.1.

To apply delay conditions, we need to define the phase space axioms \mathcal{B} introduced by Hale and Kato [63] and follow the terminology used in [72]. Thus $(\mathcal{B}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{B}})$ will be a semi-normed linear space of functions mapping $(-\infty, 0]$ into E and fulfilling the axioms below.

(C1) If $w : (-\infty, \tau) \rightarrow E, \tau > 0$ is continuous on \mathcal{J} and $w_0 \in \mathcal{B}$, then for every $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$ the following conditions hold:

(i) $w_{\alpha} \in \mathcal{B}$;

(ii) There exists a positive constant G such that $\|w(\alpha)\|_E \leq G\|w_{\alpha}\|_{\mathcal{B}}$;

(iii) There exist two functions $P(\cdot), Q(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ independent of w with P continuous and bounded, and Q locally bounded in ways that

$$\|w_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq P(\alpha) \sup\{\|w(s)\|_E : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha\} + Q(\alpha)\|w_0\|_{\mathcal{B}}.$$

(C2) For the function $w(\cdot)$ in (C1), w_α is a \mathcal{B} -valued continuous function on \mathcal{J} .

(C3) The space \mathcal{B} is complete.

For simplicity, we denote

$$p = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|P(\alpha)\| \quad \text{and} \quad q = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{J}} \|Q(\alpha)\|.$$

From the above axioms, we realize that (C1)(ii) equivalent to $\|\varphi(0)\| \leq G\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}$ for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{B}$.

Now, we define the space

$$Y_\tau = \{w : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E \quad \text{such that} \quad w_0 \in \mathcal{B} \quad \text{and the condition} \quad w|_{\mathcal{J}} \text{ is continuous}\}.$$

For the function $\|\cdot\|_{Y_\tau}$ is defined as a seminorm in Y_τ ,

$$\|w\|_{Y_\tau} = \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \sup_{s \in \mathcal{J}} \|w(s)\|, \quad w \in Y_\tau.$$

In view of 1.11.2, we are now able to describe the mild solution of the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2).

Definition 4.2.1. [9, 18] A function $w \in Y_\tau$ is a mild solution of (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) if $w_0 = \varphi \in \mathcal{B}$ and satisfies the following integral equation

$$w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \end{cases} \quad (4.2.1)$$

$\mathbb{S} = \zeta^*(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ with $\zeta^* = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} \sigma^{\vartheta-1} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma \quad (4.2.2)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta, \vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (4.2.3)$$

where Γ is a path lying on $\sum_{(\tilde{\alpha}, \omega)}$, see for instance [24].

4.3 Existence Results for ABFSIDE

In this section, we present and demonstrate the existence results for the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) under the Banach contraction principle [1.10.1] and Leray-Schauder fixed point theorem [1.10.3].

Next, we list the subsequent hypotheses for the use of the Banach fixed point theorem [1.10.1]:

(A1) The function $k(\alpha, s, \cdot) : \Delta \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is continuous and there exists a constant $\mathcal{N}_k > 0$ such that for all $(\alpha, s) \in \mathcal{J}; u, v \in \mathcal{B}$;

$$(A1)(i) \quad \left\| \int_0^\alpha [k(\alpha, s, u) - k(\alpha, s, v)] ds \right\| \leq \mathcal{N}_k \|u - v\|_{\mathcal{B}};$$

$$(A1)(ii) \quad \left\| \int_0^\alpha k(\alpha, s, u) ds \right\| \leq \mathcal{N}_k (1 + \|u\|_{\mathcal{B}});$$

(A2) $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous and there exist positive constants $\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}}, \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}, \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}$ such that for each $(\alpha, u, v), (\alpha, u_1, v_1), (\alpha, u_2, v_2) \in \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \times E$;

$$(A2)(i) \quad \|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, u_1, v_1) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, u_2, v_2)\| \leq \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} (\|u_1 - u_2\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \|v_1 - v_2\|);$$

$$(A2)(ii) \quad \|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, u, v)\| \leq \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} (\|u\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \|v\|) + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}.$$

(A3) \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} are bounded linear operators and we can find constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$.

Our first existence result for the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) is based on the Banach contraction principle.

Theorem 4.3.1. *If assumptions (A1)(i)-(A2)(i) and (A3) are satisfied and*

$$\left[\left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] p \right] < 1, \quad (4.3.1)$$

then the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) has a unique mild solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$.

Proof. Consider the operator $\Upsilon : Y_\tau \rightarrow Y_\tau$ defined by

$$(\Upsilon w)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \leq 0, \\ \mathbb{S} \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) \varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S} \mathbb{T} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases} \quad (4.3.2)$$

Evidently, fixed points of the operator Υ are mild solutions of the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2).

Let us define $u(\cdot) : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ by

$$u(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \leq 0 \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0), & \alpha \in \mathcal{J}. \end{cases}$$

Therefore $u_0 = \varphi$. For each function $v \in \mathcal{C}(\mathcal{J}, E)$ with $v_0 = 0$, we express by \bar{v} the function defined by

$$\bar{v}(\alpha) = \begin{cases} 0, & \alpha \leq 0 \\ v(\alpha), & \alpha \in \mathcal{J}. \end{cases}$$

If $w(\cdot)$ fulfills (4.2.1), we split it as $w(\alpha) = v(\alpha) + u(\alpha)$, $\alpha \geq 0$ which suggest that $w_\alpha = v_\alpha + u_\alpha$ for every $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$ and the function $v(\cdot)$ fulfills

$$v(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases} \quad (4.3.3)$$

Let $Y_\tau^0 = \{v \in Y_\tau : v_0 = 0 \in \mathcal{B}\}$. For any $v \in Y_\tau^0$, we obtain

$$\|v\|_{Y_\tau^0} = \|v_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \sup\{\|v(s)\|_E : 0 \leq s \leq \tau\} = \sup\{\|v(s)\|_E : 0 \leq s \leq \tau\}.$$

Thus $(Y_\tau^0, \|\cdot\|_{Y_\tau^0})$ is a Banach space. Operator $\bar{\Upsilon} : Y_\tau^0 \rightarrow Y_\tau^0$ is defined by:

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases} \quad (4.3.4)$$

Clearly the operator Υ has a fixed point is equivalent to $\bar{\Upsilon}$ has a fixed point, and so we turn to show that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ has a fixed point. Now, our purpose is to demonstrate that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is a

contraction map of Y_τ^0 . Indeed, for every $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, $v, \bar{v} \in Y_\tau^0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}\bar{v})(\alpha)\| \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} \left[\|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{E}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left\| \int_0^s [k(s, \zeta, v_\zeta) - k(s, \zeta, \bar{v}_\zeta)] d\zeta \right\| \right] ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] \|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{E}} ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] p \sup_{s \in [0, \tau]} \|v(s) - \bar{v}(s)\|_{\mathcal{E}} ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] p \|v - \bar{v}\|_{Y_\tau^0}. \tag{4.3.5}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v) - (\bar{\Upsilon}\bar{v})\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq \left[\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] p \right] \|v - \bar{v}\|_{Y_\tau^0}. \tag{4.3.6}$$

From (4.3.1), we see that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is a contraction. Hence the model (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) has a unique solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$. \square

By utilizing the nonlinear alternative of the Leray–Schauder fixed point theorem [1.10.3], now we give another existence result for the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2).

Theorem 4.3.2. *Assume that (A1)(ii), (A2)(ii) and (A3) hold. Then the system (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) has at least one mild solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$.*

Proof. Let $\bar{\Upsilon} : Y_\tau^0 \rightarrow Y_\tau^0$ be the same as described in (4.3.4). Firstly, we intend to demonstrate that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is continuous and completely continuous. In order to understand the concepts clearly, we continue in the subsequent steps.

Step 1: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is continuous on Y_τ^0 .

From the assumptions of \mathcal{F} and k , we conclude that the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is continuous.

Step 2: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ maps bounded sets into bounded sets in Y_τ^0 .

Indeed, it is sufficient to demonstrate that there exists a positive constant ℓ such that for each $v \in B_r = \{v \in Y_\tau^0 : \|v\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq r\}$, one has $\|\bar{\Upsilon}v\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq \ell$. Let $v \in B_r$. From (A1)(ii),

(A2)(ii) and (A3), for each $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha)\| \\
& \leq \left\| \frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1v_s + u_s) ds \right\| \\
& \quad + \left\| \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1v_s + u_s) ds \right\| \\
& \leq \frac{\|\mathbf{S}\|\|\mathbf{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1v_s + u_s)\| ds \\
& \quad + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbf{S}^2\|}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\| \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1v_s + u_s)\| ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
& \quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \left\{ \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}[\|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \mathcal{N}_k(1 + \|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}})] + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \right\} ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
& \quad (\times) [\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1 + \mathcal{N}_k)(e + pr) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}] \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} ds \\
& \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) [\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1 + \mathcal{N}_k)(e + pr) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}] \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} = \ell, \quad (4.3.7)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\|v_\alpha + u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} & \leq \|v_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \|u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
& \leq P(\alpha)\|v(\alpha)\|_E + Q(\alpha)\|v_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} + P(\alpha)\|u(\alpha)\|_E + Q(\alpha)\|u_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
& \leq P(\alpha)\|v(\alpha)\|_E + P(\alpha)[\|\mathbf{S}\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0)\|_E] + Q(\alpha)\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
& \leq p \sup_{0 \leq s \leq \alpha} \|v(s)\|_E + p\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}G\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + q\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
& = p \sup_{0 \leq s \leq \alpha} \|v(s)\|_E + (p\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}G + q)\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}. \quad (4.3.8)
\end{aligned}$$

Then, we get

$$\|v_\alpha + u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq e + p \sup_{0 \leq s \leq \alpha} \|v(s)\|_E, \quad (4.3.9)$$

$$e = (p\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}G + q)\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}.$$

Therefore, we get

$$\|\bar{\Upsilon}v\|_{Y_\tau} \leq \ell.$$

Step 3: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ maps bounded sets into equi-continuous sets of Y_τ^0 .

Let B_r be the same as defined in Step 2. Let $0 \leq \nu_1 \leq \nu_2 \leq \tau$ for each $\nu \in B_r$, we obtain

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq \sum_{i=1}^4 \|C_i\|, \quad (4.3.10)$$

where

$$C_1 = \frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1 - s)^{\vartheta-1}] \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds; \quad (4.3.11)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds; \quad (4.3.12)$$

$$C_3 = \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s)] \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds; \quad (4.3.13)$$

$$C_4 = \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds. \quad (4.3.14)$$

Presently

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_1\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} [\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}(1+\mathcal{N}_k)(e+pr) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}] [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_2\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} [\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}(1+\mathcal{N}_k)(e+pr) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}] [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_3\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} [\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}(1+\mathcal{N}_k)(e+pr) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}] [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \|C_4\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} [\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}(1+\mathcal{N}_k)(e+pr) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{F}] [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.18)$$

By applying the continuity of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta$, we deduce that $\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_{Y_\tau^0} \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$.

Steps 1-3, along with the Arzela–Ascoli theorem [1.10.7], we conclude that the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is continuous and completely continuous.

Step 4: In what follows, we show that there exists an open set $\Omega \subseteq Y_\tau^0$ with $v \neq \lambda \bar{\Upsilon}v$ for $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and $v \in \partial\Omega$.

Let $v \in Y_\tau^0$ and $v = \lambda \bar{Y}v$ for some $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. Then, for each $t \in [0, \tau]$, we obtain

$$v(\alpha) = \lambda \left[\frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \right] \quad (4.3.19)$$

By assumptions (A1)(ii), (A2)(ii) and (A3), for each $t \in \mathcal{J}$, we get

$$\|v(\alpha)\| \\ \leq \left\| \frac{\mathbf{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \right\| \\ + \left\| \frac{\vartheta \mathbf{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \right\| \\ \leq \frac{\|\mathbf{S}\| \|\mathbf{T}\| (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s)\| ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \|\mathbf{S}^2\|}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\| \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s)\| ds \\ \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \left\{ \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} [\|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \mathcal{N}_k (1 + \|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}})] + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \right\} ds. \quad (4.3.20)$$

If we label $\beta(\alpha)$ the right-hand of (4.3.9), we get

$$\|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq \beta(\alpha).$$

Thus

$$\|v(\alpha)\| \\ \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \left\{ \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} [\beta(s) + \mathcal{N}_k (1 + \beta(s))] + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \right\} ds \\ \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} (1 + \mathcal{N}_k) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \beta(s) ds \\ + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} ds \\ \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} (1 + \mathcal{N}_k) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \beta(s) ds \\ + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\bar{\Lambda}_1 \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta}. \quad (4.3.21)$$

By the above inequality and the definition of β , we get

$$\begin{aligned}\beta(\alpha) &\leq e + p \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \\ &\quad + p \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1 + \mathcal{N}_k) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \beta(s) ds \\ &\leq \sigma(\alpha) + \theta \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \beta(s) ds,\end{aligned}\tag{4.3.22}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(\alpha) &= e + p \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta}; \\ \theta &= p \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1 + \mathcal{N}_k).\end{aligned}$$

Thus from Lemma 2.3 [89], we get

$$\beta(\alpha) \leq e^{\theta^n(\Gamma(\vartheta))^n \alpha^{n\vartheta}/\Gamma(n\vartheta)} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\theta\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)^j \sigma(\alpha) := \widetilde{M}, \quad \alpha \in \mathcal{J}.$$

Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\|v\|_{\mathcal{J}} &\leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1 + \mathcal{N}_k) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \widetilde{M} \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{D}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} = \mathcal{M}^*.\end{aligned}$$

Set

$$\Omega = \{v \in Y_\tau^0 : \|v\|_{Y_\tau^0} < \mathcal{M}^* + 1\}.$$

$\bar{\Upsilon} : \bar{\Omega} \rightarrow Y_\tau^0$ is continuous and completely continuous. From the choice of Ω , there is no $v \in \partial\Omega$ such that $v = \lambda\bar{\Upsilon}(v)$, $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. As a result of the nonlinear alternative of Leray-Schauder type [1.10.3], we conclude that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ has a fixed point in Ω . \square

4.4 Example

Consider the subsequent semi-linear functional differential equation of fractional order:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta z(\alpha, \kappa) &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \kappa^2} z(\alpha, \kappa) + a(\kappa)z(\alpha, \kappa) \\ &\quad + \int_0^\alpha \int_{-\infty}^s \bar{k}(\sigma - s, \zeta, \kappa) z(\sigma, \kappa) d\sigma ds, \quad 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau, 0 \leq \kappa \leq \pi,\end{aligned}\tag{4.4.1}$$

$$z(\alpha, 0) = z(\alpha, \pi) = 0, \alpha \in [0, \tau], \quad (4.4.2)$$

$$z(\theta, \kappa) = \varphi(\theta, \kappa), \theta \leq 0, \kappa \in [0, \pi]. \quad (4.4.3)$$

To write the system (4.4.1)-(4.4.3) in the form (4.1.1)-(4.1.2), we shall take $E = L^2[0, \pi]$ and define $w(\alpha)(\kappa) = z(\alpha, \kappa)$. Let $\mathcal{Q} : D(\mathcal{Q}) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ be an operator by $\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \Theta''$, $\Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q})$ with domain $D(\mathcal{Q}) = \{\Theta \in E; \Theta \text{ and } \Theta' \text{ are absolutely continuous, } \Theta'' \in E, \Theta(0) = \Theta(\pi) = 0\}$. Then

$$\mathcal{Q}\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \Theta \in D(\mathcal{Q}),$$

where $\Theta_n(s) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin(ns)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the orthonormal set of eigenvectors of \mathcal{Q} and \mathcal{Q} generates a C_0 semigroup $\{\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ in E which is given by

$$\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\alpha} \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \Theta \in E, \alpha > 0$$

which is uniformly bounded and also a compact semigroup and hence the operator $R(\lambda, \mathcal{Q}) = (\lambda I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ is compact for each $\lambda \in \rho(\mathcal{Q})$, i.e., $\mathcal{Q} \in \mathcal{A}^\theta(\beta_0, \Theta_0)$. We also obtain through the concept of subordination of the solution operator $\|\mathcal{B}_\theta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_\theta$ for each $\alpha \in [0, \pi]$. For more details, refer [72, 82].

For the phase space \mathcal{B} , we choose the well-known space $\mathcal{B} = C_r \times L^p(g; E)$, $r \geq 0$, $1 \leq p \leq \infty$, with $r = 0$, $p = 2$ and $E = L^2[0, \pi]$, which has been discussed in [87]. Assume that the following conditions hold:

- (i) The function $\bar{k}(\cdot)$ is measurable with $\int_{-\infty}^0 \left(\bar{k}^2(\theta)/g(\theta) \right) d\theta < \infty$.
- (ii) The function φ defined by $\varphi(\theta)(\kappa) = z(\theta, \kappa)$ belongs to \mathcal{B} .

Define the functions $k : \Delta \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ and $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{I} \times \mathcal{B} \times E \rightarrow E$ by

$$k(\alpha, s, \psi)(\kappa) = \int_{-\infty}^0 \bar{k}(\theta, \zeta, \kappa) \psi(\theta, \kappa) d\theta$$

$$\mathcal{F} \left(\alpha, \psi, \int_0^\alpha k(\alpha, s, \psi) ds \right) (\kappa) = a(\kappa) \psi(0, \kappa) + \int_0^\alpha k(\alpha, s, \psi)(\kappa) ds$$

The system (4.4.1)-(4.4.3) can be reduced into an abstract form (4.1.1)-(4.1.2) and it satisfied all conditions of Theorem 4.3.1. As a consequence, the system (4.4.1)-(4.4.3) has at least one mild solution on \mathcal{I} .

4.5 Existence Results for ABFSNIDE

This section is devoted to present and analyze the existence results for the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4).

Before we define the mild solution for the system, first we need to prove the following crucial Lemma.

In view of 1.11.2, we define the mild solution for the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4).

Definition 4.5.1. A function $w \in Y_\tau$ is a mild solution of (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) if $w_0 = \varphi \in \mathcal{B}$; the restriction of $w(\cdot)$ to the interval $\mathcal{J} = [0, \tau]$ is continuous; for each $0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau$, the function $\mathcal{G}(s, w_s)$, $s \in [0, \alpha]$, is integrable and satisfies the following integral equation

$$w(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)[\varphi(0) - \mathcal{G}(0, \varphi)] + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds \\ + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{G}(s, w_s) ds + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds \\ - \mathbb{S}\mathbb{T} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) \mathcal{G}(s, w_s) ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \end{cases} \quad (4.5.1)$$

where $\mathbb{S} = \zeta^*(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}\mathcal{Q}(\zeta^*I - \mathcal{Q})^{-1}$ with $\zeta^* = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$; $\mathcal{Q} = -\frac{B(\vartheta)\mathbb{T}}{\vartheta\mathbb{S}}$ and $\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)$; $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)$ are same as defined in (2.2.3) and (2.2.4) respectively.

Now, we frame the subsequent additional assumptions to analyze the given system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4).

(A4) The function $\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is continuous and we can find constants $\mathcal{N}_\mathcal{G}, \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{G}$ such that for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, $u, v \in \mathcal{B}$,

$$(A4)(i) \quad \|\mathcal{G}(\alpha, u) - \mathcal{G}(\alpha, v)\| \leq \mathcal{N}_\mathcal{G} \|u - v\|_\mathcal{B};$$

$$(A4)(ii) \quad \|\mathcal{G}(\alpha, u)\| \leq \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_\mathcal{G} (1 + \|u\|_\mathcal{B}).$$

With the help of Banach contraction theorem [1.10.1], in this section, first we establish the existence and uniqueness for the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4).

Theorem 4.5.1. If assumptions (A1)(i)-(A2)(i), (A3) and (A4)(i) are satisfied and

$$\frac{p\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{N}_\mathcal{F} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right) \mathcal{N}_\mathcal{G} \right] < 1, \quad (4.5.2)$$

then the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) has a unique mild solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$.

Proof. Consider the operator $\Upsilon_1 : Y_\tau \rightarrow Y_\tau$ defined by

$$(\Upsilon_1 w)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \leq 0, \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)[\varphi(0) - \mathcal{G}(0, \varphi)] + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds \\ + \frac{\mathbb{ST}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{G}(s, w_s) ds + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s) ds \\ - \mathbb{ST} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{G}(s, w_s) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases} \quad (4.5.3)$$

In view of (4.3.4), define the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}_1 : Y_\tau^0 \rightarrow Y_\tau^0$ as

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}_1 w)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} -\mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\mathcal{G}(0, \varphi) + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\mathbb{ST}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{G}(s, v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \\ - \mathbb{ST} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{G}(s, v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases} \quad (4.5.4)$$

Clearly the operator Υ_1 has a fixed point is equivalent to $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ has a fixed point, and so we turn to proving that $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ has a fixed point. Now, our purpose is to demonstrate that $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ is a contraction map of Y_τ^0 . Indeed, for every $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, $v, \bar{v} \in Y_\tau^0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}_1 v)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}_1 \bar{v})(\alpha)\| \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} \left[\|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left\| \int_0^s [k(s, \zeta, v_\zeta) - k(s, \zeta, \bar{v}_\zeta)] d\zeta \right\| \right] ds \\ & \quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}} \|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] \|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds \\ & \quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}} \|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] p \sup_{s \in [0, \tau]} \|v(s) - \bar{v}(s)\|_E ds \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}} p \sup_{s \in [0, \tau]} \|v(s) - \bar{v}(s)\|_E ds \\
&\leq \frac{p\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right) \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}} \right] \|v - \bar{v}\|_{Y_\tau^\vartheta}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
&\|(\bar{\Upsilon}_1 v) - (\bar{\Upsilon}_1 \bar{v})\|_{Y_\tau^\vartheta} \\
&\leq \frac{p\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{F}} [1 + \mathcal{N}_k] + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right) \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}} \right] \|v - \bar{v}\|_{Y_\tau^\vartheta}.
\end{aligned}$$

From (4.5.2), we see that $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ is a contraction. Hence the model (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) has a unique mild solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$. \square

Our second existence result is based on the Krasnoselskii-Schafer fixed point theorem [1.10.2].

In order to utilize this fixed point theorem, we need to split the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ which is same as defined in (4.5.4) as $\bar{\Upsilon}_2 + \bar{\Upsilon}_3$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{\Upsilon}_2 &= -\mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\mathcal{G}(0, \varphi) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{G}(s, v_s + u_s) ds \\
&\quad - \mathbb{S}\mathbb{T} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\mathcal{G}(s, v_s + u_s) ds
\end{aligned} \tag{4.5.5}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{\Upsilon}_3 &= \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds \\
&\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s, E_1 v_s + u_s) ds.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.5.6}$$

Next, we demonstrate that the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}_2$ and $\bar{\Upsilon}_3$ satisfies the assumptions of Krasnoselskii-Schafer fixed point theorem. To prove this, we prove the subsequent vital Lemma.

Lemma 4.5.1. *If assumptions (A1)(ii), (A2)(ii), (A3) and (A4)(i) are satisfied and*

$$\frac{p\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \right] < 1, \tag{4.5.7}$$

then $\bar{\Upsilon}_2$ is a contraction and $\bar{\Upsilon}_3$ is completely continuous.

Proof. By thinking of Theorem 4.3.2, we just note that the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}_3$ is completely continuous. Presently, we demonstrate that $\bar{\Upsilon}_2$ is a contraction on Y_τ^0 . For this, take $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, $v, \bar{v} \in Y_\tau^0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|(\bar{\Upsilon}_2 v)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}_2 \bar{v})(\alpha)\| &\leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}} \|v_s - \bar{v}_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds \\ &\leq \frac{p\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\right] \|v - \bar{v}\|_{Y_\tau^0}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}_2 v) - (\bar{\Upsilon}_2 \bar{v})\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq \frac{p\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{G}}\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\right] \|v - \bar{v}\|_{Y_\tau^0}.$$

□

From (4.5.7), we conclude that the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}_2$ is contraction on Y_τ^0 .

To discuss the the existence results for the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4), now, we treat the subsequent nonlinear operator equation

$$w(\alpha) = \lambda \Upsilon_1 w(\alpha), \quad 0 < \lambda < 1,$$

where Υ_1 is same as defined in Theorem 4.5.1. For the solution of the above equation, the accompanying Lemma provides an a priori approximation.

Lemma 4.5.2. *Assume that the assumptions (A1)(ii), (A2)(ii), (A3) and (A4)(ii) hold and there exists a constant $\mathcal{K} > 0$ such that $\|w_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq \mathcal{K}$, $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$.*

Proof. By using the assumptions (A1)(ii), (A2)(ii), (A3) and (A4)(ii), for each $\alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|w(\alpha)\| &\leq \|S\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| [\|\varphi(0)\| + \|\mathcal{G}(0, \varphi)\|] \\ &\quad + \frac{\|S\| \|\mathbf{T}\| (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s)\| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\|S\| \|\mathbf{T}\|}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{G}(s, w_s)\| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta \|S\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s)\| \|\mathcal{F}(s, w_s, E_1 w_s)\| ds \\ &\quad + \|S\| \|\mathbf{T}\| \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s)\| \|\mathcal{G}(s, w_s)\| ds \\ &\leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}[G\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}(1 + \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}})] + \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}(1 + \|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}}) ds \\ &\quad + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}(1 + \|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}}) ds \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
& (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \left\{ \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}[\|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \mathcal{N}_k(1+\|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}})] + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \right\} ds \\
& \leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}[G\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}(1+\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}})] + \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \right] \\
& + \left[\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \right] \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
& + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds \\
& + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1+\mathcal{N}_k) \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds \\
& \leq \mathcal{K}_0 + \mathcal{K}_1 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds,
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{K}_0 & = \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}[G\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}(1+\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}})] + \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}}\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \right] \\
& + \left[\widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}\mathcal{N}_k + \overline{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}} \right] \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right);
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\mathcal{K}_1 = \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{G}} \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \mu\bar{\mu}\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \right) + \widetilde{\mathcal{N}}_{\mathcal{F}}(1+\mathcal{N}_k) \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right).$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
\|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} & \leq p \sup\{\|w(s)\|_E : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha\} + q\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
& \leq q\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + p\mathcal{K}_0 + p\mathcal{K}_1 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} ds.
\end{aligned}$$

Let $\beta(\alpha) = \sup\{\|w_s\|_{\mathcal{B}} : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha\}$, then the function $\beta(\alpha)$ is non-decreasing in \mathcal{J} , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(\alpha) & \leq q\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + p\mathcal{K}_0 + p\mathcal{K}_1 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \beta(s) ds \\
& \leq \tilde{\sigma}(\alpha) + \tilde{\theta} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \beta(s) ds,
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha) = q\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + p\mathcal{K}_0; \quad \tilde{\theta} = p\mathcal{K}_1.$$

Thus from Lemma 2.3 [89], we get

$$\beta(\alpha) \leq e^{\tilde{\theta}^n (\Gamma(\vartheta))^n \alpha^{n\vartheta} / \Gamma(n\vartheta)} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\tilde{\theta} \tau^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right)^j \tilde{\sigma}(\alpha) := \mathcal{K}, \quad \alpha \in \mathcal{J},$$

which indicates the expected outcome. \square

Theorem 4.5.2. *Assume that the conditions of Lemma 4.5.1 and 4.5.2 hold. Then the model (4.1.3)-(4.1.4) has at least one mild solution on \mathcal{J} .*

Proof. Considering the following set

$$\mathcal{G}(\bar{\Upsilon}_1) = \left\{ v \in Y_\tau^0 : \lambda \bar{\Upsilon}_2 \left(\frac{v}{\lambda} \right) + \lambda \bar{\Upsilon}_3 v = v, \quad \text{for some } \lambda \in (0, 1) \right\}.$$

Next, for each $v \in \mathcal{G}(\bar{\Upsilon}_1)$, just from Lemma 4.5.2, we realize that $\|w_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq \mathcal{K}, \alpha \in \mathcal{J}$, and hence

$$\begin{aligned} \|v\|_{Y_\tau^0} &= \|v_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \sup \{ \|v(\alpha)\| : 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau \} \\ &= \sup \{ \|v(\alpha)\| : 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau \} \\ &\leq \sup \{ \|w(\alpha)\| : 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau \} + \sup \{ \|u(\alpha)\| : 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau \} \\ &\leq \sup \{ G \|w_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} : 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau \} + \sup \{ \|\mathbb{S}_{\mathcal{B}\vartheta}(\alpha)\varphi(0)\| : 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau \} \\ &\leq G\mathcal{K} + \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} G \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} = G(\mathcal{K} + \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}). \end{aligned}$$

From this, we notice that the set \mathcal{G} is bounded on \mathcal{J} . Therefore, from the Krasnoselskii-Schaefer type fixed point theorem [1.10.2], the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}_1$ has a fixed point $v^* \in Y_\tau^0$. Since, $w(\alpha) = v^* + u(\alpha), \alpha \in (-\infty, \tau]$, w is a fixed point of the operator Υ_1 which is a mild solution of the system (4.1.3)-(4.1.4). \square

Chapter 5

A NEW EXISTENCE RESULTS ON FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL INCLUSIONS WITH STATE-DEPENDENT DELAY AND MITTAG-LEFFLER KERNEL IN BANACH SPACE

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we establish the existence of mild solutions of ABFFDI with SDD of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} p(\alpha) \in Ap(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, p_{\sigma(\alpha, p_{\alpha})}), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau] \quad (5.1.1)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (5.1.2)$$

where $\tau > 0, \vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, \mathcal{F} is a set-valued map and $\sigma : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow (-\infty, \tau]$ are given functions that satisfy a later-specified assumption.

We assume that $p_{\alpha} : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, p_{\alpha}(x) = p(\alpha + x), x \leq 0$, belongs to an abstract phase space \mathcal{B} .

Fractional differential equations, general enhancement of classical ordinary and partial differential equations which allows the real (or) even complex number to be its order of differentiation. The main benefits of employing the fractional derivatives is their ability to record their hereditary property of various processes which is mainly because of the non-locality nature of the operators. The hereditary property of fractional derivatives allows one to model the materials with intermediate properties such as viscoelasticity of

the substances. The greatest breakthrough in the field of fractional differential equation found in its application in the abundant fields of diverse nature such as circuits in electrical engineering, control theory, statistical modeling, the vibration of earthquake motions and so on. Many excellent monographs were available which provides the essential conceptual tools to explore more hidden applications of fractional differential equations. Similarly, one can locate the distinguish properties of both classical and fractional differential representations, we refer to the monographs [19, 106] and the related research articles of fractional differential systems are given in [5, 13, 14, 17, 75, 82, 89, 111].

In recent times, by noticing the aforementioned peculiar properties and wide applicability of fractional derivatives in various scientific fields, it became handy and more applicable to model the real world problems. The essential thing to note is that the applications and outcomes of fractional derivatives and integrals differ depending on the definitions used, such as Riemann-Liouville, Hadamard, Grunwald Letnikov, Caputo, Riesz-Caputo, Chen, Weyl, Erd Iyi-Kober, and so on. In 2015, Caputo and Fabrizio [39] proposed the recent definition of non local derivatives with non-singular kernel in the non-necessarily Banach space \mathcal{H}^1 . This concept posed a significant barrier to its implementation, but it rapidly made its way into a variety of fields, including thermal science and mechanical engineering, as well as groundwater research, see [11, 30, 31] for further information, as well as the references therein. A year later, the new definition of non-local derivatives with non singular kernel based on the Mittag-Leffler function was proposed by Atangana and Baleanu. The current concept confirmed the Caputo-Fabrizio's concept which is depends on exponential function. Atanganu-Baleanu definition achieved important applications in various fields established by the togetherness of strong relationship in among fractional calculus and Mittag-Leffler function. For more reference, the readers can see [9, 17, 19, 85].

In [51, 52], Gautam and Dabas proved the existence of mild solutions for fractional integro-differential equations with SDD by using the applicable fixed point theorem. In [44, 103], Das et al. investigated the class of second order partial neutral differential equations with SDD in Banach spaces and proved the existence of mild solution for the considered system along with the help of Hausdorff measures of non-compactness and Darbo fixed point theorem. In [113], the authors researched the abstract fractional integro-

differential inclusions with infinite state-dependent delay in Banach spaces. In [114], the authors studied the fractional neutral differential systems with SDD in Banach spaces under non-compactness measure and showed its existence via contractive and condensing maps. In recent times, Aiemene et al. [9] studied the controllability results for fractional order semilinear differential equations with impulses having finite delay in Banach spaces. Recently, Mallika Arjunan et al. [90, 91] analyzed the existence results of various fractional differential systems through A-B derivative under suitable fixed point theorem. To the best of our knowledge, there is no results reported on the existence results for ABFFDI with SDD in \mathcal{B} phase space contexts. This encouraged us to investigate the existence results of the system (5.1.1) -(5.1.2) with SDD in Banach spaces. The existence findings for (5.1.1)-(5.1.2) are presented for the first time in this work.

Now we will move on to a description of the work. We give some fundamental concepts on A-B fractional derivatives and phase space axioms (\mathcal{B}) in Section 5.2. The proof of our main findings and an example are given in Section 5.3.

5.2 Preliminaries

This part covers the fundamental definitions and results of the sectorial operator, set-valued mappings, measures of non-compactness [MNC], phase space axioms, and A-B fractional derivative, which will aid us in proving our key conclusions.

Let $(E, \|\cdot\|_E)$ be a complex Banach space. $L(E)$ is the Banach space of all bounded linear operators from X into X with $\|\cdot\|_{L(E)}$ as the corresponding norm.

$\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)$ is the Banach space of all continuous functions from $[0, \tau]$ into E with the norm $\|p\|_{\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)} = \sup\{\|p(\alpha)\| : \alpha \in [0, \tau]\}$.

The functions $p : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ that are integrable in the Bochner notion with regard to the Lebesgue measure, equipped with

$$\|p\|_1 = \int_0^\tau \|p(x)\| dx$$

is denoted by $L^1([0, \tau], E)$.

For basic definitions of fractional and A-B fractional derivative, we suggest the reader to refer 1.11.1.

5.2.1 Set-valued maps and MNC

Assume that Θ is a metric space. All through this work, $\mathcal{P}(\Theta)$ denotes a list of all nonempty subsets of Θ , whereas $\mathcal{P}_b(\Theta)$ denotes a list of all bounded nonempty subsets of Θ .

The idea of measure of non-compactness underpins several of our findings. With this purpose, we will remember a some characteristics of this idea next. As for basic information, the reader will refer [29, 46, 77, 113]. We just use Hausdorff measure of non-compactness [HMNC] concept throughout this chapter.

Definition 5.2.1 ([29, 46] (HMNC)). *Let \mathcal{U} be a family of bounded subset of Θ . Then HMNC is described by*

$$\beta(\mathcal{U}) := \inf\{\mu > 0 : \mathcal{U} = \cup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{U}_i \text{ with } \text{diam}(\mathcal{U}_i) \leq \mu \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, k\}.$$

Lemma 5.2.1 ([29, 46]). *For any bounded sets $\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{U}_1$ and \mathcal{U}_2 of Θ , we obtain*

- (i) $\beta(\mathcal{U}) = 0$ iff \mathcal{U} is totally bounded;
- (ii) $\beta(\mathcal{U}) = \beta(\overline{\mathcal{U}})$, where $\overline{\mathcal{U}}$ means the closure of \mathcal{U} ;
- (iii) For each $\mathcal{U}_1 \subset \mathcal{U}_2$ implies $\beta(\mathcal{U}_1) \leq \beta(\mathcal{U}_2)$;
- (iv) $\beta(\mathcal{U}_1 + \mathcal{U}_2) \leq \beta(\mathcal{U}_1) + \beta(\mathcal{U}_2)$;
- (v) $\beta(\mathcal{U}_1 \cup \mathcal{U}_2) = \max\{\beta(\mathcal{U}_1), \beta(\mathcal{U}_2)\}$;
- (vi) $\beta(\lambda\mathcal{U}) = |\lambda|\beta(\mathcal{U})$ for any $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (vii) $\beta(\mathcal{U}) = \beta(\overline{\text{co}}(\mathcal{U}))$.

Let \mathcal{Y} be a normed space. In order to signify the subsequent set listing, we now utilizing the terminology $\nu(\mathcal{Y})$ and $\mathcal{M}\nu(\mathcal{Y})$:

- (i) $\nu(\mathcal{Y}) = \{\mathcal{D} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y}) : \mathcal{D} \text{ is convex}\}$;
- (ii) $\mathcal{M}\nu(\mathcal{Y}) = \{\mathcal{D} \in \nu(\mathcal{Y}) : \mathcal{D} \text{ is compact}\}$.

Definition 5.2.2. *A condensing map with regard to η (abbreviated, η -condensing) is a set-valued map $\Upsilon : \Theta \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Y})$ if for any bounded set $\mathcal{D} \subset \Theta$, $\eta(\mathcal{D}) > 0$, $\eta(\Upsilon(\mathcal{D})) < \eta(\mathcal{D})$.*

Remark 5.2.1. *We can see that Υ is closed if $\Upsilon : \Theta \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\nu(\mathcal{Y})$ is u.s.c.*

Theorem 5.2.1 ([Corollary 3.3.1], [77]). *Suppose $\Upsilon : \mathcal{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\nu(\mathcal{N})$ is a upper semi-continuous β -condensing multivalued map, then $\text{Fix}(\Upsilon) = \{z \in \Upsilon(z)\}$ is a nonempty compact set, where \mathcal{N} be a convex closed subset of \mathcal{Y} .*

Now, we collect some measure β properties from [113, Lemma 2.1-2.4] that will be used to verify our key findings. We call a set $\Omega \subseteq L^1([0, \tau], E)$ is uniformly integrable if $\gamma > 0 \in L^1([0, \tau])$ in a way that $\|p(\alpha)\| \leq \gamma(\alpha)$ a.e. for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$ and all $p \in \Omega$.

5.2.2 Phase space axioms

To employ delay criteria, we must first establish the phase space axioms \mathcal{B} introduced by Hale and Kato in [63] and utilize the terminology used in [72]. As a result, $(\mathcal{B}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{B}})$ is a semi-normed linear space of functions mapping $(-\infty, 0]$ into E and satisfying the axioms below.

If $p :]-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E, \tau > 0$, is such that $p_0 \in \mathcal{B}$, then for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, the subsequent assumptions hold:

(C1) $p_\alpha \in \mathcal{B}$,

(C2) $\|p_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq Q_1(\alpha) \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \alpha} \|p(x)\| + Q_2(\alpha) \|p_0\|_{\mathcal{B}}$,

(C3) $\|p(\alpha)\| \leq \bar{W} \|p_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}}$, where $\bar{W} > 0$ is a constant and $Q_1 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous, $Q_2 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is locally bounded, and Q_1, Q_2 are independent of $p(\cdot)$. Furthermore, $\|\varphi(0)\| \leq \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}$ for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{B}$.

(C4) p_α is a \mathcal{B} -valued continuous function on $[0, \tau]$ and \mathcal{B} is complete. For more details, see [62].

Now, we define the space

$$Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E) = \{\kappa \in \mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E) : \kappa(0) = \varphi(0)\}.$$

For more details on phase space axioms and its examples, we suggest the reader to refer [62, 72, 87].

5.3 Existence Results

The existence findings for the inclusions (5.1.1)-(5.1.2) under contractive and condensing maps are presented and proved in this part.

We begin by imposing some appropriate constraints on the set-valued map \mathcal{F} .

$\mathcal{F}(i)$ For any $\omega \in \mathcal{B}$, the function $\mathcal{F}(\cdot, \omega) : [0, \tau] \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\nu(E)$ permits a strongly measurable selection.

$\mathcal{F}(ii)$ The function $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \cdot) : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\nu(E)$ is upper semi-continuous for every $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$.

$\mathcal{F}(iii)$ We can find a function $\gamma \in L^1([0, \tau])$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega)\| := \sup\{\|f\| : f \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega)\} \leq \gamma(\alpha)\Phi(\|\omega\|_{\mathcal{B}}), \quad \text{a.e. } \alpha \in [0, \tau],$$

where $\Phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous non-decreasing function.

In addition, we suppose that $\sigma : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous function such that $\sigma(\alpha, \omega) \leq \alpha$ for all $\alpha \geq 0$ and $\omega \in \mathcal{B}$.

Remark 5.3.1. In view of $\mathcal{F}(i)$ and $\mathcal{F}(ii)$, we notice that the set

$$\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa} = \{p \in L^1([0, \tau], E) : p(\alpha) \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\sigma(\alpha, \kappa_\alpha)})\} \neq \emptyset,$$

and $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa}$ is convex.

In view of 1.11.2, we can now describe the mild solution for the inclusions (5.1.1)-(5.1.2).

Definition 5.3.1. A function $\kappa : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is called a mild solution of the inclusions (5.1.1)-(5.1.2) if the subsequent holds: $p_0 = \varphi \in \mathcal{B}$ on $(-\infty, 0]$, the restriction of $\kappa(\cdot)$ to the interval $[0, \tau]$ is continuous and satisfies the following integral equation:

$$\kappa(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} p(s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)p(s) ds, & p \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa}, \text{ and all } \alpha \in [0, \tau], \end{cases} \quad (5.3.1)$$

where $\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}A(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{x\alpha} x^{\vartheta-1} (x^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} dx, \quad (5.3.2)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta,\vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{x\alpha} (x^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} dx, \quad (5.3.3)$$

Γ denotes the Bromwich path [24].

To establish our findings, we must examine an integral operator given on the set $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}$ for functions $\kappa \in Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E)$. We begin by discussing the characteristics of $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}$. The first outcome determines that $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}$ is closed. In specific, we recall the property from [113, Lemma 3.1].

Just from the other side, as a result of \mathcal{F} (iii), the set $\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}$ is uniformly integrable on $[0, \tau]$, i.e., we can find a function $\gamma_{\sigma,\kappa} > 0 \in L^1([0, \tau])$ in ways that $\|p(\alpha)\| \leq \gamma_{\sigma,\kappa}(\alpha)$ a.e. for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$ and all $p \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}$.

We introduce now the operator $\bar{\Upsilon} : L^1([0, \tau], E) \rightarrow \mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)$ given by

$$\bar{\Upsilon}p(\alpha) = \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} p(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) p(s) ds.$$

This is obvious that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is a bounded linear operator. With the use of $\bar{\Upsilon}$, we may develop the set-valued map $\tilde{\Upsilon} : Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E) \rightarrow \nu(\mathcal{C}([0, \tau]; E))$ given by

$$\tilde{\Upsilon}(\kappa) = \bar{\Upsilon}(\Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}).$$

Based on the above discussions, now, we state the following crucial lemma from [113, Lemma 3.2].

Lemma 5.3.1. *Consider a set-valued map $\mathcal{F} : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\nu(E)$ and suppose \mathcal{F} satisfies \mathcal{F} (i) – \mathcal{F} (iii). Then $\tilde{\Upsilon}$ is a upper semi-continuous map with convex compact values.*

First, we characterize the solution map for the system (5.1.1)-(5.1.2) as below.

Let $\kappa \in Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E)$. For simplicity, we described $\kappa(\cdot)$ with its extension to $(-\infty, \tau]$ supplied by $\kappa(y) = \varphi(y)$ for all $y \leq 0$. Utilizing this terminology, $\Upsilon^*(\tau)$ is defined as the set generated by all z functions given by

$$\begin{aligned} z(\alpha) &= \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} p(s) ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) p(s) ds, \quad p \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F},\sigma,\kappa}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.3.4)$$

Through our assumptions, it indicates that $z \in Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E)$. Hence, $\Upsilon^* : Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E))$. Moreover, it is obvious that $\kappa(\cdot)$ is a mild solution of the inclusions (5.1.1)-(5.1.2) if and only if $\kappa(\cdot)$ is a fixed point of Υ^* .

Our existence result is based on the contractive maps. $\mathcal{P}_{cb}(E)$ denotes the listing of closed bounded subsets of E and by $d_{\mathcal{H}}$ the Hausdorff metric in $\mathcal{P}_{cb}(E)$.

Theorem 5.3.1. *Assume that assumptions $\mathcal{F}(i), \mathcal{F}(iii)$ are satisfied. Further, suppose that the subsequent assumptions hold:*

(A1) *We can find a constant $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} > 0$ such that*

$$d_{\mathcal{H}}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_1), \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_2)) \leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \|\omega_1 - \omega_2\|_{\mathcal{B}}$$

for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$ and all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \mathcal{B}$.

(A2) *We can find a positive function $\tilde{\sigma} \in L^1([0, \tau])$ and every $Q > 0$, there exists a positive constant $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) > 0$ such that*

$$d_{\mathcal{H}}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_2}), \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_1})) \leq \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \tilde{\sigma}(\alpha) |\alpha_2 - \alpha_1|,$$

for all $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in [0, \tau]$ and $\kappa : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ such that $\kappa_0 \in \mathcal{B}, \kappa : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is continuous, and $\max_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} \|\kappa_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq Q$.

(A3) *There is a constant $\mathcal{L}_\sigma > 0$ such that*

$$|\sigma(\alpha, \omega_1) - \sigma(\alpha, \omega_2)| \leq \mathcal{L}_\sigma \|\omega_1 - \omega_2\|_{\mathcal{B}}, \omega_1, \omega_2 \in \mathcal{B}.$$

(A4) *There exist constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$ for the bounded linear operators \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} .*

If there exists $Q > 0$ in ways that

$$(Q_1^* \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{W} + Q_2^*) \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + Q_1^* \gamma^* \Phi(Q) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^\vartheta \leq Q, \quad (5.3.5)$$

and

$$\left[Q_1^* \left[\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \mathcal{L}_\sigma \tilde{\sigma}^* \right] \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^\vartheta \right] < 1, \quad (5.3.6)$$

where $Q_1^ = \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} Q_1(x)$ and $Q_2^* = \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} Q_2(x)$, then there exists a mild solution of the inclusions (5.1.1)-(5.1.2).*

Proof. In view of Lemma 5.3.1 and our assumptions that Υ^* is upper semi-continuous set-valued map with convex compact values.

Let $B_Q = \{\kappa \in Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E) : \|\kappa_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq Q, 0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$. It is obvious that B_Q is a complete metric space. Furthermore, $\Upsilon^* \kappa \subseteq B_Q$ for all $\kappa \in B_Q$. As a matter of truth, if $z(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \bar{\Upsilon}p(\alpha)$, for $p \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa}$, and denote $\gamma^* = \sup_{0 < s < \tau} \gamma(s)$, it follows from $\mathcal{F}(iii)$ that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|z(\alpha)\| \\
&= \left\| \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\Gamma(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} p(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)p(s) ds \right\| \\
&\leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|p(s)\| ds \\
&\leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \gamma(s) \Phi(\|\kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s)}\|_{\mathcal{B}}) ds \\
&\leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \gamma^* \Phi(Q) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} ds \\
&\leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \gamma^* \Phi(Q) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \\
&= \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \gamma^* \Phi(Q) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^\vartheta
\end{aligned}$$

which suggest that

$$\begin{aligned}
\|z_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} &\leq Q_1^* \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \gamma^* \Phi(Q) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^\vartheta \right] + Q_2^* \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&\leq (Q_1^* \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \bar{W} + Q_2^*) \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + Q_1^* \gamma^* \Phi(Q) \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^\vartheta
\end{aligned}$$

and utilizing (5.3.5), we get the affirmation.

Next we demonstrate that a contraction map is defined by Υ^* described on B_Q .

Indeed, let $\kappa^\ell \in B_Q$, $z^\ell \in \Upsilon^* \kappa^\ell$, $z^\ell(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \bar{\Upsilon}p^\ell(\alpha)$, for $\ell = 1, 2$. We can use [113, Lemma 3.3] to find out if there are any $p^2 \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa^2}$ that fulfills

$$\|p^1(s) - p^2(s)\| = d\left(p^1(s), \mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^2)}^2\right)\right), \quad \text{a. e.}$$

This means that

$$\begin{aligned}
& d(z^1, \Upsilon^* \kappa^2) \\
&= \inf_{p^2 \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa^2}} \|\bar{\Upsilon}(p^1 - p^2)\| \\
&\leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \inf_{p^2 \in \Upsilon_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa^2}} \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|p^1(s) - p^2(s)\| ds \\
&\leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \sup_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|p^1(s) - p^2(s)\| ds. \tag{5.3.7}
\end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
d\left(p^1(s), \mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^2)}^2\right)\right) &\leq d_{\mathcal{H}}\left(\mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^1\right), \mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^2\right)\right) \\
&\quad + d_{\mathcal{H}}\left(\mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^2\right), \mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^2)}^2\right)\right) \\
&\leq \sum_{i=1}^2 I_i, \tag{5.3.8}
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= d_{\mathcal{H}}\left(\mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^1\right), \mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^2\right)\right); \\
I_2 &= d_{\mathcal{H}}\left(\mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^2\right), \mathcal{F}\left(s, \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^2)}^2\right)\right).
\end{aligned}$$

By using the assumption (A1), we can find the estimation of I_1 as

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &\leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \left\| \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^1 - \kappa_{\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)}^2 \right\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&\leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} Q_1(\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)) \max_{0 \leq \mu^* \leq \sigma(s, \kappa_s^1)} \|\kappa^1(\mu^*) - \kappa^2(\mu^*)\| \\
&\leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} Q_1^* \max_{0 \leq \mu^* \leq s} \|\kappa^1(\mu^*) - \kappa^2(\mu^*)\|. \tag{5.3.9}
\end{aligned}$$

By utilizing the assumptions (A2)-(A3), we can find the estimation of I_2 as

$$\begin{aligned}
I_2 &\leq \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \tilde{\sigma}(s) |\sigma(s, \kappa_s^1) - \sigma(s, \kappa_s^2)| \\
&\leq \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \tilde{\sigma}(s) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma} \|\kappa_s^1 - \kappa_s^2\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&\leq \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \tilde{\sigma}(s) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma} Q_1^* \max_{0 \leq \mu^* \leq s} \|\kappa^1(\mu^*) - \kappa^2(\mu^*)\| \\
&\leq \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \tilde{\sigma}^* \mathcal{L}_{\sigma} Q_1^* \max_{0 \leq \mu^* \leq s} \|\kappa^1(\mu^*) - \kappa^2(\mu^*)\|, \tag{5.3.10}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}^* = \sup_{0 < s < \tau} \tilde{\sigma}(s)$.

By substituting the equations (5.3.9) and (5.3.10) in (5.3.8), we obtain

$$\|p^1(s) - p^2(s)\| \leq Q_1^* \left[\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma} \tilde{\sigma}^* \right] \max_{0 \leq \mu^* \leq s} \|\kappa^1(\mu^*) - \kappa^2(\mu^*)\|. \quad (5.3.11)$$

By substituting the equation (5.3.11) in (5.3.7), we get

$$d(z^1, \Upsilon^* \kappa^2) \leq \left[Q_1^* \left[\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma} \tilde{\sigma}^* \right] \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^{\vartheta} \right] \|\kappa^1 - \kappa^2\|_{\infty}.$$

Continuing to estimate $d(z^2, \Upsilon^* \kappa^1)$ as above, and applying that

$$d_{\mathcal{H}}(\Upsilon^* \kappa^1, \Upsilon^* \kappa^2) = \max \left\{ \sup_{z^1 \in \Upsilon^* \kappa^1} d(z^1, \Upsilon^* \kappa^2), \sup_{z^2 \in \Upsilon^* \kappa^2} d(z^2, \Upsilon^* \kappa^1) \right\},$$

we come to the conclusion that

$$d(\Upsilon^* \kappa^1, \Upsilon^* \kappa^2) \leq \left[Q_1^* \left[\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} + \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma} \tilde{\sigma}^* \right] \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \tau^{\vartheta} \right] d(\kappa^1, \kappa^2).$$

As a result, by (5.3.6), the map Υ^* is a contraction on B_Q . From [60, Theorem 1.2.3.1], we realize that the operator Υ^* has a fixed point $\kappa \in B_Q$. \square

Example 5.3.1.

We develop a class of functions \mathcal{F} in this illustration that fulfill all of the previous assumptions. Consider the phase space $\mathcal{B} = C_0 \times L^q(g, E)$, $1 < q < \infty$ as described in [113, Example 2.1]. Let \tilde{q} be the conjugate exponent of q .

Define a function $\mathcal{F}_0 : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ by

$$\mathcal{F}_0(\alpha, \omega) = \tilde{\sigma}(\alpha) \widetilde{W} \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \omega(\eta) d\eta \right), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \quad \omega \in \mathcal{B},$$

where $\tilde{\sigma} \in L^1([0, \tau])$, $\widetilde{W} : E \rightarrow E$ is a map that fulfills the Lipschitz assumption

$$\|\widetilde{W}(u) - \widetilde{W}(v)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_{\widetilde{W}} \|u - v\|, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\widetilde{W}} \geq 0; \quad u, v \in E$$

and $e : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow (-\infty, 0)$ is a function that fulfills the assumptions:

(i) Let $e \in \mathcal{C}^1$ and $\mathcal{L}_e^1 : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous function such that

$$|e'(\eta)| \leq \mathcal{L}_e^1(s), \quad \eta \leq s \leq 0, \text{ and}$$

$$\nu^1 = \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{|\mathcal{L}_e^1(\eta)|^{\tilde{q}}}{g(\eta)^{\tilde{q}-1}} d\eta \right)^{1/\tilde{q}} < \infty.$$

$$(ii) \nu = \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{|e(\eta)|^{\tilde{q}}}{g(\eta)^{\tilde{q}-1}} d\eta \right)^{1/\tilde{q}} < \infty.$$

We describe $\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ by

$$\mathcal{G}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta)\omega(\eta)d\eta.$$

Given (ii), we may deduce that $\mathcal{G}(\omega)$ is properly described and

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{G}(\omega)\| &\leq \int_{-\infty}^0 |e(\eta)|\|\omega(\eta)\|d\eta \\ &\leq \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{|e(\eta)|}{g(\eta)^{1/q}} g(\eta)^{1/q} \|\omega(\eta)\|d\eta \\ &\leq \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{|e(\eta)|^{\tilde{q}}}{g(\eta)^{\tilde{q}/q}} d\eta \right)^{1/\tilde{q}} \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 g(\eta)\|\omega(\eta)\|^q d\eta \right)^{1/q} \\ &\leq \nu\|\omega\|_{\mathcal{B}}. \end{aligned}$$

Assume that $\mathcal{C} \subseteq E$ is a convex compact set with $0 \in \mathcal{C}$. Further, we describe

$$\mathcal{F}(z, \omega) = \mathcal{F}_0(\alpha, \omega) + \mathcal{C}, \alpha \in [0, \tau], \omega \in \mathcal{B}.$$

From this, we notice that \mathcal{F} fulfills $\mathcal{F}(i)$. Utilizing [46, Proposition 1.1], we can see that \mathcal{F} is upper semi-continuous implying that \mathcal{F} satisfies $\mathcal{F}(ii)$. Further,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega)\| &= \sup\{\|\nu\| : \nu \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega)\} \leq \|\mathcal{F}_0(\alpha, \omega)\| + \sup_{\kappa \in \mathcal{C}} \|\kappa\| \\ &\leq |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)| \left[\mathcal{L}_{\tilde{W}}\nu\|\omega\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \|\tilde{W}(0)\| \right] + \sup_{\kappa \in \mathcal{C}} \|\kappa\| \\ &\leq \gamma(\alpha)\Phi(\|\omega\|_{\mathcal{B}}), \text{ a.e. } \alpha \in [0, \tau], \omega \in \mathcal{B}, \end{aligned}$$

thinking $\gamma = |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)| \in L^1([0, \tau])$ and a continuous function $\Phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, described by

$$\Phi(\alpha) = \left[\mathcal{L}_{\tilde{W}}\nu\|\omega\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \|\tilde{W}(0)\| \right] + |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)|^{-1} \sup_{\kappa \in \mathcal{C}} \|\kappa\|.$$

This delivers that \mathcal{F} fulfills the assumption $\mathcal{F}(iii)$.

Next, we show that \mathcal{F} fulfills the assumptions (A1) and (A2). Since

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathcal{H}}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_1), \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_2)) &\leq \|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_1) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_2)\| \\ &\leq |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)| \mathcal{L}_{\tilde{W}}\nu \|\omega_1 - \omega_2\|_{\mathcal{B}}. \end{aligned}$$

From this, we conclude that \mathcal{F} fulfills (A1). Let $\kappa : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ be a function such that $\kappa_0 = \varphi, \kappa : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is continuous, and $\|\kappa_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq Q$ for all $0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau$. Taking $0 \leq \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 \leq \tau$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & d_{\mathcal{H}}(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_2}), \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_1})) \\ & \leq |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)| \|\mathcal{F}_0(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_2}) - \mathcal{F}_0(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_1})\| \\ & \leq |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)| \mathcal{L}_{\overline{W}} \left\| \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \kappa(\alpha_2 + \eta) d\eta - \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \kappa(\alpha_1 + \eta) d\eta \right\|. \end{aligned} \quad (5.3.12)$$

Moreover, since

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \kappa(\alpha_2 + \eta) d\eta - \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \kappa(\alpha_1 + \eta) d\eta \\ & = \int_{-\infty}^{\alpha_2} e(s - \alpha_2) \kappa(s) ds - \int_{-\infty}^{\alpha_1} e(s - \alpha_1) \kappa(s) ds \\ & = \int_{-\infty}^0 [e(s - \alpha_2) - e(s - \alpha_1)] \varphi(s) ds + \int_0^{\alpha_1} [e(s - \alpha_2) - e(s - \alpha_1)] \kappa(s) ds \\ & \quad + \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_2} e(s - \alpha_2) \kappa(s) ds \end{aligned}$$

and using (i) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \kappa(\alpha_2 + \eta) d\eta - \int_{-\infty}^0 e(\eta) \kappa(\alpha_1 + \eta) d\eta \right\| \\ & \leq \left(\nu^1 + \mathcal{L}_e^1(0)\tau + \overline{W} \sup_{-\tau \leq \eta \leq 0} |e(\eta)| \right) (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) Q. \end{aligned} \quad (5.3.13)$$

From (5.3.12) and (5.3.13) we infer that (A2) is fulfilled.

Further, in this section, as an application on Theorem 5.3.1, we consider the following system

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta p(\alpha) = Ap(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, p_{\sigma(\alpha, p_\alpha)}), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau] \quad (5.3.14)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (5.3.15)$$

Here, the function $\mathcal{F} : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is single-valued. The other functions are identical to those specified in (5.1.1)-(5.1.2).

The subsequent conclusion can be drawn as a result of Theorem 5.3.1.

Corollary 5.3.1. *Let assumptions (A3)-(A4) be hold. In addition, we assume that the following assumptions are fulfilled:*

(i) For every $\omega \in \mathcal{B}$, $\mathcal{F}(\cdot, \omega) : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is strongly measurable.

(ii) We can find a constant $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} > 0$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_1) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega_2)\| \leq \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{F}} \|\omega_1 - \omega_2\|_{\mathcal{B}}$$

for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$ and all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in \mathcal{B}$.

(iii) We can find a positive function $\tilde{\sigma} \in L^1([0, \tau])$ and every $Q > 0$, there exists a positive constant $\widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) > 0$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_2}) - \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa_{\alpha_1})\| \leq \widetilde{\mathcal{L}}_{\mathcal{F}}(Q) \tilde{\sigma}(\alpha) |\alpha_2 - \alpha_1|$$

for all $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in [0, \tau]$ and $\kappa : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ such that $\kappa_0 \in \mathcal{B}$, $\kappa : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is continuous, and $\max_{0 \leq \alpha \leq \tau} \|\kappa_{\alpha}\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq Q$.

(iv) We can find a function $\gamma \in L^1([0, \tau])$ such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \omega)\| \leq \gamma(\alpha) \Phi(\|\omega\|_{\mathcal{B}}), \quad \text{a.e. } \alpha \in [0, \tau], \omega \in \mathcal{B},$$

where $\Phi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous non-decreasing function.

If assumptions (5.3.5) and (5.3.6) are fulfilled, a unique mild solution to the system (5.3.14)-(5.3.15) is available.

We can now prove the section's main result without the assumptions (5.3.5) and (5.3.6).

Theorem 5.3.2. Assume that assumptions $\mathcal{F}(i) - \mathcal{F}(iii)$ are satisfied. In addition, we also assume that the subsequent assumption holds.

$\mathcal{F}(iv)$ Let $u(\cdot)$ be a positive integrable function on $[0, \tau]$ in ways that

$$\chi(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, V_s)) \leq u(\alpha) \sup_{0 \leq x \leq s} \chi(\{\kappa(x) : \kappa \in Q\}), \quad \text{a.e. } \alpha \in [0, \tau]$$

for all bounded sets $V \subseteq Y_{\varphi}([0, \tau], E)$, where $V_x = \{\kappa_x : \kappa \in V\}$.

If

$$\left[2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \left(\int_0^{\tau} (\tau - s)^{\vartheta-1} u(s) ds \right) \right] < 1, \quad (5.3.16)$$

then $\Upsilon^* : Y_{\varphi}([0, \tau], E) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}\nu(Y_{\varphi}([0, \tau], E))$ given by (5.3.4) is upper semi-continuous and β -condensing.

Proof. According to our hypothesis, the operator Υ^* is a upper semi-continuous set-valued map with convex compact values. Demonstrating that Υ^* is β -condensing is still required. Let $K \subset Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E)$ be a bounded set such that $\beta(\Upsilon^*(K)) \geq \beta(K)$. In view of [67, Lemma 2.9], we can find a sequence $(z^n)_n$ in $\Upsilon^*(K)$ such that $\beta(\Upsilon^*(K)) = \beta(\{z^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\})$. We may write $z^n \in \Upsilon^* \kappa^n$, for some $\kappa^n \in K$.

Utilizing (5.3.4), we can calculate $\beta(\{z^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\})$, we have

$$z^n(\alpha) = \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \Xi(p^n)(\alpha),$$

where

$$\Xi(p^n)(\alpha) = \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} p^n(s) ds + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) p^n(s) ds$$

for $p^n \in \Upsilon^*_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa^n}$.

Then, we obtain

$$\beta(\{z^n(\cdot) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) \leq \beta(\{\Xi(p^n)(\cdot) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}).$$

Since $p^n \in \Upsilon^*_{\mathcal{F}, \sigma, \kappa^n}$, for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we obtain $p^n(\alpha) \in \mathcal{F}(\alpha, \kappa^n_{\sigma(\alpha, \kappa^n_\alpha)})$. Thus $\{p^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is uniformly integrable and from $\mathcal{F}(iv)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(\{p^n(\alpha) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) &\leq u(\alpha) \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \sigma(\alpha, \kappa^n_\alpha)} \chi(\{\kappa^n(x) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) \\ &\leq u(\alpha) \beta(\{\kappa^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}). \end{aligned}$$

We may deduce from this estimation and from [77] that

$$\begin{aligned} &\beta(\{\Xi(p^n)(\cdot) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) \\ &\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \beta(\{\kappa^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) \int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} u(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, after compiling these information, we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(K) &\leq \beta(\Upsilon^*(K)) \\ &= \beta(\{z^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) \\ &\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \left(\int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} u(s) ds \right) \beta(\{\kappa^n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}) \\ &= \left[2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \left(\int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} u(s) ds \right) \right] \beta(K). \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\beta(K) \left[1 - 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{F}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \left(\int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} u(s) ds \right) \right] \leq 0.$$

From (5.3.16), we conclude that $\beta(K) = 0$ and hence Υ^* is a β -condensing map. The proof is now completed. \square

Example 5.3.2.

Now, we need to prove that the function \mathcal{F} fulfills $\mathcal{F}(iv)$. For this, by thinking of Example 5.3.1, assume $V \subseteq Y_\varphi([0, \tau], E)$ be a bounded set and $V_s = \{\kappa_s : \kappa \in V\}$. Using the characteristics stated in preliminaries, it is easy to demonstrate that

$$\chi(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, V_s)) \leq \nu |\tilde{\sigma}(\alpha)| \mathcal{L}_{\widetilde{W}} \beta(K).$$

Thus the function \mathcal{F} fulfills $\mathcal{F}(iv)$.

Chapter 6

NON-INSTANTANEOUS IMPULSIVE FRACTIONAL-ORDER DELAY DIFFERENTIAL SYSTEMS WITH MITTAG-LEFFLER KERNEL

6.1 Introduction

Fractional calculus (FC) was invented by Newton in 1695, but it has recently piqued the interest of many academics. The most fascinating advances in scientific and engineering applications have been discovered within the framework of FC over the last two decades. Due to the difficulties involved with a heterogeneity issue, the idea of the fractional derivative has been industrialized [124–126]. The essential thing to note is that the applications and outcomes of fractional derivatives and integrals differ depending on the definitions used, such as Riemann-Liouville, Hadamard, Grunwald Letnikov, Caputo, Riesz-Caputo, Chen, Weyl, Erd Iyi-Kober, and so on. Recently, Caputo and Fabrizio [38] introduced a novel non-local and non-singular kernel idea in the non-typical Banach space H^1 in 2015. This idea presented a considerable hurdle to application, but it quickly found its way into a variety of areas, including thermal science and mechanical engineering, as well as groundwater research; for more information, see [11, 30, 31], and the references therein. Later, Atangana and Baleanu [18] offered a new concept of non-local derivatives with non-singular kernel depending on the Mittag-Leffler function, which supported the Caputo-Fabrizio's one based on exponential function. The Atangana and Baleanu descriptions have deepened the link between fractional calculus and the Mittag-Leffler function, as well as the major applications that they attain jointly. The reader can

view [9, 18, 24] for more information.

Instantaneous impulsive differential equations (IIDEs) theory describes processes that, during certain moments, undergo a drastic shift in their states. Such processes occur often and spontaneously, particularly in phenomena investigated in the fields of science, control systems, engineering and biological sciences [33, 84]. In the recent several decades, the theory of IIDEs in Banach spaces has emerged as a significant topic of research. For additional information on this concept and its uses, see the references [9, 12, 40, 42, 47, 59, 112], which include a wide range of characteristics of their solutions as well as extensive bibliographies.

In a brief, differential systems with instantaneous impulses examine situations with sudden and instant impulses. However, it is clear that models with instantaneous impulses are unable to explain some aspects of pharmacological evolution processes. When we examine the simplified scenario of a person's hemodynamic equilibrium, the entry of medicines into the circulation and the body's subsequent absorption are slow and continuous processes, as Hernandez and O'Regan pointed out in [68]. As a result, this circumstance might be interpreted as an impulsive activity that begins quickly and continues for a finite period of time. Non-instantaneous impulses are a term we use to describe this phenomena that occurs while building mathematical models. Numerous models derived from actual models may be represented as partial differential systems with NII, according to the research.

Several authors have investigated NII in recent years and come up with some intriguing conclusions, see [1, 32, 41, 53, 69, 82, 114]. Furthermore, very few authors studied the existence and controllability of fractional order differential system through A-B derivative, see for instance [9, 82, 90, 91]. In particular, in [82], Kumar and Pandey investigated the existence findings for fractional order differential systems having NII utilizing the A-B derivative in Banach spaces through measures of non-compactness. Recently, Mallika Arjunan et al. [90, 91] studied the existence results of various fractional order differential systems through A-B derivative under suitable fixed point theorem.

In light of the foregoing, in this chapter, we address the existence findings for a class of

FFDE with NII and Mittag-Leffler kernel of the form

$$\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta} p(\alpha) = Ap(\alpha) + \mathcal{F}(\alpha, p_{\alpha}), \quad \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \quad (6.1.1)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, p_{\alpha}), \quad \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \quad (6.1.2)$$

$$p(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathcal{B}, \quad (6.1.3)$$

where $J = [0, \tau], \tau > 0$ is the operational interval, $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_{\vartheta}(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^{\vartheta}$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_m < \alpha_{m+1} = \tau$, $s_0 = 0$ and $s_{\ell} \in (\alpha_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1})$ for each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$; $\mathcal{F} : \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_{\ell}, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is a stated function that meets later-specified assumptions. We consider the non-instantaneous impulsive functions $\kappa_{\ell} : (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $\varphi \in \mathcal{B}$.

We assume that $p_{\alpha} : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, p_{\alpha}(x) = p(\alpha + x)$, $x \leq 0$, belongs to an abstract phase space \mathcal{B} .

Now we will move on to a description of the work. We give some fundamental concepts on A-B fractional derivatives, phase space axioms (\mathcal{B}) and mild solution of the system (6.1.1)-(6.1.3) in Section 6.2. The proof of our main findings are given in Section 6.3. An illustration is given in the last part.

6.2 Preliminaries

This part covers the fundamental definitions and results of the sectorial operator, piecewise continuous functions, measures of non-compactness [MNC], phase space axioms, and A-B fractional derivative, which will aid us in proving our key conclusions.

Let $(E, \|\cdot\|_E)$ be a complex Banach space. $L(E)$ is the Banach space of all bounded linear operators from X into X with $\|\cdot\|_{L(E)}$ as the corresponding norm.

$\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)$ is the Banach space of all continuous functions from $[0, \tau]$ into E with the norm

$$\|p\|_{\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)} = \sup\{\|p(\alpha)\| : \alpha \in [0, \tau]\}.$$

The functions $p : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ that are integrable in the Bochner notion with regard to

the Lebesgue measure, equipped with

$$\|p\|_{L^1} = \int_0^\tau \|p(x)\| dx$$

is denoted by $L^1([0, \tau], E)$.

For basic definitions of fractional and A-B fractional derivative, we suggest the reader to refer 1.11.1.

6.2.1 Piece-wise Continuous Functions

When incorporating impulsive constraints, we must first construct the piece-wise continuous functions.

We discuss it in detail here.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E) = \{p : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E : p \text{ is continuous for } \alpha \neq \alpha_\ell, \\ \text{left continuous at } \alpha = \alpha_\ell \text{ and } p(\alpha_\ell^+) \text{ exists for } \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m\}. \end{aligned}$$

The fact that $\mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E)$ is a Banach space equipped with the \mathcal{PC} -norm

$$\|p\|_{\mathcal{PC}} = \max \left\{ \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \|p(\alpha^+)\|, \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \|p(\alpha^-)\| \right\}, \quad p \in \mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E),$$

where $p(\alpha^+)$ and $p(\alpha^-)$ constitute respectively the right and left limits of $p(\alpha)$ at $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$.

6.2.2 Phase space axioms

To employ delay criteria, we must first establish the phase space axioms \mathcal{B} introduced by Hale and Kato in [63] and utilize the terminology used in [72]. As a result, $(\mathcal{B}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{B}})$ is a semi-normed linear space of functions mapping $(-\infty, 0]$ into E and satisfying the axioms below.

If $p :]-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E, \tau > 0$, is such that $p_0 \in \mathcal{B}$, then for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, the subsequent assumptions hold:

$$(C1) \quad p_\alpha \in \mathcal{B},$$

$$(C2) \quad \|p_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq Q_1(\alpha) \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \alpha} \|p(x)\| + Q_2(\alpha) \|p_0\|_{\mathcal{B}},$$

(C3) $\|p(\alpha)\| \leq \bar{W} \|p_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}}$, where $\bar{W} > 0$ is a constant and $Q_1 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous, $Q_2 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is locally bounded, and Q_1, Q_2 are independent of $p(\cdot)$. Furthermore, $\|\varphi(0)\| \leq \bar{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}$ for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{B}$.

(C4) p_α is a \mathcal{B} -valued continuous function on $[0, \tau]$ and \mathcal{B} is complete. For more details, see [62].

Now, we define the space

$$Y_\tau = \{p : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E \text{ such that } p_0 \in \mathcal{B} \text{ and the assumption } p|_{[0, \tau]} \in \mathcal{P}\mathcal{C}\}.$$

In Y_τ , the function $\|\cdot\|_{Y_\tau}$ is described as a seminorm,

$$\|p\|_{Y_\tau} = \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} \|p(x)\|, \quad x \in Y_\tau.$$

For more details on phase space axioms and its examples, we suggest the reader to refer [62, 72].

Definition 6.2.1. *If a function $\mathcal{F} : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B}$ meets the subsequent criteria, it is said to be Caratheodory:*

(i) *the function $\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \cdot) : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is continuous for almost every $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$.*

(ii) *the function $\mathcal{F}(\cdot, p) : [0, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is measurable for every $p \in \mathcal{B}$.*

6.2.3 Measures of Noncompactness

Several of our conclusions are based on the concept of measure of non-compactness. With this purpose, we will remember a some characteristics of this idea next. As for basic information, the reader will refer [29, 46]. We just use Kuratowski measure of non-compactness [KMNC] concept throughout this chapter.

Definition 6.2.2. [29, 46] *(Kuratowski measure of noncompactness) Let $B(E)$ be a family of bounded subset of E , where E is a Banach space. Then $\beta : B(E) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is set to*

$$\beta(\mathcal{U}) := \inf\{\mu > 0 : \mathcal{U} = \cup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{U}_i \text{ with } \text{diam}(\mathcal{U}_i) \leq \mu \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, k\},$$

where $\mathcal{U} \in B(E)$ is known as KMNC.

Lemma 6.2.1 ([29, 32, 46]). *For any bounded sets $\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{U}_1$ and \mathcal{U}_2 of a Banach space E , we obtain*

- (i) $\beta(\mathcal{U}) = 0$ iff \mathcal{U} is totally bounded;
- (ii) $\beta(\mathcal{U}) = \beta(\overline{\mathcal{U}})$, where $\overline{\mathcal{U}}$ means the closure of \mathcal{U} ;
- (iii) For each $\mathcal{U}_1 \subset \mathcal{U}_2$ implies $\beta(\mathcal{U}_1) \leq \beta(\mathcal{U}_2)$;
- (iv) $\beta(\mathcal{U}_1 + \mathcal{U}_2) \leq \beta(\mathcal{U}_1) + \beta(\mathcal{U}_2)$;
- (v) $\beta(\mathcal{U}_1 \cup \mathcal{U}_2) = \max\{\beta(\mathcal{U}_1), \beta(\mathcal{U}_2)\}$;
- (vi) $\beta(\lambda\mathcal{U}) = |\lambda|\beta(\mathcal{U})$ for any $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (vii) $\beta(\mathcal{U}) = \beta(\overline{c\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{U})})$.

Lemma 6.2.2. [29] *If $\mathcal{U} \subset \mathcal{C}([\tau_1, \tau_2], E)$ is bounded and equi-continuous on $[\tau_1, \tau_2]$, then $\beta(\mathcal{U}(\alpha))$ is continuous for $\alpha \in [\tau_1, \tau_2]$ and $\beta_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{U}) = \sup\{\beta(\mathcal{U}(\alpha)), \alpha \in [\tau_1, \tau_2]\}$, where $\mathcal{U}(\alpha) = \{p(\alpha) : p \in \mathcal{U}\} \subset E$.*

Lemma 6.2.3. [29] *If \mathcal{U} is a bounded set in $\mathcal{C}([\tau_1, \tau_2], E)$, then $\mathcal{U}(\alpha)$ is bounded in E and $\beta(\mathcal{U}(\alpha)) \leq \beta_{\mathcal{C}}(\mathcal{U})$.*

Lemma 6.2.4. [41] *If $\mathcal{U} \subset E$ is bounded for a Banach space E , then a countable subset $\mathcal{U}_0 \subset \mathcal{U}$ exists, for which $\beta(\mathcal{U}) \leq 2\beta(\mathcal{U}_0)$ exists.*

Lemma 6.2.5 ([41]). *Let E be a Banach space, and let $\mathcal{U} = \{v_n\} \subset \mathcal{PC}([\tau_1, \tau_2], E)$ be a bounded and countable set for constants $-\infty < \tau_1 < \tau_2 < +\infty$. Then $\beta(\mathcal{U}(\alpha))$ is Lebesgue integral on $[\tau_1, \tau_2]$, and $\beta\left(\left\{\int_{\tau_1}^{\tau_2} v_n(\alpha)d\alpha : n \in \mathbb{N}\right\}\right) \leq 2 \int_{\tau_1}^{\tau_2} \beta(\mathcal{U}(\alpha))d\alpha$.*

The KMNC on the bounded set of E , $\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)$, and $\mathcal{PC}([0, \tau], E)$ is denoted by $\beta(\cdot)$, $\beta_{\mathcal{C}}(\cdot)$, and $\beta_{\mathcal{PC}}(\cdot)$, respectively, in this chapter.

In view of 1.11.2, we can now describe the mild solution for the system (6.1.1)-(6.1.3).

Definition 6.2.3. [90] *A function $p \in Y_{\tau}$ is called a mild solution of the system (6.1.1)-(6.1.3) if $p_0 = \varphi \in \mathcal{B}$ and $p(\alpha) = \kappa_{\ell}(\alpha, p_{\alpha})$ for $\alpha \in (\alpha_{\ell}, s_{\ell}]$, and each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$,*

satisfies the following integral equation

$$p(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds, & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, p_{s_\ell}) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (6.2.1)$$

$\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}A(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{x\alpha} x^{\vartheta-1} (x^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} dx, \quad (6.2.2)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta, \vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{x\alpha} (x^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} dx, \quad (6.2.3)$$

Γ denotes the Bromwich path [24].

6.3 Existence Results

The existence findings for the system (6.1.1)-(6.1.3) under the Monch fixed point theorem [1.10.5] are presented and proved in this section.

The following assumptions for the usage of the fixed point theorem [1.10.5] are then listed.

(A1) The function $\mathcal{F} : [0, \tau] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ is Caratheodory.

(A2) There exists a non-decreasing continuous function $\Omega : [0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ and a function $\gamma \in \mathcal{L}^1([0, \tau], \mathbb{R}_+)$ is such that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\alpha, v)\|_E \leq \gamma(\alpha)\Omega(\|v\|_{\mathcal{B}}) \quad \text{for a.e. } \alpha \in [0, \tau] \text{ and } v \in \mathcal{B}.$$

(A3) For each $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ the functions $\kappa_\ell : (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times \mathcal{B} \rightarrow E$ are continuous and fulfills the subsequent assumptions:

(i) There are constants $L_{\kappa_\ell}, \bar{L}_{\kappa_\ell}$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ in ways that

$$\|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, v)\|_E \leq L_{\kappa_\ell}\|v\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \bar{L}_{\kappa_\ell}, \quad \text{for a.e. } \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], v \in \mathcal{B}.$$

(ii) The constants $\gamma_\ell > 0$ such that, for each bounded $\mathcal{U}_1 \subset \mathcal{B}$,

$$\beta(\kappa_\ell(\alpha, \mathcal{U}_1)) \leq \gamma_\ell \sup_{-\infty < \theta \leq 0} \beta(\mathcal{U}_1(\theta)), \quad \text{for a.e. } \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m.$$

(A4) The sets $\{\alpha \rightarrow \kappa_\ell(\alpha, p_\alpha) : p_\alpha \in \mathcal{U}\}$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ are equi-continuous in \mathcal{B} for any bounded set $\mathcal{U} \subset \mathcal{B}$.

(A5) For each $\ell = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$, there exist constants $L_\ell > 0$ in ways that for any countable set $\mathcal{U}_2 \subset \mathcal{B}$

$$\beta(\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \mathcal{U}_2)) \leq L_\ell \sup_{-\infty < \theta \leq 0} \beta(\mathcal{U}_2(\theta)) \quad \forall \alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}].$$

(A6) There exist constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$ for the bounded linear operators \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 6.3.1. *Assume that (A1)-(A6) hold. If*

$$\hat{\Theta} = \left[2\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\widehat{\gamma} + 4 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{L} \right] < 1, \quad (6.3.1)$$

where $\widehat{\gamma} = \max_{\ell=1,2,\dots,m} \gamma_\ell$ and $\widetilde{L} = \max_{\ell=0,1,2,\dots,m} \{(\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^\vartheta L_\ell\}$. Then the system (6.1.1)-(6.1.3) has at least one mild solution on $[0, \tau]$.

Proof. Now the operator $\Upsilon : Y_\tau \rightarrow Y_\tau$ described by

$$(\Upsilon p)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \leq 0, \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds, & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1], \\ \kappa_\ell(\alpha, p_\alpha), & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell)\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, p_{s_\ell}) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, p_s) ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

Let $u(\cdot) : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ be the function described by

$$u(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0), & \alpha \in [0, \tau], \end{cases}$$

then $u_0 = \varphi$. For every $v \in \mathcal{C}([0, \tau], \mathbb{R})$ with $v(0) = 0$, we denote by \bar{v} the function described by

$$\bar{v}(\alpha) = \begin{cases} 0, & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0]; \\ v(\alpha), & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases}$$

Let $p(\cdot)$ satisfies (6.2.1), then we decompose $p(\cdot)$ as $p(\alpha) = v(\alpha) + u(\alpha)$ for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, which suggests $p_\alpha = v_\alpha + u_\alpha$, and the function $v(\cdot)$ fulfills

$$v(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1], \\ \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha + u_\alpha), & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell) \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v_{s_\ell} + u_{s_\ell}) + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

Set $Y_\tau^0 = \{v \in Y_\tau : v_0 = 0 \in \mathcal{B}\}$ and for any $v \in Y_\tau^0$, we have

$$\|v\|_{Y_\tau^0} = \|v_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \sup\{\|v(x)\|_E : 0 \leq x < +\infty\} = \sup\{\|v(x)\|_E : 0 \leq x < +\infty\}.$$

As a result, the Banach space $(Y_\tau^0, \|\cdot\|_{Y_\tau^0})$ exists. Consider $\bar{\Upsilon} : Y_\tau^0 \rightarrow Y_\tau^0$, which is described as:

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1], \\ \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha + u_\alpha), & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell) \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v_{s_\ell} + u_{s_\ell}) + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

It is obvious that operator Υ has a fixed-point if and only if $\bar{\Upsilon}$ has a fixed-point.

To prove the result, we first determine the estimate of the phase space axioms. For every $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we have from 6.2.2,

$$\begin{aligned}
\|v_\alpha + u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} &\leq \|v_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \|u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&\leq Q_1(\alpha)\|v(\alpha)\|_E + Q_2(\alpha)\|v_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} + Q_1(\alpha)\|u(\alpha)\|_E + Q_2(\alpha)\|u_0\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&\leq Q_1(\alpha)\|v(\alpha)\|_E + Q_1(\alpha)[\|\mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\varphi(0)\|_E] + Q_2(\alpha)\|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&\leq Q_1^* \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \alpha} \|v(x)\|_E + Q_1^* \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{W} \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} + Q_2^* \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}} \\
&= Q_1^* \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \alpha} \|v(x)\|_E + (Q_1^* \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{W} + Q_2^*) \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}},
\end{aligned}$$

where $Q_1^* = \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} Q_1(x)$ and $Q_2^* = \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} Q_2(x)$.

Then, we get

$$\|v_\alpha + u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} \leq e + Q_1^* \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \alpha} \|v(x)\|_E, \quad (6.3.2)$$

where $e = (Q_1^* \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \overline{W} + Q_2^*) \|\varphi\|_{\mathcal{B}}$.

We have divided the proof into stages to make it easier to understand.

Step 1: $\overline{\Upsilon}$ is continuous.

Allow v^n be a sequence such that $v^n \rightarrow v$ in Y_τ^0 .

$$(\overline{\Upsilon}v^n)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in (0, \alpha_1], \\ \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha^n + u_\alpha), & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-s_\ell) \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v_{s_\ell}^n + u_{s_\ell}) + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) ds, & \alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

By using the dominated convergence theorem along with (A6), for $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\|(\overline{\Upsilon}v^n)(\alpha) - (\overline{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha)\|_E \\
&\leq \left\| \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) - \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)] ds \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [\mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) - \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)] ds \right\|_E \\
&\leq \frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\alpha-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) - \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E ds
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\vartheta \mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\alpha-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) - \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E ds \\
& \leq \left[\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta) \alpha_1^\vartheta}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \alpha_1^\vartheta}{B(\vartheta)} \right] \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) - \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E \\
& \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.
\end{aligned}$$

For any $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\|(\bar{\Upsilon} v^n)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon} v)(\alpha)\|_E & \leq \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha^n + u_\alpha) - \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha + u_\alpha)\|_E \\
& \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.
\end{aligned}$$

For $\alpha \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\|(\bar{\Upsilon} v^n)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon} v)(\alpha)\|_E & \leq \|\mathbb{S} \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell)\|_E [\|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha^n + u_\alpha) - \kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha + u_\alpha)\|_E] \\
& + \left[\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right] \widehat{L} \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s^n + u_s) - \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E \\
& \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty,
\end{aligned}$$

where $\widehat{L} = \max_{\ell=0,1,2,\dots,m} (\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^\vartheta$.

It is easy to see that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|(\bar{\Upsilon} v^n) - (\bar{\Upsilon} v)\|_{Y_\tau^0} = 0.$$

As a result, in Y_τ^0 , the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is continuous.

Step 2: Any closed ball B_R of Y_τ^0 is mapped into bounded sets in Y_τ^0 by $\bar{\Upsilon}$.

Of course, it is enough to show that there exists $N > 0$ such that for every $v \in B_R = \{v \in Y_\tau^0 : \|v\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq R\}$ one has $\|\bar{\Upsilon}(v)\|_{Y_\tau^0} \leq N$.

Let $v \in Y_\tau^0$ and denote $\gamma^* = \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \tau} \gamma(x)$. If $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, then by (A2) and (6.3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\|(\bar{\Upsilon} v)(\alpha)\|_E & \leq \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{T}\| (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E ds \\
& + \frac{\vartheta \|\mathbb{S}\|^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E ds \\
& \leq \frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta) \Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \gamma(s) \Omega(\|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}}) ds \\
& + \frac{\vartheta \mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \gamma(s) \Omega(\|v_s + u_s\|_{\mathcal{B}}) ds
\end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \left[\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)\alpha_1^\vartheta}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\alpha_1^\vartheta}{B(\vartheta)} \right] \gamma^*\Omega(e+Q_1^*R).$$

For $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, then by (A3) and (6.3.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha)\|_E &= \|\kappa_\ell(\alpha, v_\alpha + u_\alpha)\|_E \\ &\leq L_{\kappa_\ell}\|v_\alpha + u_\alpha\|_{\mathcal{B}} + \bar{L}_{\kappa_\ell} \\ &\leq L_{\kappa_\ell}(e + Q_1^*R) + \bar{L}_{\kappa_\ell} \\ &\leq L(1 + e + Q_1^*R), \end{aligned}$$

where $L = \max_{\ell=1,2,\dots,m} \{L_{\kappa_\ell}, \bar{L}_{\kappa_\ell}\}$.

For $\alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$, then by conditions (A2)-(A3) along with (6.3.2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\alpha)\|_E \\ &\leq \|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell)\|\|\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v_{s_\ell} + u_{s_\ell})\|_E \\ &\quad + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathbb{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbb{S}\|^2\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|\mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s)\|_E ds \\ &\leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}L(1 + e + Q_1^*R) + \left[\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right] (\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^\vartheta \gamma^*\Omega(e + Q_1^*R) \\ &\leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}L(1 + e + Q_1^*R) + \left[\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right] \gamma^*\Omega(e + Q_1^*R)\widehat{L} \\ &\leq N, \end{aligned}$$

where $\widehat{L} = \max_{\ell=0,1,2,\dots,m} (\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^\vartheta$.

Step 3: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ maps bounded sets of Y_τ^0 into equi-continuous sets on Y_τ^0 .

Let B_R be the same as defined in Step 2. Let $0 \leq \nu_1 \leq \nu_2 \leq \alpha_1$ for each $\nu \in B_R$, we obtain

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_E \leq \sum_{i=1}^4 \|I_i\|,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2-s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1-s)^{\vartheta-1}] \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds; \\
I_2 &= \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds; \\
I_3 &= \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2-s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1-s)] \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds; \\
I_4 &= \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2-s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
\|I_1\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_2\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_3\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_4\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

We can conclude that $\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_E \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$ by using the continuity of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta$.

For any $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_E &= \|\kappa_\ell(\nu_2, v_{\nu_2} + u_{\nu_2}) - \kappa_\ell(\nu_1, v_{\nu_1} + u_{\nu_1})\|_E \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

In the similar manner, for any $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in \cup_{\ell=0}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $s_\ell \leq \nu_1 < \nu_2 \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, we obtain

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_E \leq \sum_{i=5}^9 \|I_i\|,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
I_5 &= \mathbb{S}[\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s_\ell)]\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v_{s_\ell} + u_{s_\ell})\| \\
I_6 &= \frac{\mathbb{S}\Gamma(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1 - s)^{\vartheta-1}] \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds; \\
I_7 &= \frac{\mathbb{S}\Gamma(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds; \\
I_8 &= \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s)] \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds; \\
I_9 &= \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) \mathcal{F}(s, v_s + u_s) ds.
\end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned}
\|I_5\| &\leq \mu \|[\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s_\ell)]\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, v_{s_\ell} + u_{s_\ell})\|_E \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_6\| &\leq \frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2 - s_\ell)^\vartheta - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta - (\nu_1 - s_\ell)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_7\| &\leq \frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_8\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2 - s_\ell)^\vartheta - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta - (\nu_1 - s_\ell)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|I_9\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \gamma^* \Omega(e + Q_1^* R) [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

From the above discussion, we conclude that $\|(\overline{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_2) - (\overline{\Upsilon}v)(\nu_1)\|_E \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$.

On Y_τ^0 , the operator $\overline{\Upsilon}$ is hence equi-continuous.

Now, let W be a subset of B_R such that $W \subset \overline{\text{conv}}(\Upsilon(W) \cup \{0\})$. Furthermore, for every bounded set \mathcal{U} , by Lemma 6.2.4, we realize that there exists a countable set $\mathcal{U}_0 = \{w_n\} \subset \mathcal{U}$, such that $\beta(\overline{\Upsilon}(\mathcal{U})) \leq 2\beta(\overline{\Upsilon}(\mathcal{U}_0))$. Thus for $\{w_n\} \subset \mathcal{U}$, noting that the choice of W . For every $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, by utilizing Lemma 6.2.5, condition (A5) and

properties of the measure β , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(\bar{\Upsilon}(w_n)) &= \beta \left(\left\{ \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_{ns} + u_s) ds \right\} \right) \\
&\quad + \beta \left(\left\{ \frac{\vartheta \text{S}^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_{ns} + u_s) ds \right\} \right) \\
&= \beta \left(\left\{ \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right\} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_{ns} + u_s) ds \right) \\
&\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
&\quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} L_\ell \left[\sup_{-\infty < \theta \leq 0} \beta(w_n(\theta + s) + u(\theta + s)) \right] ds \\
&\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} L_\ell \sup_{0 < \mu \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(\mu)) ds \\
&\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} L_\ell \sup_{0 < s \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(s)) ds \\
&\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) L_\ell \beta(\{w_n\}) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} ds \\
&\leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) L_\ell \cdot \frac{\alpha_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \beta(\{w_n\})
\end{aligned}$$

which ensures that

$$\beta(\bar{\Upsilon}(W)) \leq 2 \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} + \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{E}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widehat{L}_1 \beta_{\mathcal{E}}(W),$$

where $\widehat{L}_1 = \max_{\ell=0,1,2,\dots,m} \{L_\ell \alpha_1^\vartheta\}$.

For any $\alpha \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(\bar{\Upsilon}(w_n)) &= \beta(\{\kappa_\ell(\kappa, w_{n\alpha} + u_\alpha)\}) \\
&\leq 2\gamma_\ell \sup_{-\infty < \theta \leq 0} \beta(w_n(\theta + \alpha) + u(\theta + \alpha)) \\
&\leq 2\gamma_\ell \sup_{0 < \mu \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(\mu)) \\
&\leq 2\gamma_\ell \sup_{0 < s \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(s)) \\
&\leq 2\gamma_\ell \beta(\{w_n\})
\end{aligned}$$

which ensures that

$$\beta(\bar{\Upsilon}(W)) \leq 2\widehat{\gamma} \beta_{\mathcal{E}}(W),$$

where $\widehat{\gamma} = \max_{\ell=1,2,\dots,m} \gamma_\ell$.

Likewise, for any $\alpha \in (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(\overline{\Upsilon}(w_n)) &= \beta \left(\left\{ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - s_\ell) \kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w_{ns_\ell} + u_{s_\ell}) \right. \right. \\
&\quad + \frac{\mathbb{S}\Gamma(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\vartheta (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_{ns} + u_s) ds \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \mathcal{F}(s, w_{ns} + u_s) ds \right\} \right) \\
&\leq 2\mu \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \beta(\{\kappa_\ell(s_\ell, w_{ns_\ell} + u_{s_\ell})\}) + 2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta \mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\
&\quad (\times) \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} L_\ell \left[\sup_{-\infty < \theta \leq 0} \beta(w_n(\theta + s) + u(\theta + s)) \right] ds \\
&\leq 2\mu \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \gamma_\ell \sup_{-\infty < \theta \leq 0} \beta(w_n(\theta + s_\ell) + u(\theta + s_\ell)) \\
&\quad + 2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta \mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} L_\ell \sup_{s_\ell < \mu \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(\mu)) ds \\
&\leq 2\mu \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \gamma_\ell \sup_{0 < s \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(s)) \\
&\quad + 2 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\vartheta \mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{s_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} L_\ell \sup_{0 < s \leq \tau} \beta(w_n(s)) ds
\end{aligned}$$

which ensures that

$$\beta(\overline{\Upsilon}(W)) \leq \left(2\mu \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \widehat{\gamma} + 4 \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta + 1)} + \frac{\mu^2 \widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \widetilde{L} \right) \beta_{\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}}(W),$$

where $\widehat{\gamma} = \max_{\ell=1,2,\dots,m} \gamma_\ell$ and $\widetilde{L} = \max_{\ell=0,1,2,\dots,m} \{(\alpha_{\ell+1} - s_\ell)^\vartheta L_\ell\}$.

Then

$$\beta_{\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}}(W) \leq \beta(\overline{\Upsilon}(W))_{\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}} \leq \widehat{\Theta} \beta_{\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}}(W).$$

That is to say

$$\beta_{\mathcal{D}\mathcal{E}}(W)(1 - \widehat{\Theta}) \leq 0.$$

Hence, we get $\beta(W) = 0$. Given Arzela-Ascoli's theorem [1.10.7], W in Y_τ^0 is relatively compact. The result of Monch fixed point theorem 1.10.5 is that $\overline{\Upsilon}$ has a fixed point $v \in Y_\tau^0$. \square

6.4 Example

Consider the following fractional differential equation with non-instantaneous impulsive condition of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta z(\alpha, w) &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial w^2} z(\alpha, w) \\ &+ \int_{-\infty}^0 W(\theta) \mu(\alpha, z(\alpha + \theta, w)) d\theta, \quad (\alpha, w) \in \cup_{\ell=1}^m (s_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}] \times [0, \pi], \end{aligned} \quad (6.4.1)$$

$$z(\alpha, 0) = z(\alpha, \pi) = 0, \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \quad (6.4.2)$$

$$z(\theta, w) = z_0(\theta, w), \quad -\infty < \theta \leq 0, \quad w \in [0, \pi], \quad (6.4.3)$$

$$z(\alpha, w) = \int_{-\infty}^0 \tilde{\mu}_\ell(s) z(\alpha + s, w) ds, \quad (\alpha, w) \in (\alpha_\ell, s_\ell] \times [0, \pi], \quad \ell = 1, 2, \dots, m, \quad (6.4.4)$$

where $W : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$; $\mu : [0, +\infty) \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $z_0 : (-\infty, 0] \times [0, \pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\tilde{\mu}_\ell : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, m$ are continuous functions.

Let $E = L^2([0, \pi], \mathbb{R})$ and $A : D(A) \subseteq E \rightarrow E$ be an operator by $A\Theta = \Theta''$, $\Theta \in D(A)$ with domain $D(A) = \{\Theta \in E; \Theta \text{ and } \Theta' \text{ are absolutely continuous, } \Theta'' \in E, \Theta(0) = \Theta(\pi) = 0\}$. Then

$$A\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in D(A),$$

where $\Theta_n(s) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin(ns)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the orthonormal set of eigenvectors of A and A generates a C_0 semigroup $\{\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \geq 0}$ in E which is given by

$$\mathcal{B}(\alpha)\Theta = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2\alpha} \langle \Theta, \Theta_n \rangle \Theta_n, \quad \Theta \in E, \quad \alpha > 0$$

which is uniformly bounded and also a compact semigroup and hence the operator $R(\lambda, A) = (\lambda I - A)^{-1}$ is compact for each $\lambda \in \rho(A)$, i.e., $A \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\beta_0, \Theta_0)$. We also obtain through the concept of subordination of the solution operator $\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)\| \leq \widehat{M}_\mathcal{B}$ for each $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$. For more details, refer [82].

For the phase space \mathcal{B} , we choose the well-known space $BUC(\mathbb{R}_-, E)$, the space of bounded uniformly continuous functions defined from $(-\infty, 0]$ to E endowed with the

following norm:

$$\|\varphi\| = \sup_{\theta \leq 0} |\varphi(\theta)|, \quad \text{for each } \varphi \in \mathcal{B}.$$

If $\varphi \in BUC(\mathbb{R}_-, E)$ and $w \in [0, \pi]$,

$$z(\alpha)(w) = z(\alpha, w), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], w \in [0, \pi],$$

$$\varphi(\theta)(w) = z_0(\theta, w), \quad -\infty < \theta \leq 0, w \in [0, \pi],$$

$$\mathcal{F}(\alpha, \varphi)(w) = \int_{-\infty}^0 W(\theta) \mu(\alpha, \varphi(\theta)(w)) d\theta, \quad -\infty < \theta \leq 0, w \in [0, \pi],$$

$$\kappa_\ell(\alpha, \varphi)(w) = \int_{-\infty}^0 \tilde{\mu}_\ell(s) (\varphi(\theta)(w)) d\theta.$$

The system (6.4.1)-(6.4.4) can then be written as (6.1.1)-(6.1.3) in an abstract form. Also, we can confirm that the Theorem 6.3.1 assumptions hold. As a consequence, system (6.4.1)-(6.4.4) has a mild solution from the Theorem 6.3.1.

Chapter 7

EXISTENCE AND CONTROLLABILITY OF FRACTIONAL INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION WITH INFINITE DELAY AND IMPULSIVE EFFECTS

7.1 Introduction

In modelling many physical processes, fractional differential equations (FDEs) serve as a strong mathematical tool for providing more exact and remarkable findings than integer-order equations [5, 24, 32, 35, 106]. The considerable utility of FDE applications has prompted a number of researchers to develop a variety of methodologies and strategies to address FDEs. In addition, numerous researchers have worked on the qualitative properties of FDE solutions and have developed valuable findings [53, 75, 112].

Controllability involves steering dynamic systems from a random initial state to an arbitrary final state. Along with its importance in finite and infinite dynamic systems and their unique advantage in turning the control system into a fixed problem at some point. The control function is naturally used to FDEs as alternative models of nonlinear systems, where the control function seems to direct the system solution from an arbitrary beginning state to an arbitrary final state using the set of acceptable controls [9, 45, 75].

The investigation of mathematical models of nonlinear impulsive functional differential system is prompted by a wonderful combination of two features, specifically, the dependency on prior history and jumps or abrupt changes of complex dynamic systems at specific intervals. As a result, any universal phenomenon dependent on its past history

and jumps to the finite number of points can be better represented by means of nonlinear functional differential equations. In the research monographs [25, 62, 84], the importance of both the aspects of delay and jumps in the analysis of the behaviour of such dynamic systems as well as, exhaustive account of various topics related to this problem, are discussed.

Atangana and Baleanu [18] introduced the novel A-B fractional derivative in both R-L and Caputo senses in recent years. The generalised Mittag-Leffler function is included as a kernel in this derivation. The extended Mittag-Leffler function's non-local behaviour provides for a more accurate explanation of the macroscopic behaviour and memory effects of systems including non-local interactions. As a result, studying FDEs with A-B fractional derivatives is critical. In the published works, there are a few studies that focus on the existence, uniqueness, and other quantitative and qualitative features of FDEs through A-B fractional derivative [9, 64, 73, 81, 82, 90, 91]. Especially, in [9], authors discussed the controllability of semilinear impulsive Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential equations with delay in Banach space under Darbo fixed point theorem. Recently, Kumar and Pandey [82] analyzed the existence of mild solution of Atangana-Baleanu fractional differential equations with non-instantaneous impulses and with non-local conditions through measures of non-compactness in Banach spaces. However, to our knowledge, there is no research on existence and controllability of an ABFFDS with infinite delay and impulsive effects of the form (7.1.1) and (7.1.2) in the literature. This is indeed a significant benefit for writing this work.

Inspired by the above-mentioned works, this chapter is concerned with the existence and controllability of mild solutions for an impulsive ABFFDS with infinite delay of the model

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABCP}^{\vartheta} p(\alpha) &= Ap(\alpha) + f(\alpha, p_{\alpha}, Np(\alpha)), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \alpha \neq \alpha_{\ell}, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q, \\ \Delta p(\alpha_{\ell}) &= I_{\ell}(p(\alpha_{\ell}^{-})), \quad \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q, \\ p(\alpha) &= \varphi(\alpha), \quad \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathfrak{C}_h, \end{aligned} \tag{7.1.1}$$

and the corresponding controllability model

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{ABCP}^{\vartheta} p(\alpha) &= Ap(\alpha) + f(\alpha, p_{\alpha}, Np(\alpha)) + (G\nu)(\alpha), \quad \alpha \in [0, \tau], \alpha \neq \alpha_{\ell}, \\ \Delta p(\alpha_{\ell}) &= I_{\ell}(p(\alpha_{\ell}^{-})), \quad \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q, \end{aligned} \tag{7.1.2}$$

$$p(\alpha) = \varphi(\alpha), \quad \varphi(\alpha) \in \mathfrak{C}_h,$$

where $\tau > 0, \vartheta \in (0, 1)$, $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ is the infinitesimal generator of an ϑ -resolvent family $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$, the solution operator $\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha)_{\alpha \geq 0}$ is described on a complex Banach space E , $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative, $f : [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{C}_h \times E \rightarrow E$ is a given function; G is a bounded linear operator from a Banach space $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}$ into E ; the control function $\nu(\cdot) \in L^2([0, \tau], \widehat{\mathcal{B}})$, a Banach space of admissible control function and \mathfrak{C}_h is a phase space defined in Section 7.2. Here, $0 = \alpha_0 < \alpha_1 < \dots < \alpha_q < \alpha_{q+1} = \tau, I_\ell \in \mathcal{C}(E, E), (\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q)$, are bounded functions, $\Delta p(\alpha_\ell) = p(\alpha_\ell^+) - p(\alpha_\ell^-), p(\alpha_\ell^+) = \lim_{e \rightarrow 0} p(\alpha_\ell + e)$ and $p(\alpha_\ell^-) = \lim_{e \rightarrow 0} p(\alpha_\ell - e)$ represent the right and left limits of $p(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_\ell$, respectively.

We assume that $p_\alpha : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, p_\alpha(x) = p(\alpha + x), x \leq 0$, belongs to an abstract phase space \mathfrak{C}_h . The expression $Np(\alpha)$ is defined by $Np(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha \mathcal{B}(\alpha, s)p(s)ds$, where $\mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{C}(K, \mathbb{R}^+)$ and $K = \{(\alpha, s) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : 0 \leq s \leq \alpha \leq \tau\}$.

Now we will move on to a description of the work. We give some fundamental concepts on A-B fractional derivatives, phase space axioms (\mathfrak{C}_h) and mild solution of the system (7.1.1) in Section 7.2. The proof of our main findings are given in Section 7.3 and Section 7.4. An example is given in the last section.

7.2 Preliminaries and Hypotheses

In this section, we will go over some fundamental definitions and attributes that we will need to figure out our outcomes.

Let $(E, \|\cdot\|_E)$ be a complex Banach space. $L(E)$ is the Banach space of all bounded linear operators from X into X with $\|\cdot\|_{L(E)}$ as the corresponding norm.

$\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)$ is the Banach space of all continuous functions from $[0, \tau]$ into E with the norm

$$\|p\|_{\mathcal{C}([0, \tau], E)} = \sup\{\|p(\alpha)\| : \alpha \in [0, \tau]\}.$$

Furthermore, $B_R(p, E)$ denotes a closed ball in E with a radius of R and a center at p .

For basic definitions of fractional and A-B fractional derivative, we suggest the reader to refer 1.11.1.

It should be emphasized that once the delay is infinite, then we should discuss the theoretical phase space \mathfrak{C}_h in a beneficial manner (for details see [40, 114]).

Let us consider the continuous function $h : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ with $w = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(\alpha) d\alpha < \infty$. For any $\tau > 0$, we present $\mathfrak{C} = \{\omega : [-\tau, 0] \rightarrow E \text{ such that } \omega(\alpha) \text{ is bounded and measurable}\}$ and equip the space \mathfrak{C} with the norm

$$\|\omega\|_{[-\tau, 0]} = \sup_{x \in [-\tau, 0]} |\omega(x)|, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathfrak{C}.$$

Let us define by

$$\mathfrak{C}_h = \left\{ \omega : (-\infty, 0] \rightarrow E, \text{ such that for any } d > 0, \omega|_{[-d, 0]} \in \mathfrak{C} \text{ with } \omega(0) = 0 \text{ and } \int_{-\infty}^0 h(x) \|\omega\|_{[x, 0]} dx < \infty \right\}.$$

If the norm is present in \mathfrak{C}_h , we have

$$\|\omega\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(x) \|\omega\|_{[x, 0]} dx, \quad \forall \omega \in \mathfrak{C}_h.$$

Then $(\mathfrak{C}_h, \|\cdot\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h})$ is guaranteed to be a Banach space.

Presently, we define $\mathfrak{C}'_h = \{p : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E \text{ such that } p|_{I_\ell} \in \mathcal{C}(I_\ell, E) \text{ and we can find}$

$$p(\alpha_\ell^+) \text{ and } p(\alpha_\ell^-) \text{ with } p(\alpha_\ell) = p(\alpha_\ell^-), p_0 = \varphi \in \mathfrak{C}_h, \ell = 1, \dots, q\},$$

where $p|_{I_\ell}$ is the restriction of p to $I_\ell = (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 0, 1, 2, \dots, q$. The function $\|\cdot\|_{\mathfrak{C}'_h}$ to be a seminorm in \mathfrak{C}'_h it is characterized by

$$\|p\|_{\mathfrak{C}'_h} = \sup\{|p(x)| : x \in [0, \tau]\} + \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{C}'_h}, \quad p \in \mathfrak{C}'_h :$$

If $p :]-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E, \tau > 0$, is such that $p_0 \in \mathfrak{C}_h$, then for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, the subsequent assumptions hold:

$$(C1) \quad p_\alpha \in \mathfrak{C}_h,$$

$$(C2) \quad \|p_\alpha\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} \leq Q_1(\alpha) \sup_{0 \leq x \leq \alpha} \|p(x)\| + Q_2(\alpha) \|p_0\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h},$$

$$(C3) \quad \|p(\alpha)\| \leq \overline{W} \|p_\alpha\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h}, \text{ where } \overline{W} > 0 \text{ is a constant and } Q_1 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty) \text{ is continuous, } Q_2 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty) \text{ is locally bounded, and } Q_1, Q_2 \text{ are independent of } p(\cdot). \text{ For more details, see [63].}$$

In view of 1.11.2, we can now define a mild solution of the system (7.1.1).

Definition 7.2.1. A function $p : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is called a mild solution of the system (7.1.1) if the subsequent holds: $p_0 = \varphi \in \mathfrak{C}_h$ on $(-\infty, 0]$ with $\varphi(0) = 0$; $\Delta p|_{\alpha=\alpha_\ell} = I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))$, $\ell = 1, \dots, q$, the restriction of $p(\cdot)$ to the interval $[0, \tau] \setminus \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_q\}$ is continuous and satisfies the following integral equation:

$$p(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-\alpha_1)(p(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(p(\alpha_1^-))) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha-\alpha_\ell)(p(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))) + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (7.2.1)$$

where $\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}A(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} \sigma^{\vartheta-1} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (7.2.2)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta, \vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (7.2.3)$$

Γ denotes the Bromwich path [24].

7.3 Existence Results

The existence findings for the system (7.1.1) is presented and proved in this section utilizing appropriate fixed point theorems.

Our first existence result is based on the Banach contraction principle [1.10.1].

The following requirements must be met in order to apply this theorem:

(A1) The function $f : [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{C}_h \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous and there exist positive constants $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$ such that

$$\|f(\alpha, u_1, v_1) - f(\alpha, u_2, v_2)\|_E \leq \lambda_1 \|u_1 - u_2\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + \lambda_2 \|v_1 - v_2\|_E,$$

for $\alpha \in [0, \tau], (u_1, u_2) \in \mathfrak{C}_h^2, v_1, v_2 \in E$.

(A2) The function $I_\ell \in \mathcal{C}(E, E), \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$, there exists $\eta_\ell > 0$ such that

$$\|I_\ell(u) - I_\ell(v)\|_E \leq \eta_\ell \|u - v\|_E, \quad \forall u, v \in E.$$

(A3) There exist constants $\mu, \bar{\mu}$ such that $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq \mu$ and $\|\mathbb{T}\| \leq \bar{\mu}$ for the bounded linear operators \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 7.3.1. *Assume that the conditions (A1)-(A3) hold. Then the system (7.1.1) has a unique mild solution if*

$$\max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q} \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}(1 + \eta_\ell) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right] < 1, \quad (7.3.1)$$

where $Q_1^* = \sup_{x \in [0, \tau]} Q_1(x)$ and $N^* = \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \int_0^\alpha \mathcal{B}(\alpha, s) ds < \infty$.

Proof. The system (7.1.1) will be transformed into a fixed-point problem. Consider the operator $\Upsilon : \mathfrak{C}'_h \rightarrow \mathfrak{C}'_h$ described by

$$(\Upsilon p)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)(p(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(p(\alpha_1^-))) \\ + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)(p(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))) \\ + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases} \quad (7.3.2)$$

Let $v(\cdot) : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ be the function described by

$$v(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ 0, & \alpha \in [0, \tau], \end{cases}$$

then $v_0 = \varphi$. For each $u \in \mathcal{C}([0, \tau], \mathbb{R})$ with $u(0) = 0$, we denote by \bar{u} the function defined by

$$\bar{u}(\alpha) = \begin{cases} 0, & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0]; \\ u(\alpha), & \alpha \in [0, \tau]. \end{cases}$$

Let $p(\cdot)$ satisfies (7.2.1), then we decompose $p(\cdot)$ as $p(\alpha) = v(\alpha) + \bar{u}(\alpha)$ for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, which suggests $p_\alpha = v_\alpha + \bar{u}_\alpha$, and the function $u(\cdot)$ fulfills

$$u(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)[v(\alpha_1^-) + \bar{u}(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(v(\alpha_1^-) + \bar{u}(\alpha_1^-))] \\ + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)[v(\alpha_\ell^-) + \bar{u}(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(v(\alpha_\ell^-) + \bar{u}(\alpha_\ell^-))] \\ + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases} \quad (7.3.3)$$

Set $\mathfrak{E}_h'' = \{u \in \mathfrak{E}_h' : u_0 = 0 \in \mathfrak{E}_h\}$ and let $\|\cdot\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''}$ be the seminorm in \mathfrak{E}_h'' characterized by

$$\|u\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''} = \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \|u(\alpha)\|_E + \|u_0\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h} = \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \|u(\alpha)\|_E, \quad u \in \mathfrak{E}_h'',$$

then $(\mathfrak{E}_h'', \|\cdot\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''})$ is a Banach space.

We define the operator $\bar{\Upsilon} : \mathfrak{E}_h'' \rightarrow \mathfrak{E}_h''$ by

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \end{cases} \quad (7.3.4)$$

$$(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)[u(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(u(\alpha_1^-))] \\ + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)[u(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))] \\ + \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\alpha} (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\alpha} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha - s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

It is obvious that operator Υ has a unique fixed-point if and only if $\bar{\Upsilon}$ has a unique fixed-point.

For this, let $u, u^* \in \mathfrak{C}_h''$, then for all $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u^*)(\alpha)\|_E \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^{\alpha} (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda_1 \|\bar{u}_s - \bar{u}_s^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} \\ & \quad + \lambda_2 \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)) - N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s))\|_E] ds \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\alpha_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''}, \end{aligned}$$

since

$$\begin{aligned} \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)) - N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s))\|_E & \leq \int_0^{\alpha} \mathcal{B}(\alpha, s) \|v(s) + \bar{u}(s) - v(s) - \bar{u}^*(s)\|_E ds \\ & \leq N^* \|\bar{u}(s) - \bar{u}^*(s)\|_E \\ & \leq N^* \|\bar{u} - \bar{u}^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''}. \end{aligned}$$

For $\alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u^*)(\alpha)\|_E \\ & \leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}(1 + \eta_1) \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\alpha_2^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} \\ & \leq \left[\mu\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}(1 + \eta_1) + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\alpha_2^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right] \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} \end{aligned}$$

For $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u^*)(\alpha)\|_E \\ & \leq \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(1 + \eta_\ell) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\alpha^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right] \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}u) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u^*)\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} \\ & \leq \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q} \left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(1 + \eta_\ell) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^{\vartheta}}{\vartheta} \right] \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''}. \end{aligned}$$

From (7.3.1) and in the perspective of the contraction mapping principle [1.10.1], we realize that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ includes a unique fixed point $u \in \mathfrak{C}_h''$ which is a mild solution of the model (7.1.1) on $(-\infty, \tau]$. \square

Our second result is based on the Krasnoselskii's fixed point theorem [1.10.2].

To apply this theorem, the following conditions must be met:

(A1)* The function $f : [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{C}_h \times E \rightarrow E$ is continuous, and we can find continuous functions $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 : [0, \tau] \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ such that

$$\|f(\alpha, u, v)\|_E \leq \lambda_1(\alpha)\|u\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + \lambda_2(\alpha)\|v\|_E, \quad (\alpha, u, v) \in [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{C}_h \times E.$$

(A2)* The function $I_\ell : E \rightarrow E$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$ are continuous, and there exists $W > 0$ in ways that

$$W = \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q, p \in B_R} \{\|I_\ell(p)\|_E\}.$$

The following lemma is required before proceeding.

Lemma 7.3.1. *Let*

$$Q_1^* = \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq [0, \tau]} Q_1(\tau); \quad Q_2^* = \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq [0, \tau]} Q_2(\tau); \quad \lambda_1^* = \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq [0, \tau]} \lambda_1(\tau); \quad \lambda_2^* = \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq [0, \tau]} \lambda_2(\tau),$$

then for any $s \in I$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1(s)\|v_s + \bar{u}_s\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + \lambda_2(s)\|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))\|_E & \leq \lambda_1^* \left[Q_2^* \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + Q_1^* \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq s} \|u(\tau)\|_E \right] \\ & \quad + \lambda_2^* \int_0^s \mathcal{B}(s, \tau) \|u(\tau)\|_E d\tau. \end{aligned}$$

If $\|u\|_E < R$, $R > 0$, then

$$\lambda_1(s) \|v_s + \bar{u}_s\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + \lambda_2(s) \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))\|_E \leq \lambda_1^* [Q_2^* \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + Q_1^* R] + \lambda_2^* N^* R = \Lambda, \quad (7.3.5)$$

where $N^* = \sup_{\alpha \in [0, \tau]} \int_0^\alpha \mathcal{B}(\alpha, s) ds < \infty$.

Proof. In view of (C2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|v_s + \bar{u}_s\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} &\leq \|v_s\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + \|\bar{u}_s\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} \\ &\leq Q_1(s) \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq s} \|v(\tau)\| + Q_2(s) \|v_0\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + Q_1(s) \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq s} \|u(\tau)\|_E + Q_2(s) \|u_0\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} \\ &\leq Q_2(s) \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + Q_1(s) \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq s} \|u(\tau)\|_E \\ &\leq Q_2^* \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} + Q_1^* \sup_{0 \leq \tau \leq s} \|u(\tau)\|_E \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))\|_E &\leq \int_0^s \|\mathcal{B}(s, \tau)(v(\tau) + \bar{u}(\tau))\|_E d\tau \\ &\leq \int_0^s \|\mathcal{B}(s, \tau)u(\tau)\|_E d\tau \\ &\leq \int_0^s \mathcal{B}(s, \tau) \|u(\tau)\|_E d\tau. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, we derive (7.3.5). □

Theorem 7.3.2. Assume that the assumptions (A1), (A3), (A1)*, (A2)* are true. Then on $(-\infty, \tau]$, the system (7.1.1) has at least one mild solution if

$$\left[\left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right] < 1. \quad (7.3.6)$$

Proof. Select $R \geq \left(\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(R + W) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda \tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right)$ and take into consideration $B_R = \{u \in \mathfrak{C}_h'' : \|u\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} \leq R\}$, then B_R is a bounded, closed-convex subset in \mathfrak{C}_h'' . To use Krasnoselskii's fixed point theorem, we must first define the operators $\Upsilon_1 : B_R \rightarrow B_R$ and $\Upsilon_2 : B_R \rightarrow B_R$ as follows:

$$(\Upsilon_1 u)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} 0, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)[u(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(u(\alpha_1^-))], & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)[u(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))], & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (7.3.7)$$

and

$$(\Upsilon_2 u)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]. \end{cases}$$

Next, we show that operators Υ_1, Υ_2 fulfill the Krasnoselskii's fixed point theorem.

That is, we need to prove that Υ_2 is a contraction, Υ_1 is compact and continuous and $\Upsilon_1 u + \Upsilon_2 u^* \in B_R$ for all $u, u^* \in B_R$.

We split the proof into several steps for easier readings.

Step 1: $\Upsilon_1 u + \Upsilon_2 u^* \in B_R$ for all $u, u^* \in B_R$.

For any $u, u^* \in B_R$, and for $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\Upsilon_1 u)(\alpha) + (\Upsilon_2 u^*)(\alpha)\|_E \\ & \leq \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{T}\| (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\ & \quad + \frac{\vartheta \|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\|_{L(E)} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\ & \leq \frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\ & \quad + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ & \quad (\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda_1(s) \|v_s + \bar{u}_s\|_{\mathbf{e}_h} + \lambda_2(s) \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))\|_E] ds \end{aligned}$$

and using the Lemma 7.3.1, we have

$$\|(\Upsilon_1 u) + (\Upsilon_2 u^*)\|_{\mathbf{e}_h'} \leq \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda \alpha_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta}.$$

Likewise, for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|(\Upsilon_1 u)(\alpha) + (\Upsilon_2 u^*)(\alpha)\|_E \\
& \leq \|\mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)[u(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))]\| \\
& \quad + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathbb{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\
& \quad + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\|_{L(E)} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\
& \leq \|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)\| [\|u\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h'} + \|I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E] \\
& \quad + \frac{\|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathbb{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\
& \quad + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\|_{L(E)} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s^*, N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s)))\|_E ds \\
& \leq \mu\widehat{M}_\vartheta(R+W) + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\vartheta\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda\alpha_{\ell+1}^\vartheta}{\vartheta}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then for every $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we have

$$\|(\Upsilon_1 u) + (\Upsilon_2 u^*)\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h'} \leq \mu\widehat{M}_\vartheta(R+W) + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\vartheta\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta}.$$

Thus, we can conclude that

$$\|(\Upsilon_1 u) + (\Upsilon_2 u^*)\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h'} \leq R.$$

Step 2: Υ_1 is continuous and compact.

For our convenience, first we demonstrate that the mapping $(\Upsilon_1 u)(\alpha)$ is continuous on B_R . For this reason, let $\{u^n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ be a sequence in B_R with $\lim u^n \rightarrow u \in B_R$, then for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, q$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|(\Upsilon_1 u^n)(\alpha) - (\Upsilon_1 u)(\alpha)\|_E \\
& \leq \|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)} [\|u^n(\alpha_\ell^-) - u(\alpha_\ell^-)\|_E + \|I_\ell(u^n(\alpha_\ell^-)) - I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E].
\end{aligned}$$

Since the functions I_ℓ , $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$ are continuous, hence $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Upsilon_1 u^n = \Upsilon_1 u$ in B_R which suggests that the mapping Υ_1 is continuous on B_R .

From (7.3.7), for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, q$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\|(\Upsilon_1 u)(\alpha)\|_E & \leq \|\mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)[u(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))]\| \\
& \leq \|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)} [\|u\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h'} + \|I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E] \\
& \leq \mu\widehat{M}_\vartheta(R+W), \tag{7.3.8}
\end{aligned}$$

and let $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\alpha_\ell \leq \nu_1 < \nu_2 \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, q$, $u \in B_R$, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\Upsilon_1 u)(\nu_2) - (\Upsilon_1 u)(\nu_1)\|_E \\ & \leq \|S\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)} [\|u\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''} + \|I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E] \\ & \leq \mu(R + W) \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)}. \end{aligned} \quad (7.3.9)$$

Since \mathcal{B}_ϑ is strongly continuous, the continuity of the function $\alpha \mapsto \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta\|$ allows us to conclude that $\lim_{\nu_1 \rightarrow \nu_2} \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)} = 0$, which infers that $\Upsilon_1(B_R)$ is equi-continuous.

The operator Υ_1 has uniform boundedness and is equi-continuous, according to equations (7.3.8) and (7.3.9).

Lastly, we infer that the operator Υ_1 is compact by combining Steps 1 and 2 with Ascoli's theorem.

It's just a matter of demonstrating that the operator Υ_2 is a contraction. Let $u, u^* \in B_R$, and $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, q$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \|(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\alpha) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u^*)(\alpha)\|_E \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\alpha} (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda_1 \|\bar{u}_s - \bar{u}_s^*\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h} \\ & \quad + \lambda_2 \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)) - N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s))\|_E] ds \\ & \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\alpha_{\ell+1}^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we have

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}u) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u^*)\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''} \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''}.$$

□

From (7.3.6), we conclude that the operator Υ_1 is a contraction.

The operators Υ_1 and Υ_2 satisfy all aspects of the Krasnoselskii's fixed point theorem [1.10.2] as a result of Steps 1-2.

As a result, we conclude that the system (7.1.1) has at least one solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$.

The proof is now completed.

Our final conclusion is based on Schaefer's fixed-point theorem [1.10.4].

Theorem 7.3.3. *Assume that the conditions (A1)* and (A2)* hold. Then the system (7.1.1) has at least one mild solution on $(-\infty, \tau]$ if*

$$\left[\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \right] < 1.$$

Proof. Now, we characterize the operator $\overline{\Upsilon}$ as in Theorem 7.3.1. In the next phases, we finish the proof.

Step 1: $\overline{\Upsilon}$ is continuous.

Let $\{u^n\}$ be a sequence in \mathcal{C}_h'' such that $u^n \rightarrow u$ in \mathcal{C}_h'' . Since the function f is continuous on $[0, \tau] \times \mathcal{C}_h \times E$. This infers that

$$f(s, v_s + \overline{u}_s^n, N(v(s) + \overline{u}^n(s))) ds \rightarrow f(s, v_s + \overline{u}_s, N(v(s) + \overline{u}(s))) ds \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \quad (7.3.10)$$

For $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\overline{\Upsilon}u^n(\alpha) - \overline{\Upsilon}u(\alpha)\|_E &\leq \left(\frac{\mu \overline{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &(\times) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \overline{u}_s^n, N(v(s) + \overline{u}^n(s))) - f(s, v_s + \overline{u}_s, N(v(s) + \overline{u}(s)))\|_E ds \\ &\leq \left(\frac{\mu \overline{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\alpha_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \epsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (7.3.11)$$

where $\epsilon > 0, \epsilon \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

For $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\|\overline{\Upsilon}u^n(\alpha) - \overline{\Upsilon}u(\alpha)\|_E \\ &\leq \|\mathcal{S}\| \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)} \left[\|u^n(\alpha_\ell^-) - u(\alpha_\ell^-)\|_E + \|I_\ell(u^n(\alpha_\ell^-)) - I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\mu \overline{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ &\quad (\times) \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha - s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \overline{u}_s^n, N(v(s) + \overline{u}^n(s))) - f(s, v_s + \overline{u}_s, N(v(s) + \overline{u}(s)))\|_E ds \\ &\leq \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \left[\|u^n(\alpha_\ell^-) - u(\alpha_\ell^-)\|_E + \|I_\ell(u^n(\alpha_\ell^-)) - I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\mu \overline{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\alpha_{\ell+1}^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \epsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (7.3.12)$$

where $\epsilon > 0, \epsilon \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore, we get

$$\|\bar{\Upsilon}u^n - \bar{\Upsilon}u\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''} = 0.$$

As a result, the operator $\bar{\Upsilon}$ is continuous on \mathfrak{E}_h'' .

Step 2: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ maps bounded sets into bounded sets in \mathfrak{E}_h'' .

To show that for any $R > 0$, we can find a $\Omega > 0$ such that for each $u \in B_R$, one has $\|\bar{\Upsilon}u\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''} \leq \Omega$, where B_R is same as described in Theorem 7.3.2. For $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\bar{\Upsilon}u(\alpha)\|_E &\leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda_1(s)\|v_s + \bar{u}_s\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h} \\ &\quad + \lambda_2(s)\|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))\|_E] ds \end{aligned}$$

and using the Lemma 7.3.1, we have

$$\|\bar{\Upsilon}u(\alpha)\|_E \leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda\alpha_1^\vartheta}{\vartheta}.$$

In the similar manner, for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$, we obtain

$$\|\bar{\Upsilon}u(\alpha)\|_E \leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}(R+W) + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda\alpha_{\ell+1}^\vartheta}{\vartheta}.$$

From the above estimations, we have for $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$,

$$\|\bar{\Upsilon}u\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h''} \leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}(R+W) + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathfrak{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \frac{\Lambda\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} = \Omega.$$

Step 3: $\bar{\Upsilon}$ maps bounded sets into equi-continuous sets of B_R .

Let B_R be defined as in Theorem 7.3.2. Let $0 \leq \nu_1 < \nu_2 \leq \alpha_1$ for each $\nu \in B_r$, we obtain

$$\|(\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_2) - (\bar{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_1)\|_E \leq \sum_{i=1}^4 \|H_i\|,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2-s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1-s)^{\vartheta-1}] f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds; \\ H_2 &= \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds; \\ H_3 &= \frac{\vartheta\text{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2-s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1-s)] f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds; \\ H_4 &= \frac{\vartheta\text{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
\|H_1\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|H_2\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|H_3\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)} [(\nu_2^\vartheta - \nu_1^\vartheta) - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|H_4\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

We can conclude that $\|(\overline{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_2) - (\overline{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_1)\|_E \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$ by utilizing the continuity of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta$.

Likewise, for any $\nu_1, \nu_2 \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\alpha_\ell \leq \nu_1 < \nu_2 \leq \alpha_{\ell+1}$, we get

$$\|(\overline{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_2) - (\overline{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_1)\|_E \leq \sum_{i=5}^9 \|H_i\|,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
H_5 &= \mathbb{S}[\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)][u(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))] \\
H_6 &= \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\nu_1} [(\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} - (\nu_1 - s)^{\vartheta-1}] f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds; \\
H_7 &= \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} (\nu_2 - s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds; \\
H_8 &= \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\nu_1} [\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) - \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - s)] f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds; \\
H_9 &= \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\nu_1}^{\nu_2} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds.
\end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned}
\|H_5\| &\leq \mu \|\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell) - \mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)\|_{L(E)} [\|u(\alpha_\ell^-)\|_E + \|I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\|H_6\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} [(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell)^\vartheta - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta - (\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|H_7\| &\leq \frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta+1)} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|H_8\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)} [(\nu_2 - \alpha_\ell)^\vartheta - (\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta - (\nu_1 - \alpha_\ell)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1. \\
\|H_9\| &\leq \frac{\mu^2\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\Lambda}{B(\vartheta)} [(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^\vartheta] \\
&\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1.
\end{aligned}$$

From the above estimations, we realize that $\|(\overline{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_2) - (\overline{\Upsilon}u)(\nu_1)\|_E \rightarrow 0$ as $\nu_2 \rightarrow \nu_1$. Thus the operator $\overline{\Upsilon}$ is equi-continuous on B_R . By thinking of the above Steps 1-3 along with Ascoli's theorem, we observe that the operator $\overline{\Upsilon}$ is compact.

Step 4: Finally, we prove that the set

$$F = \{u \in \mathcal{C}_h'' \quad \text{such that} \quad u = \gamma\overline{\Upsilon}u \quad \text{for some} \quad 0 < \gamma < 1\}$$

is bounded.

Let $u \in F$, then $u(\alpha) = \gamma\overline{\Upsilon}u(\alpha)$ for some $0 < \gamma < 1$. For each $\alpha \in [0, \alpha_1]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\|u(\alpha)\|_E &\leq \gamma \left[\frac{\|\mathbb{S}\|\|\mathbb{T}\|(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))\|_E ds \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{\vartheta\|\mathbb{S}\|^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \|\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s)\|_{L(E)} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))\|_E ds \right] \\
&\leq \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))\|_E ds
\end{aligned}$$

and for $\alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}]$, $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\|u(\alpha)\|_E \\
&\leq \mu\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\|u(\alpha_\ell^-)\|_E + \mu\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\|I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))\|_E \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))\|_E ds.
\end{aligned}$$

Then for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\|u(\alpha)\|_E &\leq \frac{\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}W}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} \\
&\quad + \frac{\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)}\right)}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [\lambda_1(s)\|v_s + \bar{u}_s\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h} \\
&\quad + \lambda_2(s)\|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))\|_E] ds \\
&\leq \frac{\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}W}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} + \frac{\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)}\right)}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} [\lambda_1^*Q_2^*\|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h}] \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \\
&\quad + \frac{\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)}\right)}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} [\lambda_1^*Q_1^* + \lambda_2^*N^*] \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \sup_{0 \leq x \leq s} \|u(x)\|_E ds \\
&\leq \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \sup_{0 \leq x \leq s} \|u(x)\|_E ds,
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\Theta_1 &= \frac{\mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}W}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} + \frac{\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)}\right)}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} [\lambda_1^*Q_2^*\|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h}] \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \\
\Theta_2 &= \frac{\left(\frac{\mu\bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}\vartheta\mu^2}{B(\vartheta)}\right)}{1 - \mu\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}} [\lambda_1^*Q_1^* + \lambda_2^*N^*].
\end{aligned}$$

Let $x^* \in [0, s]$ be such that $\sup_{0 \leq x \leq s} \|u(x)\|_E = \|u(x^*)\|_E$, $0 \leq s \leq \alpha$. If $x^* \in [0, \alpha]$, then above inequality becomes

$$\|u(\alpha)\|_E \leq \Theta_1 + \Theta_2 \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|u(s)\|_E ds. \quad (7.3.13)$$

By utilizing [32, Lemma 3.4], we can find a constant $C(\vartheta)$ and therefore (7.3.13) becomes

$$\|u(\alpha)\|_E \leq \Theta_1 \left[1 + \int_0^\alpha C(\vartheta)(\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} ds \right] \leq \Theta_1 \left[1 + \frac{C(\vartheta)\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right].$$

The result of Schaefer's fixed-point theorem [1.10.4] is that $\bar{\Upsilon}$ has a fixed point on $(-\infty, \tau]$. This completes the theorem's proof. \square

7.4 Controllability Results

The controllability of mild solutions for an impulsive ABFFDS with infinite delay of the model (7.1.2) under the Banach fixed point theorem [1.10.1] is presented and proved in this section.

Definition 7.4.1. A function $p : (-\infty, \tau] \rightarrow E$ is called a mild solution of the system (7.1.2) if the subsequent holds: $p_0 = \varphi \in \mathfrak{C}_h$ on $(-\infty, 0]$ with $\varphi(0) = 0$; $\Delta p|_{\alpha=\alpha_\ell} = I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))$, $\ell = 1, \dots, q$, the restriction of $p(\cdot)$ to the interval $[0, \tau] \setminus \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_q\}$ is continuous; $\nu \in L^2([0, \tau], \widehat{\mathcal{B}})$ and satisfies the following integral equation:

$$p(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)(p(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(p(\alpha_1^-))) \\ + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)(p(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))) \\ + \frac{\mathbb{S}\mathbb{T}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta\mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases} \quad (7.4.1)$$

where $\mathbb{S} = \zeta(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ and $\mathbb{T} = -\tilde{\gamma}A(\zeta I - A)^{-1}$ with $\zeta = \frac{B(\vartheta)}{1-\vartheta}$, $\tilde{\gamma} = \frac{\vartheta}{1-\vartheta}$ and

$$\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha) = E_\vartheta(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} \sigma^{\vartheta-1} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (7.4.2)$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha) = \alpha^{\vartheta-1} E_{\vartheta, \vartheta}(-\mathbb{T}\alpha^\vartheta) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_\Gamma e^{\sigma\alpha} (\sigma^\vartheta I - \mathbb{T})^{-1} d\sigma, \quad (7.4.3)$$

Γ denotes the Bromwich path [24].

Definition 7.4.2. If for every initial function $\varphi \in \mathfrak{C}_h$ and $p_1 \in E$, there exists a control

$\nu \in L^2([0, \tau], \widehat{\mathcal{B}})$ such that the mild solution $p(\cdot)$ of the system (7.1.2) fulfills $p(\tau) = p_1$, then the system (7.1.2) is said to be controllable on the interval $[0, \tau]$.

In addition to the conditions (A1)-(A3), we list the subsequent condition:

(A4) $\widetilde{W} : L^2([0, \tau], \widehat{\mathcal{B}}) \rightarrow E$, the linear operator described by

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{W}\nu &= + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\tau} (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} G\nu(s) ds \\ &+ \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^{\tau} \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) G\nu(s) ds, \ell = 0, 1, 2, \dots, q \end{aligned}$$

admits an inverse operator $\widetilde{W}^{-1} : E \rightarrow L^2([0, \tau], \widehat{\mathcal{B}})/\text{Ker}(\widetilde{W})$, \widetilde{W}^{-1} is bounded and there exist constants $\Lambda_1 > 0$ and $\Lambda_2 > 0$ such that $\|G\| \leq \Lambda_1$ and $\|\widetilde{W}^{-1}\| \leq \Lambda_2$.

Theorem 7.4.1. Assume that the assumptions (A1)-(A3) and (A4) are true. Then the control system (7.1.2) is exactly controllable on $[0, \tau]$ if

$$\mathfrak{F} = (1 + \Lambda_1 \Lambda_2) \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q} \left[\left(\mu \widehat{M}_\vartheta (1 + \eta_\ell) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu} (1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_\vartheta \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right) \right] < 1. \quad (7.4.4)$$

Proof. Consider the operator $N : \mathfrak{C}_h \rightarrow \mathfrak{C}_h$, described by

$$N(p)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \varphi(\alpha), & \alpha \in (-\infty, 0] \\ \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)(p(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(p(\alpha_1^-))) \\ + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)(p(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))) \\ + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_p(s) + f(s, p_s, Np(s))] ds, \\ \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q. \end{cases}$$

(7.4.5)

Utilizing the assumption (A4), for an arbitrary function $p(\cdot)$, we present the control

$$\nu_p(\alpha) = \widetilde{W}^{-1} \begin{cases} p_\tau - \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ - \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\tau \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ p_\tau - \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\tau - \alpha_1)(p(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(p(\alpha_1^-))) \\ - \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ - \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\tau \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, & \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ p_\tau - \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\tau - \alpha_\ell)(p(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))) \\ - \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds \\ - \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\tau \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) f(s, p_s, Np(s)) ds, \\ \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q. \end{cases} \quad (7.4.6)$$

Observe that if the operator N has a fixed point, the control (7.4.6) moves the system (7.1.2) from the starting state φ to the end state p_τ . By utilizing the procedure of Theorem 7.3.1, the operator $\bar{N} : \mathfrak{C}_h'' \rightarrow \mathfrak{C}_h''$ is defined by

$$(\bar{N}u)(\alpha) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(s) + f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(s) + f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))] ds, \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_1)[u(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(u(\alpha_1^-))] \\ + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(s) + f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(s) + f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))] ds, \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\alpha - \alpha_\ell)[u(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(u(\alpha_\ell^-))] \\ + \frac{\text{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha (\alpha-s)^{\vartheta-1} [G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(s) + f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))] ds \\ + \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\alpha \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\alpha-s) [G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(s) + f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)))] ds, \\ \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \end{cases}$$

where

$$\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(\alpha) = \widetilde{W}^{-1} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_\tau - \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ - \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_0^\tau \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, \quad \alpha \in [0, \alpha_1], \\ p_\tau - \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\tau - \alpha_1)(p(\alpha_1^-) + I_1(p(\alpha_1^-))) \\ - \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ - \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_1}^\tau \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, \quad \alpha \in (\alpha_1, \alpha_2], \\ \vdots \\ p_\tau - \mathbb{S}\mathcal{B}_\vartheta(\tau - \alpha_\ell)(p(\alpha_\ell^-) + I_\ell(p(\alpha_\ell^-))) \\ - \frac{\mathbb{ST}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds \\ - \frac{\vartheta \mathbb{S}^2}{B(\vartheta)} \int_{\alpha_\ell}^\tau \widehat{\mathcal{B}}_\vartheta(\tau-s) f(s, v_s + \bar{u}_s, N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s))) ds, \\ \alpha \in (\alpha_\ell, \alpha_{\ell+1}], \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q. \end{array} \right.$$

It is obvious that operator N has a unique fixed-point if and only if \bar{N} has a unique fixed-point.

Before we prove the result, first we find the following estimation:

For $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|G\nu_{v+\bar{u}}(\alpha) - G\nu_{v+\bar{u}^*}(\alpha)\|_E \\ & \leq \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q} [\Lambda_1 \Lambda_2 \mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(1 + \eta_\ell)] \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) \\ & \quad (\times) \int_0^\tau (\tau-s)^{\vartheta-1} \|G\| \|\widetilde{W}^{-1}\| [\lambda_1 \|\bar{u}_s - \bar{u}_s^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h} \\ & \quad + \lambda_2 \|N(v(s) + \bar{u}(s)) - N(v(s) + \bar{u}^*(s))\|_E] ds \\ & \leq \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q} \left[\Lambda_1 \Lambda_2 \left(\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(1 + \eta_\ell) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1-\vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right) \right] \\ & \quad (\times) \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''}. \end{aligned}$$

To prove that \bar{N} has a unique fixed-point, let $u, u^* \in \mathfrak{C}_h''$, then for all $\alpha \in [0, \tau]$, we obtain

$$\|(\bar{N}u) - (\bar{N}u^*)\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq (1 + \Lambda_1 \Lambda_2) \max_{1 \leq \ell \leq q} \left[\left(\mu \widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}}(1 + \eta_\ell) + \left(\frac{\mu \bar{\mu}(1 - \vartheta)}{B(\vartheta)\Gamma(\vartheta)} + \frac{\widehat{M}_{\mathcal{B}} \vartheta \mu^2}{B(\vartheta)} \right) (\lambda_1 Q_1^* + \lambda_2 N^*) \frac{\tau^\vartheta}{\vartheta} \right) \right] \\
&\quad (\times) \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''} \\
&\leq \mathfrak{F} \|u - u^*\|_{\mathfrak{C}_h''}.
\end{aligned}$$

In view of (7.4.4), $\mathfrak{F} < 1$ and in the perspective of the contraction mapping principle [1.10.1], we realize that \overline{N} includes a unique fixed point $u \in \mathfrak{C}_h''$. Thus the system (7.1.2) is exactly controllable on $[0, \tau]$. \square

7.5 Example

To demonstrate our theoretical findings, we first consider the following partial integro-differential system with fractional derivative of the structure

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta u(\alpha, p) &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial p^2} u(\alpha, p) + \int_{-\infty}^{\alpha} P(\alpha, p, s - \alpha) \tilde{P}(u(s, p)) ds \\
&\quad + \int_0^{\alpha} e(s, \alpha) e^{-u(s, p)} ds, \quad p \in [0, \pi], \alpha \in [0, \tau], \alpha \neq \alpha_\ell, \\
u(\alpha, 0) &= 0 = u(\alpha, \pi), \quad \alpha \geq 0, \\
u(\alpha, p) &= \varphi(\alpha, p), \quad \alpha \in (-\infty, 0], p \in [0, \pi], \\
\Delta u(\alpha_\ell)(p) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\alpha_\ell} p_\ell(\alpha_\ell - s) u(s, p) ds, \quad p \in [0, \pi],
\end{aligned} \tag{7.5.1}$$

where $\mathcal{D}_{ABC}^\vartheta$ is the Atangana-Baleanu-Caputo derivative of order $0 < \vartheta < 1$; $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_\ell < \tau$ are prefixed numbers, and $\varphi \in \mathfrak{C}_h$. Let $E = L^2[0, \pi]$, and define the operator $A : D(A) \subset E \rightarrow E$ by $Az = z''$ with the domain $D(A) := \{z \in E : z, z' \text{ are absolutely continuous, } z'' \in E, z(0) = 0 = z(\pi)\}$, then

$$Az = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 (z, z_n) z_n, \quad z \in D(A),$$

where $z_n(p) = \sqrt{2/\pi} \sin(np)$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the orthogonal set of eigenvectors of A . It is well known that A is the infinitesimal generator of an analytic semigroup $(\mathcal{B}(\alpha))_{\alpha \geq 0}$ in E and is given by

$$\mathcal{B}(\alpha)z = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \alpha} (z, z_n) z_n, \quad \forall z \in E, \text{ and every } \alpha > 0$$

which is uniformly bounded by 1 and also a compact semigroup and hence the operator $R(\lambda, A) = (\lambda I - A)^{-1}$ is compact for each $\lambda \in \rho(A)$, i.e., $A \in \mathcal{A}^\vartheta(\tilde{\alpha}_0, \omega_0)$. For additional information, we recommend the reader to refer [82].

Let $h(s) = e^{2s}$, $s < 0$, then $w = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) ds = \frac{1}{2}$, and describe

$$\|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{E}_h} = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) \sup_{\tau \in [s, 0]} \|\varphi(\tau)\|_{L^2} ds.$$

Hence, for $(\alpha, \varphi) \in [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{E}_h$, where $\varphi(\tau)(p) = \varphi(\tau, p)$, $(\tau, p) \in (-\infty, 0] \times [0, \pi]$.

Set $u(\alpha)(p) = u(\alpha, p)$,

$$\begin{aligned} f(\alpha, \varphi, Nu(\alpha))(p) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \tilde{P}(\varphi(\tau)(p)) d\tau + Nu(\alpha)(p); \\ I_\ell(\varphi)(p) &= \int_{-\infty}^0 p_\ell(-\tau) \varphi(\tau)(p) d\tau, \end{aligned}$$

where $Nu(\alpha)(p) = \int_0^\alpha e(s, \alpha) e^{-u(s, p)} ds$.

The aforementioned system (7.5.1) may then be expressed in its abstract form (7.1.1) using these parameters.

Assumption I:

The functions P, e , and \tilde{P} are fulfilling some assumptions, and $p_\ell : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous and $d_\ell = \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{p_\ell^2(-\tau)}{h(\tau)} d\tau \right) < \infty$ for $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$.

Suppose further that

- (i) The functions $\tilde{P}_i, i = 1, 2$ are continuous and $u(\tau, p), v(\tau, p)$ are continuous in $(-\infty, 0] \times [0, \pi]$,

$$0 \leq \tilde{P}_i(u(\tau)(p)) - \tilde{P}_i(v(\tau)(p)) \leq \int_{-\infty}^0 e^{2s} \|u(s, \cdot) - v(s, \cdot)\|_{L^2} ds$$

- (ii) The function $P(\alpha, p, \tau)$, continuous in $[0, \tau] \times [0, \pi] \times (-\infty, 0)$ and fulfilling

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 P^2(\alpha, p, \tau) d\tau < \tilde{C}_1, \quad \tilde{C}_1 > 0.$$

Now we can see that: For $(\alpha, \varphi, Nu(\alpha)), (\alpha, \tilde{\varphi}, Nv(\alpha)) \in [0, \tau] \times \mathfrak{E}_h \times E$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \|f(\alpha, \varphi, Nu(\alpha)) - f(\alpha, \tilde{\varphi}, Nv(\alpha))\|_{L^2} \\
&= \left[\int_0^\pi \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \left(\tilde{P}_2(\varphi(\tau)(p)) - \tilde{P}_2(\tilde{\varphi}(\tau)(p)) \right) d\tau \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + Nu(\alpha)(p) - Nv(\alpha)(p) \right\}^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \left(\tilde{P}_2(\varphi(\tau)(p)) - \tilde{P}_2(\tilde{\varphi}(\tau)(p)) \right) d\tau \right\}^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \left[\int_0^\pi \{Nu(\alpha)(p) - Nv(\alpha)(p)\}^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 e^{2s} \|\varphi(s)(\cdot) - \tilde{\varphi}(s)(\cdot)\|_{L^2} ds \right) d\tau \right\}^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \|Nu(\alpha) - Nv(\alpha)\|_{L^2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 e^{2s} \sup_{s \in [\tau, 0]} \|\varphi(s) - \tilde{\varphi}(s)\|_{L^2} ds \right) d\tau \right\}^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \|Nu(\alpha) - Nv(\alpha)\|_{L^2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) d\tau \right\}^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \|\varphi - \tilde{\varphi}\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h} + \|Nu(\alpha) - Nv(\alpha)\|_{L^2} \\
&\leq \tilde{C}_1 \sqrt{\pi} \|\varphi - \tilde{\varphi}\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h} + \|Nu(\alpha) - Nv(\alpha)\|_{L^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

If we consider $\lambda_1 = \tilde{C}_1 \sqrt{\pi}$ and $\lambda_2 = 1$, hence f fulfills (A1) and in a similar manner, we can demonstrate that I_ℓ may satisfy (A2). Further, \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{T} are bounded linear operators, hence (A3) satisfied. All the conditions of Theorem 7.3.1 have been fulfilled, so we deduced that the system (7.5.1) has a mild solution.

Assumption II:

The functions P, \tilde{P}, e and I_ℓ are fulfilling some assumptions.

Suppose further that

- (i) the function $P(\alpha, p, \tau)$ is continuous in $[0, \tau] \times [0, \pi] \times (-\infty, 0]$ and $P(\alpha, p, \tau) \geq 0$,
 $\int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) d\tau = m_1(\alpha, p) < \infty$;

(ii) the function $\tilde{P}(\cdot)$ is continuous and for each $(\tau, p) \in (-\infty, 0] \times [0, \pi], 0 \leq \tilde{P}(u(\tau)(p)) \leq \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 e^{2s} \|u(s, \cdot)\|_{L^2} ds \right)$;

(iii) the functions $p_\ell \in \mathcal{C}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$ and $d_\ell = \int_{-\infty}^0 h(s) p_\ell^2(s) ds < \infty, \ell = 1, 2, \dots, q$.

We can now observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
\|f(\alpha, \varphi, Nu(\alpha))\|_{L^2} &= \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \tilde{P}(\varphi(\tau)(p)) d\tau + Nu(\alpha)(p) dp \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 e^{2s} \|\varphi(s)(\cdot)\|_{L^2} ds \right) d\tau \right)^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_0^t e(s, \alpha) e^{-u(s,p)} ds \right)^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 e^{2s} \sup_{s \in [\tau, 0]} \|\varphi(s)\|_{L^2} ds \right) d\tau \right)^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_0^t e(s, \alpha) e^{-u(s,p)} ds \right)^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi \left(\int_{-\infty}^0 P(\alpha, p, \tau) d\tau \right)^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h} + \|Nu(\alpha)\|_{L^2} \\
&\leq \left[\int_0^\pi (m_1(\alpha, p))^2 dp \right]^{1/2} \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h} + \|Nu(\alpha)\|_{L^2} \\
&\leq \bar{m}_1(\alpha) \|\varphi\|_{\mathfrak{e}_h} + \|Nu(\alpha)\|_{L^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

If we consider $\lambda_1(\alpha) = \bar{m}_1(\alpha)$ and $\lambda_2(\alpha) = 1$, hence f fulfills (A1)*, and similarly we can prove that I_ℓ fulfills (A2)*. Since all of Theorem 7.3.3's requirements have been met, we may conclude that system (7.5.1) has a mild solution.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

- (1) On a new class of Atangana-Baleanu fractional Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusions with non-instantaneous impulses, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, 148(2021), 111075.
- (2) Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional neutral integro-differential systems with infinite delay through sectorial operators, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, 149(2021), 111042.
- (3) Existence results for Atangana-Baleanu fractional integro-differential systems with non-instantaneous impulses, *Nonlinear Studies*, 28(3)(2021), 865–877.
- (4) Non-instantaneous impulsive fractional-order delay differential systems with Mittag-Leffler kernel, *AIMS Mathematics*, Communicated, 2021.
- (5) Existence of a solution for a fractional delay differential equation with non-instantaneous impulses and Mittag-Leffler kernel, *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computing*, Communicated, 2021.
- (6) Existence and controllability of fractional integro-differential equation with infinite delay and impulsive effects, *Chaos, Solitons and Fractals*, Communicated, 2021.
- (7) A new existence results on fractional differential inclusions with state-dependent delay and Mittag-Leffler kernel in Banach space, *Analele Universitatii "Ovidius" Constanta - Seria Matematica*, Communicated, 2021.

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